

Production networks in the cultural and creative sectors: case studies from the festival and performing arts industries

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Production networks in the cultural and creative sectors: case studies from the festival and performing arts industries

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Work package	<p>The CICERONE project consists of seven work packages (WPs). This report is part of WP2, which constitutes the empirical backbone of CICERONE. It contains case study research that focuses on networked production in eight cultural and creative industries: 1) architecture, 2) archives (including libraries and cultural heritage), 3) artistic crafts, 4) audio-visual media (film, TV, videogames, multimedia) and radio, 5) design, 6) festivals, as well as performing and visual arts, 7) music and, 8) publishing. The purpose of the case study research is to understand key linkages and mechanisms in real-life CCS production networks and their relationships to context-dependent variables.</p> <p>Drawing on the case study research, the CICERONE project explores policies that may contribute to enhancing the impact of the cultural and creative sectors on competitiveness, cultural diversity and environmental sustainability. It also explores how to support post-Covid recovery of the sector itself. Furthermore, the case study research also facilitates the identification of gaps in extant sources of quantitative data, suggesting approaches on how these can be plugged. For this reason, WP2 is not just the empirical backbone of the CICERONE project, it also provides critical inputs for the work in other WPs (most notably WP4 and WP6).</p> <p>This deliverable (D2.6a) reports on the case studies on festivals and performing arts. Together with the reports D2.1 to D2.5, D2.6b, D2.7 and D2.8, it provides strategic snapshots of the rich and variegated tapestry of European production networks (both within and across industries).</p> <p>All the deliverables from the CICERONE project are publicly disclosed on the project's website www.cicerone-project.eu and through its Zenodo community on https://zenodo.org/communities/cicerone-h2020.</p>

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Introduction

Festivals and performing arts come in all shapes and sizes. From a three-day music festival with over 100,000 international visitors and performers from different countries to a village festival which primarily caters to a local audience with local artists celebrating local traditions. The same can be said with regard to performers. They range from megastars such as Adele to buskers who every now and then are hired by a club or café. What these all have in common, though, is the key element of performances in front of a live audience, which, in principle, pays to see the show. Furthermore, each such performance is 'ephemeral, meaning that it is supplied at a specific moment in time and, when a performance is over, the service it supplied has disappeared'. Indeed, these events 'are supplied one at a time and the same resources must be replicated at each performance regardless of the size of the audience' (Towse, 2010: 199).

Festival art practices have existed since antiquity. In the modern world, festivals are forums for the appreciation and celebration of human abilities, and they encompass the entire spectrum of art types, genera, movements, styles and schools. Through festivals, professional communities and art connoisseurs exchange ideas and share valuable experiences. Their fruits, in turn, enrich the arts with new expressions and messages. Festivals carry forward and promote traditions, but they are also a kind of laboratory for experiments in artistic expression. Festivals are a powerful tool for making sense of local, national and civilizational cultural identity. Moreover, they foster the transfer of ideas, including across opposing religious, ethnic, ideological and political lines.

Festivals, through their programmes, reflect the most significant artistic facts and events that have remained out of sight of many people. Festivals are a democratic tool for creating an educated and competent audience (Kutin, 2018). The impact of festivals cannot be overstated. Not only do they support and stimulate the local development of settlements in all aspects of urban planning, economy, social activities, education and arts, they also result in diverse forms of solidarity and advocacy of causes. Indeed, festivals declare commitment and empathy to the authors, performers, producers and attendees. They offer the opportunity to both professional artists and amateurs to give a special performance.

This report examines the production networks of projects in the festival and performing arts sector in Europe, with a special focus on the Netherlands and Bulgaria. Drawing on statistical analysis and semi-structured interviews with actors involved in various phases of the production network, this report provides insights into general, shared aspects of the architectural design sector as well as into more case-specific features. With the selection of the four case studies presented below, the CICERONE project has aimed at grasping at least some of that multidimensional diversity.

The CICERONE approach to production networks

The point of departure for the analysis of the CCS is the Global Production Network (GPN) approach, which was developed by Neil Coe and Henry Yeung on the basis of the Global Value Chain (GVC) approach (Coe & Yeung, 2015; Kloosterman, Pratt, D’Ovidio, Greco & Borén, 2019). The GPN approach is increasingly used to unravel production networks that involve a complex cross-border spatial division of labour. Such production networks have proliferated across many sectors as a consequence of technological advances in communication and transport as well as due to the liberalisation and deregulation of trade (Kano et al. 2020). These processes have also affected (many) CCSs. However, the GPN approach has rarely been applied to them (Coe, 2015 is an exception). By opting for this innovative approach to the CCS, the CICERONE project generated new insights on its functioning.

In a sense, we have used the GPN method to spatialise. Sociological approaches were already proposed by Howard Becker (Becker, 1982), with his concept of the *art world*, and by Pierre Bourdieu (Bourdieu, 1996), who developed the concept of *field*. Both approaches, the differences between them notwithstanding (Buttero & Crossley, 2011), aim at embedding the process of creation into a broader societal setting and at going beyond the identification of individual genius. When we use the GPN approach, we cannot simply position the CCS in that broad context – we must also highlight its spatial footprint. We thus employ the GPN approach as a tool for analysing a wide variety of production networks in the CCS. In other words, the approach is a heuristic tool that explains how the products of the CCS progress from inception to sale and whether and how they may be preserved for future generations.

On the pages that follow, we first briefly summarise the key elements of the GPN approach that guided our fieldwork. Thereafter, we focus on the process by which we selected the units of analysis for our case studies. This section is followed by an explanation of the manner in which our sample of case studies lays the foundation for a concise typology of the CCS which can be used by policymakers to devise more targeted combinations of interventions to foster economic growth and employment as well as social and cultural diversity.

Key elements of the GPN approach

Phases and the spatial footprint

Evidently, the most obvious feature of the GPN approach is the carving up of the value chain into distinct value-adding stages which can unfold in different locations and which may involve different sets of actors (including other firms). We have inserted the archiving phase into the value-adding stages because many (if not all) of those who participate in cultural and creative endeavours draw on the works of their predecessors in one way or another (Pratt, 1997). Therefore, in the CICERONE project, we, in principle, distinguish between the following stages:

- 1) Creation (the initial conception of an idea or a set of ideas that define aesthetic quality),
- 2) Production (the realisation of those ideas through an actual good or service),
- 3) Distribution (the sale of the good or the presentation of the service in front of an audience),
- 4) Exchange (the wider setting which enables distribution), and
- 5) Archiving (the formal preservation of the cultural product).

Creation

It is in this part of the cycle that new ideas, processes or approaches are devised. The notion of “creation”, in the sense in which the term is used here, is a social one – what is new is also relational, situated and conditional. Therefore, a “creative process”, that is, a method, is involved (“design” is an example). Reference is also made to history and to previous instances of creation (the preceding stage). Sometimes, this is referred to as “ideation”, that is, having ideas.

Production

An idea or a creative new thing remains provisional, potential and conditional until it can be stabilised or made. The intervening period is often called the prototype stage. Usually, the product is also developed during the multiple (or mass) production phase. Technology and labour costs, production decisions, and technological and regulatory standards affect costs and potential access to the products. Marketing and advertising are also relevant, but we allocate them to the exchange phase here.

Distribution or circulation

Products, even if they are new and unusual, are unformed and inaccessible unless they can be moved or migrated to markets or audiences. Physical distribution is clearly a key issue for access and reach. The same is true of digital approaches, which may overcome some barriers. Generally, distribution systems (or platforms) are expensive to develop and susceptible to monopoly control.

Exchange

Exchange is the stage at which the product of service engages the audience or customers. It is a critical moment of information exchange, and one in which (e)valuation occurs. That (e)valuation may take forms as varied as market transaction, participation or critique. Values are made and stabilised at this stage. Therefore, marketing and expectation setting provide a link to distribution. In the experience economy, and particularly in the cultural one, the negotiation of value is a critical element of the transaction, and institutions have been developed that normalise it and reduce risks. The engagement of the audience or consumer is also shaped directly by advertising and marketing – to refer to the previous stages once more, the exchange process can determine which products are available for production and distribution.

Archiving

Since cultural value is relational, history and cultural diversity always interact with the present. Moreover, the process of reflection and learning (or that of rejection) is part of the critical appreciation

of culture. The archiving of culture creates both normative structures that enable cultural production systems and the disruptive elements that facilitate new approaches. This stage also includes education (of audiences or consumers as well as of creative practitioners), institutions such as universities and media systems, and repositories such as libraries, museums and galleries. It is at this point that heritage is identified and later mobilised via the production system. More generally, archiving constitutes the resource from which new ideas are developed, which refers back to creation.

Source: D'Ovidio et al., 2019

We treat this model of the phases as a *point of departure*, not as a given, and we employ the case studies to explore the extent to which these distinctions may explain production in the CCS. As Throsby (Throsby, 2010, p. 25) observed, in some production processes in the CCS, there is no simple and neat sequence, and “[t]he apparent linearity of the value chain may be replaced, for some cultural products, by something more akin to a value network, where multiple inputs, feedback loops, and a pervasive ‘value-creating ecology’ replaces a simple stage-wise process”. Although he was rightly critical of the slavish application of a value chain approach to the CCS, he also observed that “[f]rom a policy point of view, depicting the cultural production process as a value chain allows an analysis of the effects of policy intervention at various points in the chain. For example, in assessing the impacts of existing policy measures, or in determining the optimal point at which to apply prospective measures, the policy analyst can use the value-chain concept to clarify where the effects of intervention have been or will be felt, and who are the affected stakeholders upstream or downstream from the point of intervention”.

It therefore stands to reason that one should start with the conceptual framework of these stages and then determine which phases can be identified as distinct, which boundaries are blurred and which phases overlap or are deeply intertwined. Subsequently, we locate phases or combinations of phases – the spatial footprint – and we identify the parties that are involved. In this manner, we extend our focus beyond creation to include other parts of the input-output structure of the CCS.

Governance

The second element that we derive from the GPN approach and which we use to open the black box of the production network is the concept of governance. The complex global value chains and production networks which have been studied (mostly in manufacturing) typically exhibit asymmetrical power structures, with one lead firm engaging in explicit coordination (Gereffi, 2005). This lead firm may be involved in the production phase (producer-driven chain) or in the distribution phase (buyer-driven chain). If power dynamics are asymmetric and a lead firm takes charge of coordinating the network, it may be inferred that it is capable of forcing the other actors to act in a certain way but also that it can capture much of the value that is created in the network. Similarly to our approach to the stages, we do not take the existence of a lead firm in the CCS for granted. Instead, we attempt to identify a more explicit hierarchical power distribution or a more dispersed horizontal

one. Furthermore, we do not assume that the presence of a lead firm or actor necessarily results in an asymmetrical distribution of (economic) value, and we examine this issue as a research question.

Embeddedness

The third element that we use to understand the production networks of the CCS is that of embeddedness. In his seminal work on the transformation of the British economy in the 19th century, Karl Polanyi (Polanyi, 1957) emphasised the importance of the institutional context in which all economic actions are embedded. In this context, differences in embeddedness affect economic actions, the likelihood of their occurrence, the manner in which they unfold and their consequences (Granovetter, 1985). This view became widespread in economic sociology, organisation studies, strategic management (Smelser & Swedberg, 2005) and, somewhat later, in economic geography. The GPN approach explicitly aims to apply embeddedness to make sense of the spatial footprint of the production network: why are such-and-such activities located in such-and-such places? According to Kleiber and Horner (Kleibert & Horner, 2018), the operations of actors within the same universalistic category of a transnational production system is very much contingent on their embeddedness in a particular society, place and social network. Embeddedness thus becomes crucial for understanding the spatial and social division of labour within a production network. The forms of embeddedness are also critical for the design of effective policies for the CCS (Salder, 2022).

We have adopted the multi-layered approach to embeddedness that Coe and Yeung (2015) proposed. We therefore distinguish between three levels of embeddedness.

- i. Societal embeddedness: the influence of institutional contexts on the actions taken by actors in production networks (rules, laws and regulations) which are mainly located at the EU level and the national level.
- ii. Territorial embeddedness: the local context of the location where a certain activity takes place, which is closely related to local clusters and ecosystems with distinct sets of agglomeration economies that selectively sustain and foster economic activities (Scott, 2000).
- iii. Network embeddedness: the linkages between different actors and the functional and social connectivity of those relationships (e.g. social network relationships based on trust).

As with the phases, the boundaries between these forms of embeddedness are not set in stone. Place-based communities are an essential element of agglomeration economies, but they are also closely linked to social networks. We analyse these levels of embeddedness more comprehensively.

Unit of analysis

The CCS are characterised by their emphasis on unique aesthetic qualities and, importantly, on near-infinite horizontal differentiation (Caves, 2000), volatile (cross-sectoral) cooperation, and, crucially,

forms of collaboration that are often ad hoc and usually involve several actors with different skills and functions. Those forms of collaboration often permeate the legal boundaries of firms. This particular way of producing involves, as a result, “complex teams – the motley crew property”, as well as “close temporal coordination of their activities” (Caves, 2000, p.8). Watson (Watson, 2012, p. 617) added that “[t]he complexity of the [jointly produced product or service] necessitates the coordination of multidisciplinary skills” and that permanent centralisation is not economically efficient (Lorenzen & Frederiksen, 2005). Production must often be completed under severe time constraints (Hobday, 2000; Staber, 2004) Temporary networks, interpersonal collaboration and projects in the CCS are therefore very much intertwined. As de Klerk (de Klerk, 2015, p. 829) observed, “[t]he dynamic environment in the industry is mostly project-based... thus often obliging these workers to find alternative employment between projects to optimise their limited work opportunities. Bricolage results from working arrangements structured by festivals or special assignments where creative workers move in and out of networks as they are needed”.

The GPN approach has mainly been used to analyse the large-scale production of goods. Some CCSs, such as parts of the fashion industry, seem to fit this format of production well. However, at least a some CCS activities are different from the usual subjects of the GPN literature, which tends to focus on production networks in which large firms manufacture large volumes of standardised goods. In other segments, small firms predominate. Instead of churning out many similar (tangible) products, they focus on creating products, such as goods and services, in small numbers (often just one) that require production networks to be more or less ad hoc. The composition of those networks typically fluctuates. A performance, a song or an album, a painting and the design of a theatre are all unique products which are typically created by such ad hoc production networks that vary from product to product (Power & Hallencreutz, 2002; Power & Jansson, 2004; Pratt, 2006).

It must be noted that projects in some CCSs are less volatile (for example, the spring and summer collection and the autumn and winter collection of a large fashion firm, which may involve the same designers, suppliers and sellers). Therefore, they resemble the type of networks which are prominent in the GPN literature. In other CCSs, such as architectural design or festivals, the composition of the networks is much more variable and contextual, and sequences of projects may have different networks and stakeholders.

In order to cover production networks in the CCS that are volatile and project based, we focus in most case studies on projects as a unit of analysis. This approach is very much in line with the literature on the forms of collaboration in the cultural and creative industries. In more recent economic-geographic studies and in sociological research on CCS, project-based work, which involves a multiplicity of organisational and personal social networks, is a key component of the analysis (see Watson, 2012 for a very thorough overview). Notably, studies on labour conditions in the CCS have benefited from departing from the project-based approach. The important role of project-based work has been corroborated in many CCSs (de Klerk, 2015).

In the CCS, then, the firm should not be granted a privileged ontological status. Instead, networks should be central. One could even go a step further and conceptualise the firm as a more permanent or sustained project or as a collection of long-term projects (although it is evidently subject to recombination and change) that has been solidified into a legal entity. The temporal dimension of the project and therefore of its network then become a crucial variable for the case studies. This shift evidently dovetails into our GPN approach, which emphasises the role of networks. In the CICERONE project, we conceive of these networks not *a priori* in terms of firms but in terms of interpersonal networks that are organised around a specific project. In *Art Worlds*, Howard Becker also highlighted interpersonal relationships (Becker, 1982). Our focus also allows us to emphasise the role of cultural value, which may trump economic value, and the salience of motives other than profit maximisation, especially in the creation phase. These distinguishing features of the CCS have significant consequences for the functioning of its production networks.

A more practical advantage of circling on specific projects is that it enabled us to select respondents more easily – we could simply focus on those individuals who were involved in a given project. It then also became easier to limit the number of respondents (only project-related key or lead actors or firms, strategic partners, strategic suppliers and key customers) that we had to consider.

Selection of cases

The main purpose of the CICERONE project is to provide a new foundation for CCS policies on the basis of a production network approach that generates novel insights on the functioning of the CCS and its cultural and social impact. Our approach situates the CCS in networks of production that extend far beyond the creation phase. We use case studies to map the configuration of production networks and to analyse relationships between actors in creation, production, distribution, exchange and archiving. The case studies are thus intended to uncover linkages and mechanisms within these production networks and to lay the foundation for more informed policies which not only extend beyond the creation phase but also take spatial footprints and governance structures into account.

Business models within the CCS vary widely. That variance obtains not only across sectors but also within them. There are differences in staff numbers, turnover, type of products, barriers to entry, the use of technology, capital needs, end markets and strategies, to name but a few. Networks also differ in terms of power relationships, shape and organisation, and the nature, complexity and geography of their linkages. At present, no data sets cover these characteristics comprehensively. Representative sampling is certainly not feasible within the timeframe of the CICERONE project. The investigation of the variance in question, accordingly, is a voyage into uncharted waters.

We have therefore opted for a purposive selection of cases, whereby researchers select the units to be sampled on the basis of their knowledge, which in our case is the background research that we conducted prior to the cases studies. The aim of this selection was to include cases which may

plausibly be assumed to represent a sufficient range of easily assessable variations in key business model characteristics, notably staffing and turnover. This approach yielded cases that typify a significant proportion of the population of the CCS while also exhibiting sufficient differences to represent its variability (Gerring, 2007). In the case study reports that follow, each case study is positioned within the wider sector.

Typology matrix

While the case studies are intended to present a rich picture of the key mechanisms and the main linkages that show how spatial footprints, governance structures and levels of embeddedness are intertwined in real-life situations, a higher level of abstraction that transcends the study of individual production networks must be accessed if general insights are to be derived. We must simplify characteristics and relationships in order to present a clear narrative for policymakers. The key elements of our approach – spatial footprints, governance structures and multi-layered embeddedness – guided us in reducing the complexity of the case studies so as to distil insights from findings.

The first step is to position concrete cases from the CCS in a simple grid which combines the spatial footprint with the governance structure. The two variables are crucial determinants of societal effects. A completely local production network with a horizontal governance structure and a mainly global and hierarchical network that is coordinated by a lead firm or actor differ starkly in their social, economic and cultural impact and in the policy interventions that they require. Furthermore, if creation is local but production and distribution are global, targeting policy only at the creation phase may have unforeseen consequences for the wider network.

In principle, the typology matrix of production networks distinguishes between different phases. Since these phases may overlap, as is the case of many forms of visual art, they may be merged. For each phase or set of phases, it is possible to determine whether a single actor is in charge of all activities. Different phases may then exhibit different governance structures. It may also be the case that one actor is ultimately in charge of the whole network and is clearly present in the coordination of each phase. Alternatively, a small number of actors may control the network. The typology matrix allows more nuanced representations of this kind. Using this typology matrix enables us to draw cross-sectoral comparisons between cases and therefore to depart from the conventional siloed approaches. We expect that certain combinations will transpire to be much more likely to occur than others: the likelihood of a small local network having a more horizontal governance structure is evidently much higher than that of a complex and truly global network adopting such a form of governance, which requires much more extensive coordination.

CCSs are embedded in multi-layered contexts, which range from the EU and the national level to that of the territorial and social network. Our empirical work shows how these contexts affect individual

cases. Cross-case analysis shows how the forms of embeddedness are related to the typology matrix more generally. Power relations, for instance, may also depend on institutional conditions. Those conditions may allow an actor to assume leadership or to take advantage of the network.

This typology matrix is a starting point for an exploration of the potential role of hard policy levers (e.g. tax breaks, subsidies and such like) and soft policy levers (e.g. strengthening the institutional framework, establishing platforms for collaboration, improving education and so on) that various policymakers at different spatial levels may in principle manipulate. Policy makers can use this typology matrix as a tool for assessing the key characteristics of the concrete CCS populations, which may be defined narrowly or widely, whose societal impact they wish to improve. Filling this typology matrix clearly also requires new sets of data which allow the larger CCS populations to be profiled.

The typology matrix is crucial to constructing an overarching narrative that transcends the idiosyncrasies of individual cases. Moreover, it supplies a basis for our policy recommendations, which are phase and location specific and must be sensitive to the organisation of network governance. We strove for high uniformity to enable comparisons. We present a guide to achieving that goal below.

It is often difficult to compress information for a whole production network on the spatial footprint dimension from the outset. Instead, we divide the network into phases and then locate the actors in each phase. This process yields a refined stepwise analysis of the production network. The next step is to summarise the findings for the whole network. Production networks may be local from the creation phase to archiving or global from start to finish. It may also be the case that creation and production are entirely local or regional but distribution and exchange are national or even global. Identifying such spatial footprints would convey important information to policy makers.

Similarly, we adopt a stepwise approach to assessing the organisation of network governance. For each phase, we inquire which actor initiates, organises, monitors and controls activities. It may be that one actor is in charge of the whole network. It may also be the case that two actors are in charge of different phases. A more horizontal governance configuration without clear leading actors is also a possibility. How policies impact production networks depends on their governance configurations. Throwing money at a specific cultural and creative industry which is controlled by a transnational corporation that is located outside the EU would be a different proposition from financing a network in which the leading actor is close to the others, in the same country or even in the same city.

We use the typology matrix to systematise the classification of the cases that we studied. This matrix must be completed by using the actor categories in Table 2. We use the labels from Table 2 to ensure consistency.

Table 1. The typology matrix

PRODUCTION NETWORK PHASES	Local/regional	National	Intra-EU	Global	GOVERNANCE
Creation					
Production					
Distribution					
Exchange					
Archiving					
Network level					Lead actor/multiple actors/horizontal

Table 2. Key actors in the production networks

Creators	Actors who participate in the initial creation (individuals, such as writers and musicians, or collectives, such as fashion brands and film crews)
Suppliers (specialised)	Suppliers that provide specialised/dedicated services or products and are hard to replace in the short term
Strategic partners (private sector)	Providers of strategic resources (capital, labour, knowledge and certifications) such as banks, educational institutions, professional associations, tastemakers and critics
Strategic partners (civil society)	Actors that operate at neither the state level nor the market level and which provide essential goods, services or resources (funding, labour, information and certifications)
Strategic partners (public sector, multilevel)	Public sector actors at the level of the EU, the national, the regional or the local government that provide strategic resources (e.g. funding and certifications)
Distributors	Actors (individual or collective) in charge of delivering the good or service to the customer or consumer
Consumers	B2C (business to consumer): final market with large number of buyers
Customer	B2B (business to business): final market, typically with a single buyer (e.g. real estate firm commissioning a design for a building)
Lead actor(s)	Actor(s) who initiates, organises, monitors and controls the activities of the network

Phases

We depart from the GPN approach with its five phases. In many cases, however, the phases overlap, and borders are blurred. Such issues can be addressed easily by merging the cells for phases that overlap or by drawing dotted lines if the phases are distinct but their boundaries are blurred.

The spatial scales

We distinguish between four scales: the local or the regional, the national, the intra-EU and the global. These scales, in principle, correspond to different policymakers and, in many cases, also to different policies (from local policies to provide workspaces through national subsidy programmes to EU competition regulations and trade policies). The anchor point for *the local or regional* scale is the point at which initial creation occurs, that is, the point at which the aesthetic component of the good or service is created. This spatial level may coincide with a particular city, a large metropolitan area or a rural region. The origin of the value chain may be located elsewhere, as in the case of architectural design, a domain in which the customer may be located across the globe. However, our focus here is on the first moves of concrete actors from a specific CCS. We then inquire, for each phase, where the other key actors in the production network are located. The location of an activity is where the actors are from: e.g., flying in a choreographer from Norway and a light engineer from Israel to create a modern dance work in The Hague is still a form of global import.

Governance

Governance pertains to the whole network. We distinguish between three options: a) networks with a lead actor, b) networks with multiple lead actors (not more than 2 or 3) and c) bottom-up horizontal arrangements.

PART 1. The European production network of festivals and performing arts: an overview

1.1 Overview of the festival and performing arts industry

1.1.1 Goods and services

Festivals and performing arts are considered ‘a presentation of live art to a live audience; if recorded or displayed on a screen, a performance falls under other domains (e.g. Film)’ (ESSnet-Culture, 2012). The industry includes theatre, musicals, opera, ballet, dance, cabaret and circus. UNESCO (2009) includes festivals as a sub-industry of the performing arts. Below, we delve into the key economic characteristics of the services produced in this industry.

The European Commission (2017) listed number of key economic characteristics that, despite the great diversity in products, apply to all festivals and performances. Below, these characteristics are listed briefly.

Experience goods

The value and quality of art are difficult to determine. The enjoyment of performances depends on personal experiences and may differ from person to person. To evaluate a performance, one must have seen the act and experienced it (Johnson, 2014). This assessment, furthermore, is largely based on interpretation and not on ‘objective’ criteria, given the fact that the quality of a performance is first and foremost symbolic.

Scarce commodities

Performances typically take place in dedicated venues or at certain festival sites that offer space for a limited number of visitors. As a result, the services might also be scarce *positional goods* (i.e. goods and services that people value because of their limited supply), given the inevitable limits to the size of any venue and the busy schedule of performers. The potential audience may even be many times larger than a venue allows, but increased demand can only be met by an increase in the costs of a larger venue (if possible) or more performances. Supply, then, turns out to be rather inelastic (Haller, 2013). Because there are few substitutes for these unique events, groups of consumers are often willing (and able) to pay significant sums of money (with ticket prices on the black market considerably higher than the official price) to attend a performance by a famous artist (Trentmann, 2016; Currid-Halkett, 2018). As a result, touring has become very profitable for many artists and has become their main source of income (pre-Covid-19).

Merit goods

Festivals and performances can also be considered merit or public goods, which 'are provided by the public sector irrespective of consumer demand, where the usual operation of consumer sovereignty is set aside in favour of the government's own preferences' (Throsby, 2010: 60). They can be considered beneficial for society in general as they may be associated with several types of positive externalities, such as traditions, education, social cohesion, national prestige and international recognition. These spill overs mean that governments are often willing to subsidise parts of the event (EC, 2017).

Risky goods

Performances and festivals are risky goods to invest in. The events require high upfront costs, and returns on investment are uncertain. Cultural consumption is unpredictable because of several factors (e.g. unexpected weather). In addition, artists and festival organisations face high levels of competition. The 'winner takes all' characteristic creates what Richard Caves (2000) calls the 'nobody knows' property: some will be hits, and many others will be misses. And this is hard to tell beforehand. Because of this uncertainty, those active in festivals and performing arts often receive public subsidy.

Cost-disease

Another characteristic of festivals and performing arts is their vulnerability to Baumol's cost-disease. The basic resource of performing is human labour in a much more direct and palpable sense than in most other economic activities. Human labour is both the initial and final product, and substitution through capital is in many cases difficult. As a result, labour productivity in the performing arts is, in principle, hard to raise (Baumol & Bowen, 1966). Based on extensive observations, Baumol and Bowen concluded that the financial problems of the performing arts do not diminish but intensify over time and that stage organisations are doomed to suffer a 'gap' between revenue and expense.

According to Baumol's cost-disease, it is difficult to increase labour productivity in services because of a low substitutability between labour and capital, whereas in many manufacturing activities mechanisation and automation can boost labour productivity on a long-term basis (Throsby, 2010). According to Baumol's cost-disease, increases in production costs caused by increases in wages in line with jobs in other sectors of the economy cannot (or can only very partially) be compensated through increases in labour productivity. Moreover, price increases are also difficult because they would dampen the demand for these services and, hence, supply. Raising the supply of performing arts above this equilibrium level set by the market would require extra funding either from the state in the form of subsidies or from private actors in the form of patronage. The dependence of the performing arts on external funding above this equilibrium level points to the inherent importance of the institutional context and the role of the state more specifically.

Although Baumol's cost-disease certainly affects many performing arts, it is, however, not the whole story. First, productivity can be increased in the performing arts through capital substitution.

Electronic amplification of sound and image through large screens and electronic instruments have made it possible to increase the size of the audience to crowds of over 100,000 for a single performance while also making it possible to decrease the number of musicians (from a symphony orchestra of some 80 to 100 musicians) to a jazz band (with just over 10 musicians) to a rock band (with four or five members) to just one DJ playing electronic dance music to large crowds.

Complex goods

Finally, these events can also be considered complex goods, as they require a lot of cooperation and coordination between a wide range of actors along the value chain (EC, 2017). These actors have different critical resources and have to come together at the right time in each of the production stages.

Intrinsic complexity

As mentioned above, festivals and performances are complex goods that require close coordination between many stakeholders. Events depend on specific resources from artists, producers, technical crews, agents, promoters, ticket distributors, investors, venue owners, journalists, municipalities and other public authorities. The festival organisation has to coordinate these flows in different stages of production to make sure that everything is ready for the festival or performance. In addition, in some cases, performers (often established A-list artists) will bring along their own technical crew, which makes coordination even more complicated.

Moreover, demand for cultural consumption of these events is unpredictable (cf. Caves, 2000), and costs are high upfront, making them risky goods. Determining the initial price for an event is a matter of 'balancing the costs of production or cost of buying a production, the consumer's willingness to pay, and the expected revenue from other sources, such as subsidies or earned income from other productions or performances' (EC, 2017, p. 72). Because demand for these cultural goods is unpredictable, long-term planning is difficult. However, to stimulate the production of performances, many governments provide subsidies for this cultural industry. Local authorities believe that festivals and performing arts can generate socio-economic benefits. An event is able to 'improve the city's image, create place distinctiveness and draw visitors and tourists' (Van Aalst & Van Melik, 2011, p. 196). Cities may even compete with each other to attract and host events in order to raise their profile. In some cases, local authorities may guarantee a subsidy for several years to retain the event.

Dynamics over time

The performing arts and festival industry have changed over the years because of developments such as digitalisation and globalisation. Below, we explore these developments and their influence on the services produced in this industry.

Digitalisation

Compared to other cultural and creative sectors, such as the music industry, performing arts and festivals are less exposed to the digital shift (European Commission, 2017). Technology has (to a large extent) not forced the sector to transform its business model because the core element of the business model remains live performances. Events are first and foremost experience goods, which have to be consumed and enjoyed during the actual performance. Digitalisation does not fundamentally change this essential characteristic of performances as live experiences.

However, digitalisation has fundamentally altered the production process. In the creation, production and exchange phases, digitalisation has introduced special video technologies; experimentation with art forms, such as virtual stages and holograms; and stronger amplifiers and audio speakers to reach larger groups. In addition, the digital shift may also have improved artists' bargaining positions. Through social media, artists have an online platform to show performances to audiences. This makes them less dependent on intermediaries (European Commission, 2017). In the distribution phase, new financing mechanisms, such as crowdfunding, online ticket sales and online marketing, have taken over.

Finally, the archiving phase has also changed significantly because of digitalisation. Consumers themselves are one of the most important actors in this stage. For instance, festival attendees post videos and photos of events online to their social media accounts, thereby documenting and spreading awareness of the events.

Globalisation

Since the end of the 1970s, there has been marked growth in the number of festivals. Frey (2011) shows how festivals often deal with lower wage costs because performers do not need fixed contracts with a permanent cultural operator (Towse, 2010). In addition, this increase in festival numbers can also partly be explained by the external trend of globalisation. Artists can travel around more easily and perform in different countries. Touring has become profitable for many artists and has become their main source of income. The mobility of consumers has also increased as they may travel to other countries to see their favourite artists perform.

However, according to EC (2017, p. 84), global sourcing (which is 'the provision of goods and services from international markets beyond geopolitical boundaries') is still not common. The performing arts industry is typically locally oriented. Linguistic, cultural and geographical aspects are central to these events and can, therefore, act as barriers to global sourcing. As explained by EC (2017, p. 61), 'certain performances are constrained by language barriers (e.g. cabaret, performances by stand-up comedians), substantially limiting the internationalisation process'.

1.1.2 Labour

Festivals and performing arts are often complex events. They often depend on an array of actors, each of which brings a different critical resource. They then have to come together at the right time for each of the production stages. They thus display what Richard Caves (2000: 8) has called ‘the motley crew’ property. In his view, ‘[t]he performing arts and creative activities involv[e] complex teams’ and ‘obviously require close temporal coordination of their activities’. Getz (1991, p. 15), who published a series of studies on festivals, makes a similar point but casts a wider net by also including users and those who are directly affected by the events. He refers to these actors as *event stakeholders*: ‘those people and groups with a stake in the event and its outcomes, including all groups participating in the event production, sponsors and grant-givers, community representatives, and everyone impacted by the event’. To organise festivals and performing arts, many stakeholders must interact and collaborate. These stakeholders can be individual or collective actors, public or private sector actors, or members of volunteer organisations (Presenza & Iocca, 2012).

Creation

The first phase of the production process starts with the creation of a concept for the event (defining the event’s purpose and its interest groups) (Allen et al., 2008). The event promoter has to apply this purpose to the particular context and environment in which the event will take place. A management team conducts research on their event concept and its feasibility. This includes examining the demand for their event and how a target audience might respond to it, and consequently which stakeholders and resources are needed to produce the event (Caciur, 2012). This second step – creating and coordinating a network of stakeholders – is necessary to start the production phase. Therefore, the management must gather a clear picture of all the stakeholders they depend on. Thus, in the creation phase, the event promoter and management team start to assemble a production network of stakeholders in order to fulfil the concept purpose of the event.

Production

During the production phase, the event promoter starts planning the event by contacting several stakeholders, described below.

Venue owner

First, the event promoter must decide on a venue and get in touch with the owner. Logistics are important for ensuring that all stakeholders, resources and equipment can reach the location at the right time. In addition, factors such as costs (rent), capacity of the location (accommodations) and legal issues (possible constraints) have to be taken into consideration (Caciur, 2012).

Local authorities

Local authorities may play a key role because they decide on permits and, in some cases, own the venues, provide public transport and facilities, and offer financial support. They are, therefore, frequently a powerful and dominant stakeholder. However, at the same time, local governments are increasingly aware of the potential benefits of cultural events in terms of generating income and jobs on a local level and increasing the visibility and identity of places (Van Aalst & Van Melik, 2011, p. 196). This awareness has fostered mutually dependent relationships. If a local government is involved in providing not just permits but also resources for organising and realising an event, it usually wants to evaluate the local economic impacts of the event as well as the social and environmental impacts. Local governments, in many cases, even compete with each other in attracting events. This, consequently, enhances the negotiating power of event promoters.

Investors and sponsors

An event promoter has to seek sponsors and financial investors. Festivals and performing arts often depend on a mixed model of public and private financial aid. The degree of subsidy depends on the size and expected external positive outcomes of an event. Small-scale events often have lower production costs and therefore require less financial assistance. In addition, event promoters have to contact tourism traders and transport companies to ensure that a given location has sufficient capacity to welcome a large audience.

Artists and suppliers of equipment

Finally, the artists and suppliers of light and sound equipment need to be approached. In the production phase, technical staff must think about the construction of different stages, and the artists need to start rehearsing their performances. The method of approaching artists varies according to the status and size of the event. Negotiations are crucial to establish contact with artists and their managers. Some artists are represented by themselves, while others have a promotional agency or a manager. Depending on their popularity, some artists have more negotiating power than others. In addition, more well-known artists often travel with their own personnel, such as roadies, technicians and stylists (Allen et al., 2008). At large events, promoters often use backwards scheduling, in which a few popular 'headliners' are scheduled first (taking into account the time length), and others are scheduled backwards from there (Ahlberg, 2011).

Distribution

In the distribution phase, the promotion of the event takes place. Typically, the event promoter partially hands over their power to actors who have more reach to inform possible audiences. The event promoter provides instructions to other actors on their marketing strategy and the audience they hope to attract.

Media specialised firms

A firm specialising in communications and event promotion is often hired to design a festival's communication strategy (defining the audience segments to reach out to) and its promotion tools and materials (e.g. an event's visual identity and website as well as the design of catalogues, programmes and PR actions). Other actors, such as sponsors and media actors, help in spreading awareness of the event. For example, media actors can be influential by sharing their enthusiasm about the concept (Caciur, 2012). In addition, with the arrival of new social media, artists themselves have the opportunity to promote an event. They are able to share information on upcoming events (e.g. dates and location) with their fan base.

Exchange

In the exchange phase, the actual event takes place. Depending on the event, this can take a few hours, a day or several days. During the event, almost all stakeholders become active, creating a temporary peak in the demand for labour. This peak is often met by outsourcing, hiring part-time employees and finding volunteers. In this stage, artists perform, audiences consume, security guards monitor, employees and volunteers sell beverages, and technicians manage sound and lighting. In addition, merchandise sellers, tourism traders and critics work during the event. Finally, the event promoter coordinates and supervises the event.

Archiving

In this last phase of the production process, the event is documented. A few stakeholders are vital during this phase – namely, the festival promoter, the media and the audience members themselves. The festival promoter produces catalogues, programmes and publications and often edits an after-movie, in which the highlights of the event are documented. Critics share their judgement about the event in media outlets and write about the atmosphere, facilities and performances (collected in press clippings). Finally, with the rise of social media, audiences are likely the most valuable actors in the archiving phase. They share information about the event with their networks by posting photos and videos. Their enthusiasm reaches many others, contributing to the event's attractiveness. Their activities on social media help spread awareness for the event for upcoming years. All media and public attention (via printed, electronic and social media, with the numbers of direct audiences reached) is documented and provided to the funding bodies (local governments, foundations, sponsors, etc.).

Training and education in festivals and performing arts

In order to enter the industry of festivals and performing arts, a formal education is not mandatory. To produce an artwork or perform at a festival, one does not necessarily need a formal certification. Although the barriers of entry may appear low, practice shows otherwise. Being recognised as an artist

and making a career may be easier for artists who have a degree. Being formally educated at an art school often provides both the relevant skills and networks. Being embedded in the right social networks is crucial to distribute and sell art and to gain brand awareness. Moreover, in order to organise festivals, barriers are rather high because economies of scale are important.

In addition, artists are not only responsible for their creative work; they also have to negotiate to receive incomes. However, determining prices for their service is rather difficult because there is no shared view on how to do so. In many cases, pricing is based on comparisons with apparently similar types of artists and based on tradition. As a result, many artists receive insufficient income from their artistic activities and are forced to get supplementary jobs (Bondi & Sitton, 2007).

1.1.3 Embeddedness

Festival organisations run their events within a nexus of artistic, cultural and territorial objectives. The relative importance awarded to each of these goals may differ per festival, but they are always present: ‘There are no festivals, then, which can be described as purely artistic, cultural, or territorial. Rather, festivals must constantly take into account their local context and artistic quality as well as show a heightened sensitivity to their audience members’ (Négrier et al., 2013, p. 75).

These objectives point to a strong degree of embeddedness of this CCS. Festivals are socially, culturally, economically and territorially embedded in several ways. The increasingly competitive festival environment has made this embeddedness even more pronounced as it has encouraged festival organisers to ‘reaffirm their originality in order to distinguish themselves from competitors’ (Négrier et al., 2013, p. 72). They find uniqueness in their programming but also in their organised activities and the general ambiance they strive to create. For example, many festival organisations use local, cultural and historical values to shape events.

Territorial embeddedness

The territorial embeddedness of festivals and performing arts manifests in various ways. Determining how the production of cultural goods is anchored in and shaped by specific places helps understand the CCI. To do so, a multi-scalar analysis must be conducted that includes a comprehensive set of institutional conditions and policies at European, national and local scales. Events in the festival industry are typically uniquely tied to a particular location and are often connected with local cultures. Festivals that are closely related to a location tend to have explicit local goals for the event. These include strengthening social cohesion (Rao, 2001), learning about the local culture and history, and creating a collective sense of belonging (Lorentzen, 2009).

Examples of Dutch place-bound festivals are Leids Ontzet and the Jordaan Festival. Leids Ontzet is celebrated each year on the 3rd of October in Leiden to commemorate the end of the siege of this city during the Eighty Years War in 1574 (Nas & Roymans, 1998). Central to this festival is the history of a specific place and various local traditions (e.g. eating local food such as herring and stew consisting of carrots and potatoes).

The Jordaan festival is another annual festival. It takes place in the former working-class neighbourhood De Jordaan, in Amsterdam. The festival highlights many famous Amsterdam folk singers (Jordaan Festival, n.d.). Here, too, goals such as strengthening social cohesion, honouring the local culture and history and fostering a collective sense of belonging are of great importance.

Another way in which territorial embeddedness comes to the fore is when festivals are organised and run directly by municipalities themselves. This arrangement is, for example, quite common in Spain, where local civil servants are often in charge of managing the activities of the festival. From an economic perspective, this organisational set-up ensures a relatively reliable financial foundation for the event. However, a disadvantage can be that most cities are 'burdened with a heavy bureaucratic framework, making the decision-making process very cumbersome when compared with festivals run by not-for-profit associations' (Négrier et al., 2013, p. 197).

In addition, even when municipalities do not directly organise events themselves, their influence is felt because local authorities decide on permits and, in some cases, may own the venues, provide public transportation and facilities, and offer financial support. They can therefore be seen as powerful and dominant actors and stakeholders within the festival industry. However, at the same time, local governments are increasingly aware of the potential benefits of cultural events in terms of generating income and jobs on a local level and increasing the visibility and identity of places (Van Aalst & Van Melik, 2012, p. 196). This awareness has fostered mutually dependent relationships. If a local government is involved in providing not just permits but also resources to the organisation and realisation of an event, it usually wants to evaluate the local economic, social and environmental impacts. Local governments, viewing festivals as strategic placemaking events, in many cases even compete with each other in attracting them. This, consequently, enhances the negotiating power of event promoters.

The territorial embeddedness that applies to festivals in many cases also applies to performing arts. In addition, to a certain extent, some cities even lend their identity to a particular type of performing art. For example, the city of Vienna is known for its classical music performances and operas, and London is known for its vibrant theatre scene.

The main regulatory framework for the cultural sector in the Republic of Bulgaria was introduced in 1999, with the adoption of the Protection and Development of Culture Act. The act regulates the legal status of cultural organisations and the different types of cultural institutions – state (national), municipal (local), private and those with mixed governance and funding (state and municipal). The act

regulates the functions of the Ministry of Culture as the main allocator of public funds from the state budget and as the first-ranking authorising body. The other instruments of public funding in Bulgaria are the National Culture Fund of the Ministry of Culture (established by the same act in 1999) and the Municipal Culture Funds (at the local level). The cultural sector in Bulgaria is predominantly publicly subsidised – from national or local budgets; There are also some private actors (foundations or NGOs) supporting targeted activities through grants. Private funding is predominant in some commercial genres, such as popular and folklore music, dance and amateur arts.

As mentioned above, many local authorities believe in a positive relationship between festivals, performances and their city. They expect festivals, performing arts and museums to generate socio-economic benefits because events are able to ‘improve the city’s image, create place distinctiveness and draw visitors and tourists’ (Van Aalst & Van Melik, 2012, p. 196). As a result, governments are more willing to subsidise cultural events and institutions. In some cases, cities may even guarantee a subsidy for several years in order to retain certain events (Van Aalst & Van Melik, 2012) or to compete with cities to attract and host events in order to raise their profile.

Thus, all over Europe, cities have shown interest in organising festivals and performances (Getz & Andersson, 2010). This interest indicates a vital and mutual relationship between places and events. A festival is able to contribute to a region’s identity, while a location might also influence an event’s content (Van Aalst & Van Melik, 2012). Festivals are closely connected to the cultural infrastructure and facilities of a city (Kloosterman, 2005; 2014). This is particularly important for festivals, which attract many visitors within a short period of time. High security standards, good transport systems, hotels, restaurants and sanitation need to be in place to manage these large crowds.

As a result of the awareness of the potential strategic socio-economic benefits of cultural goods, governments have been paying increased attention to policy frameworks to support the festival and performing arts industry. In many cities, we can observe spatial clusters of a specific CCS industry (Scott, 2000; Hutton, 2015; Leriche, 2020). Examples of this are the fashion industry in Paris and the film industry in Los Angeles. These cities are internationally known for their cultural activities, number of artists and supportive institutions. Underlying the creation of agglomerations are path-dependent processes that stimulate these cultural activities. Supportive policy frameworks can be part of these processes. In addition, when a city is known for a cultural activity (just like Paris is known for its fashion), this trend can reinforce itself, leading to reproduction.

Vienna, for example, has fostered its image as an important international cultural capital, offering high quality opera and classical performances. These cultural activities attract many visitors from all over the world, thereby generating large income flows for the city. The socio-economic benefits are the main reason that the municipality allocated almost half of its total budget for culture in 2018 (47.98%) to theatres, music theatres and dance/performance. Other cultural and creative industries received much smaller shares of the total amount. This shows the ‘the cultural importance and heritage

tradition of big opera performances and high-quality theatre productions' (Gmeiner et al., 2020, p. 4), ultimately creating a process of path reproduction.

When comparing national policy frameworks related to festivals, Négrier, Bonet and Guérin (2013) observed that Spain and Quebec stand out from other countries because of the emphasis they place on local objectives. Spain's local goals relate to expanding its touristic appeal, strengthening its territorial identity and culturally developing its region. These local objectives can be explained by the fact that 'a large number of festivals are held in cities with less touristic appeal and, according to the legal status of the festival, the festival organizer and public sponsor are more 'politically' attentive to the local economic impact of a festival' (Négrier et al., 2013, p. 75). In Quebec, public governments use festivals first and foremost as a means to economically recover and to strengthen their touristic appeal in specific regions.

Finally, festival and performing arts organisations, as well as museums, often develop partnerships with local institutions and associations dedicated to education and culture. This way, these partnerships contribute to the realisation of broader socio-cultural and economic objectives through the organisation of festival events.

Network embeddedness

To explore network embeddedness, it is key to analyse the linkages between different actors in cultural production networks and to understand the functional and social connectivity of these relationships. Intra-firm, inter-firm and extra-firm relationships can act as bridges between actors and stimulate knowledge exchange and innovation. Firms in a network may collaborate with each other on specific projects and help connect suppliers to customers. Below, we discuss types of network embeddedness in festivals and performing arts.

One of the largest festival associations in Europe is the European Festival Association (EFA). It comprises more than 100 festivals (e.g. music, dance, theatre and multidisciplinary arts) across 40 countries. The EFA was established to unite and represent its members, and it acts as an important platform whereby festivals can interact with each other, with public authorities and with other stakeholders. Through these connections, the EFA enables the sharing of strategic information and hopes to enrich the festival landscape (EFA, n.d.).

Thus, the EFA's main mission is to enable festivals to cooperate by sharing strategic information. This type of cooperation (i.e. the exchange of information) is also one of the most frequently used forms by which festivals collaborate. Festival organisers often do so with the help of thematic and national festival associations, through which they can search for data about trends broadly affecting the industry and its economy or public policies. Festivals also occasionally agree to share performance costs or the co-production of a work. This happens sporadically and for practical reasons (Négrier et

al., 2013). When festivals collaborate, they strive to retain their own autonomy and remain independent entities. For this reason, the sharing of strategic information is favourable; it presents only a limited obligation for festivals. Other types of collaboration, such as the sharing of a common strategy or sharing human and technical resources, are less attractive because they require a higher degree of synergy between festivals, precise coordination and more commitment.

Finally, most collaborations between festivals do not exceed national borders. As Négrier et al. (2013, p. 116) state: 'More than 80% of those surveyed limit themselves to national partnerships' (Négrier et al., 2013). However, festival associations operating at smaller regional scales remain rare. This finding is rather surprising considering governmental support for festivals is primarily managed through local and regional authorities. However, according to Négrier, Bonet and Guérin (2013), this is precisely the reason festival associations are mainly confined to national borders. 'Regional authorities are perhaps too close to festival organizers to encourage collaboration between festivals. Thus, within their geographical areas, festivals can be seen more as competitors than as partners in the same project'.

Societal embeddedness

Societal embeddedness refers to the influence of socio-cultural, institutional and historical origins on the actions taken by actors in production networks (Coe & Yeung 2015). Various cultural elements (e.g. values and attitudes) shape the production of goods and services in terms of their aesthetics, meanings and value in the festivals and performing arts industry. Festivals can become part of the identity of a city and vice versa: a city or place can become embedded in a festival. Over the years these vicious cycles the products have been influenced by various societal factors. To discuss all of these elements exceeds the scope of this report.

1.1.4 Policy

Stakeholders active in festivals and the performing arts often face high levels of risk and uncertainty. Towse (2010, p. 307) even states that 'uncertainty about income and career prospects seems to be inherent in artists' labour markets', and this makes them dependent on external support from the state or private actors. This uncertainty can be explained by a few key features of the CCI. First, products of CCIs (e.g. performances) are experience goods, and the quality of the product and responses of the audience are relatively unpredictable, which makes long-term planning difficult. The economist Richard Caves (2000) underscores the uncertainties of cultural consumption on the basis of what he calls the 'nobody knows property': some will be hits, and many others will be misses. And it is hard to tell beforehand. Innovation, demand, audience formation and market development take place under conditions of unpredictability.

Second, the festival and performing arts sector displays an outspoken ‘winner takes all’ characteristic, whereby only a small number of (often internationally known) artists and organisations make up the majority of sales (Prendergast 2014). Because of a high degree of competition on the supply side, the majority of artists are in weak and uncertain market positions; they have a high degree of substitutability (EC, 2017; Towse, 2010). Velthuis (2003, p. 470) observes that ‘[i]n most Western European countries and the United States, only a small percentage of artists can make a living from selling their work on the market’. Among those who can, there are a few who are extremely successful and, typically, become celebrities.

As explained above (see p. 12), another characteristic of festivals and performing arts is their vulnerability to Baumol’s cost-disease. Thus, the creative process of festivals and performing arts has a great deal of uncertainty and risk. The need for state support is rooted in the fact that demand is unpredictable, artists face high levels of competition and the industries are vulnerable to Baumol’s cost-disease. To cope with these difficulties, we see various configurations of public and private sector actors involved. Different international and national (and sometimes regional and even local) institutional frameworks maintain different systems of art subsidies.

Accordingly, when analysing the cultural and creative industries, it is important to keep in mind that the artistic field is inserted in a specific socio-institutional framework. Regulatory regimes influence distribution and selling systems, and these systems in turn affect both the size and type of supply and demand of stakeholders involved (Alexander & Rueschemeyer, 2005). This chapter zoom in on these regulatory frameworks by exploring why and how regulations and incentives are implemented. It considers how national and local policies and actions in Europe affect artists and others in visual arts, festivals and performing arts?

This section outlines how production networks of visual arts, festivals and performing arts are embedded in broader institutional frameworks, predominantly the support measures implemented by the European Union. However, it is important to note that this outline of public incentives is by no means exhaustive.

Levels of Governance

Performing arts and festivals embrace different qualities which help cause socio-economic progress. Cultural events stimulate income flows by creating jobs and attracting tourists and consumers. Cultural products may also be able to trigger intercultural dialogues. International artists and their work may add to peoples’ awareness of different cultures. This way, performances and visual arts can be seen as a means for citizens to break out of tunnel vision and to develop an understanding from a different point of view. Especially in festivals and performances that have diverse acts and artists, people may have experiences beyond their own tastes. In addition, festivals and performances are

live experiences and foster the assembly of different people, enabling them to interact. This may strengthen a feeling of belonging and social cohesion (KEA, 2018).

Because of their intrinsic cultural value and their socio-economic benefits, performing arts, festivals and visual arts can be seen as *merit goods*: goods that are ‘provided by the public sector irrespective of consumer demand, where the usual operation of consumer sovereignty is set aside in favour of the imposition of the government’s own preferences’ (Throsby, 2010, p. 60). Other festivals may be strictly commercial. Most of the time, it is a combination of the two: there is a clear motive for profit, but aid, subsidies and sponsoring are available. As mentioned above, performances and visual artworks may be associated with several types of positive externalities, such as traditions, education, national identity, pride and prestige. Accordingly, stakeholders in these sectors are eligible for European and national funding and may receive additional technical or advisory assistance. Below, we explain these inherent characteristics and the relations with the state and its wider institutional context.

European Union regulations

The European Union has established several agendas to strengthen the CCI and its expected positive impacts on society, such as ‘The Council Work Plan for Culture 2015-2018’, and the ‘Creative Europe Plan 2014–2020’. The Creative Europe EU Regulation is a legal framework applicable to all EU (and EEA) Member States. It includes festivals in the scope of ‘cultural and creative sectors’. One of its objectives is to strengthen international creative activities in the European Union: ‘supporting actions enabling cultural and creative players to cooperate internationally and to internationalise their careers and activities in the Union and beyond . . . ; and providing support to strengthen European cultural and creative organisations and international networking in order to facilitate access to professional opportunities.’ The other priority is to promote transnational circulation and mobility, which includes ‘supporting international touring, events, exhibitions and festivals’ (EU, 2013).

In order to catalyse creativity, promote cultural diversity and intercultural dialogue, and enhance international relations, the EU has implemented several incentives and initiatives, varying from grant programmes and contests to various regulations (e.g. pertaining to copyrights and artists’ re-sale rights). The regulations were primarily introduced to ensure the protection and support of artists by setting a favourable framework for the development of the CCI. Below, we discuss a variety of support measures implemented by the European Union to do so.

Artistic and cultural mobility

One of the central goals of the Creative Europe program is to stimulate the circulation of artists and their creative work among Member States. Policy support incentives aiming to internationalise careers and cultural activities are important for stakeholders active in visual arts, festivals and performing arts, as they increasingly depend on global (transnational) production networks. Therefore, mobility is considered an essential part of the work of artists and other cultural professionals (KEA, 2018). This

has been increasingly acknowledged by European policymakers, who see mobility as a key instrument to achieve their cultural objectives.

The Creative Europe programme dedicated around 60% of its total budget from 2014 to 2017 to address the circulation of cultural works. By means of various grants and prizes, the EU stimulated transnational distribution. In addition, a short pilot project, called 'i-Portunus' was selected and funded by the Creative Europe programme to conduct a trial mobility scheme for cultural professionals (i-Portunus, n.d.). The project provided support for the international mobility of stakeholders active in the performing or visual arts. Applicants who applied for this grant had to have a 'specific and well-defined objective, such as to develop an international collaboration, to engage in a production-oriented residency or in professional development in the destination country' (i-Portunus, n.d.). In short time, the organisation received over 3000 applications from artists based in 41 countries, revealing the necessity for artistic and cultural mobility. Artists and their projects were selected through an evaluation by international experts. The project issued 620,933 euros of direct financial support to 337 individual cultural professionals (i-Portunus, n.d.). Projects like i-Portunus are used as trials to test how best to facilitate the cross-national mobility of artists. In 2021, a new Creative Europe programme starts, in which these types of mobility incentives will likely become permanent.

The grants and awards implemented by the EU are tools to strengthen international creative exchange. However, according to KEA (2018), there is still room for improvement to strengthen the European framework for mobility. At the EU level, as well as national levels, there are many regulatory issues (e.g. related to social security, taxation and visas) that hamper mobility (KEA, 2018). In addition, various EU countries have fragmented mobility policies. As a result, KEA stresses the need for one clear strategy among all EU members, with a specific scheme for the mobility of artists and cultural professionals. A clear policy framework could lead to vibrant cultural communities and creative trans-border environments.

Direct and indirect public funding

The EU supports visual artists and professionals active in festivals and performing arts through direct and indirect public funding. Direct funding is a traditional way of directly supporting CCIs – namely, through subsidies, awards, and grants provided by central and lower levels of governments. A non-repayable amount of money is given to cultural professionals after a selection process mainly based on artistic quality (Daubeuf et al., 2020). For example, the European Union has founded several funding programmes for the cultural sector that benefit visual artists. Examples are Erasmus (provides mobility grants for artists and encourages cross-national education) and Creative Europe (funding of cultural projects through pilots such as i-Portunus).

Besides direct public funding, the EU is also able to support CCIs through indirect forms of financial support to create a financially favourable framework. Examples are public loan guarantees and value-added tax (VAT) exemption regulations. VAT exemption stimulates the consumption of cultural

products, such as theatre and music concert tickets. The implementation of lower VAT rates for cultural products are substantiated based on their social value and the positive externalities that come with cultural consumption. For instance, cultural products such as books are considered merit goods. They are subject to a reduced VAT rate (10%) instead of the standard rate (20%), to make them more affordable for low-income groups (Daubeuf et al., 2020). Not many festivals and performances explicitly display these VAT exemptions, but they may in the near future.

VAT regulations stimulate consumption of cultural products, whereas public loan guarantees are implemented to stimulate the production of cultural products. Public loan guarantees are offered by the EU to encourage banks to give out loans to small and medium cultural enterprises. These guarantees are able to mobilise and leverage debt, thereby covering eventual losses incurred by investors in CCIs. This way, public loan guarantees operate similar to insurance. In cases of commercial default, guarantees cover part of the losses incurred by banks (EC, 2012). Thus, public loan guarantees mitigate risks, thereby stimulating banks to invest in cultural organisations such as festivals.

Finally, the EU has also implemented regulations to stimulate private investments in cultural projects. Incentives leveraging private investments aim to create wider economic benefits for private capital to be invested in CCIs (Daubeuf et al., 2020). Examples are tax incentives and public investment funds. Public funds offer a wide array of financial instruments to encourage scaling-up promising enterprises. Examples are loans with free or favourable interest rates and matching funds (CINCERONE, 2020).

National Regulations

Interactions between artists, institutions and audiences involved in festivals and performing arts are also shaped by state policies. The European Union gives EU Member States a high degree of freedom to implement cultural policy. As a result, Member States may differ significantly in the degree and manner of government support for cultural actors. Alexander and Rueschemeyer (2005) studied the interrelationships between state policy and visual arts. The authors highlight two key elements: ‘the amount and type of support that states may offer, and the degree of control they attempt to exert (Alexander & Rueschemeyer, 2005, p. 2). With this distinction they emphasise Member States’ powerful position in CCIs. States are able to support artists but can also negatively affect them through forms of repression and control. These policies do not have to be very obvious to the public. For example, by selecting artworks for public funding projects, the state decides who does and who does not receive financial support. This way, states have some degree of control over artists work since they have the power to support artists who conform to their accepted styles and ideas. Therefore, Alexander and Rueschemeyer (2005, p. 9) argue that the line between repression and selective support is thin: ‘not receiving what is expected or ‘deserved’ is punishment as well, and such sanctions may have important consequences for the ability of an artist to continue in the same direction or even to work in the field at all’. Thus, by selecting only the ‘socially acceptable’ works of art for public support, states are to some extent able to shape artists work (Alexander & Rueschemeyer, 2005).

However, in order to prevent such injustices, many Member States have decided to outsource the operation of art subsidies to independent committees.

Below, we delve into regulations and incentives implemented by states to support stakeholders active in festivals and performing arts.

Financial, legal and material support

Many states support artists and organisations through public subsidies. For instance, in many European countries, festivals and performing arts organisations can apply for grants. Based on certain criteria (positive externalities), states determine how their budget will be divided. However, because of the economic crisis of 2008, governments were less able to finance temporary events such as festivals. As a result, festival organisations have somewhat changed how they structure their income strategies regarding the distribution of public and private financial aid (Négrier et al., 2013). After the economic crisis, private partnerships became more important because festivals increasingly rely on patronage and sponsoring to make up for shortfalls in public financing (Négrier et al., 2013). Despite this decline, state support of CCIs is still important. They offer indirect financial support through VAT exemption and favourable tax incentives. The tax incentives stimulate private investments in CCIs (e.g. tax deduction on private investments or donations to CCIs). These tax shelters allow investors to deduct investments from their taxable income while still receiving profits.

In addition to financial support, states may also offer salaried positions, fellowships and educational opportunities. Artists may qualify for legal advice and assistance, and in some cases, states provide artists with materials and space. This form of support is often accompanied by specific laws, such as rent control given to artistic studios in neighbourhoods. Finally, besides supporting artists, states often subsidise artistic institutions, such as events, galleries and organisations.

Intermediating role

States may also take the roll of intermediaries by stimulating cultural consumption and connecting art to the public. One of the more evident ways they do so is through educational systems. Schools often teach children about the history of the visual and performing arts and arrange for trips to museums. In addition, states may offer incentives to specific groups to make art more appealing. For example, some states offer a cultural pass that provides discounts to museums and theatre concerts for citizens with lower incomes and for the elderly (Alexander & Rueschemeyer, 2005). Another example of states encouraging cultural consumption is the voucher, a credit meant to pay for a cultural commodity. Thus, a voucher is a substitute for cash. Vouchers encourage interaction between cultural agencies/artists and private businesses or schools. Hence, they stimulate businesses to hire creative services from artists. Many states award these vouchers to schools to spend on cultural and creative workshops with their students.

Regional Regulation

Cultural and creative planning has become increasingly part of urban politics. Local governments use cultural planning in entrepreneurial place-marketing strategies to ‘convince tourists, residents and investors of their unique virtues’ (Edizel, p. 634, 2013; Zukin, 1995). Consequently, ‘[t]he concept of the creative city . . . has become a powerful talisman for urban planners. Cultural policy has much to contribute towards re-vitalising depressed urban areas, improving liveability, and stimulating urban and regional economic growth’ (Throsby, 2010, p. 29). Because many local authorities believe in the positive relationship between events (e.g. festivals and theatres) and the city, governments are more willing to subsidise parts of such events. In some cases, cities may guarantee a subsidy for several years in order to retain the event (Van Aalst & Van Melik, 2011).

Other local measures are focussed on providing amenities to enable clustering of cultural activities. Creative hubs, parks, theatres and galleries are installed or subsidised to enable networking, mentoring and knowledge exchange of artists and cultural enterprises. To do so, rent control is also given to artistic studios in neighbourhoods. In addition, regulatory incentives and vouchers can also be managed at regional or local levels. Municipalities can influence consumer patterns by offering incentives to specific groups to make cultural activities more appealing (Alexander & Rueschemeyer, 2005). In addition, festival organisations are often dependent on the local municipality for obtaining a permit, regulatory approval, subsidies and tax relief (Getz & Andersson, 2010). Most facilities used are public parks, publicly owned halls and open spaces.

Conclusions

Stakeholders active in festivals and the performing arts are often dependent on public support because of their vulnerability to Baumol’s cost-disease, the high levels of competition and the unpredictability of demand. The European Union has introduced several regulations and incentives to protect and stimulate creativity. States differ in the way they arrange their support to CCIs. Some states rely more on the market and indirect funding, while others provide direct funding from their state tax revenue. Moreover, nations vary in how centralised their funding is. For instance, in Germany, funds are mainly decentralised and provided by local governments, while in Eastern European countries, funding is highly monitored by the national government (Alexander & Rueschemeyer, 2005). Many more differences can be observed between states, making their involvement in festivals and the arts highly complex. We also recognise a trend in which support for CCIs is increasingly regulated at the local level. This trend makes it interesting to conduct further research on how socio-cultural and political frameworks on various scales influence the production networks of CCIs.

Below, a summary of regulations in the festivals and performing arts industry is presented according to the GPN framework (Daubeuf et al., 2020).

Table 3. Summary of regulations in the festivals and performing arts industry

	Creation	Production	Dissemination	Exchange	Archiving
European regulations	Grants, public investment funds, copyright legislation	Tax incentives, public loan guarantees, grants	Stimulate circulation of artworks through awards and grants, artists' re-sale rights	VAT exemption, vouchers	Education, subsidising cultural organisations
National and regional regulations	Grants, public investment funds, education	Vouchers, grants, public loan guarantees, tax incentives	Awards and grants, regulations: rent control	VAT exemption, vouchers, discount pass for cultural consumption	Education, subsidising libraries and other cultural organisations

1.2 Production networks configuration of the festivals and performing arts

The table below shows a preliminary breakdown of the various stakeholders and the production phases in which they are involved in the festivals and performing arts sector. The GPN phases are creation, production, distribution, exchange and archiving. It is clear that many actors are involved at different stages. A key element within this sector that distinguishes the festivals and performing arts sector from other cultural sectors is time-sensitivity. Because the good or service is being performed, there is no flexibility in timing; everything must come together all at once and at exactly the right time. The logistics that uphold the performance or festivals is therefore key to understanding this sector, as this table shows.

Table 4. Actors, roles and tasks for each stage of the production network

	Creation (Ideas for event)	Production (Preparation)	Distribution (Promoting event)	Exchange (Live performance)	Archiving (Documenting, recordings)
Lead firm					
Event promoter	Creating artistic product and programming	Fundraising/ planning	Promoting event	Monitoring	Recordings, after movies, website
Strategic partners					
Government agencies		Permits, providing grants, regulation			
Police and other public services		Regulation of public transport		Emergency services, surveillance	
Sponsors / financial institutions		Providing funding and or loans resources	Marketing	Merchandise	
Owner of venues		Providing space (and facilities)			
Specialised suppliers					

Artists and their booking agency		Rehearsal of performance		Performance	
Suppliers of light and sound equipment		Stage setting, arranging equipment		Arranging lighting, sound	
Ticket distributor			Selling tickets online		
Media			Spreading information about upcoming events	Live streaming	Reviews from journalists, critics
Generic suppliers					
Providers of food and beverages				Providing food and drinks	
Employees/volunteers				Work during event	
Tourism traders (accommodations)		Hotels and restaurants provide accommodation		Hotels and restaurants provide accommodation	
Key customers					
Festival audiences			Buying tickets	Audience	Sharing on social media

1.2.1 Power dynamics

Festivals and performing arts depend of various configurations of public and private stakeholders. The industries display an outspoken ‘winner takes all’ characteristic, where only a few artists are able to make a living from their produced art (Caves, 2000). According to McAndrew (2010), that is because the industries resemble an ‘oligopsony’: a high number of artists and a relatively small number of consumers. As a result, artists are often in weak market positions (e.g. low wages, additional part-time jobs). Thus, in both performing arts and festivals the main locus of power seems to be located in the distribution and exchange phase, where large players are able to benefit from economies of scale and use their financial leverage to select artists and their products.

Many people dream of earning their money through music and performing, but only a few are able to do so. On the other hand, there are a few well-known artists (the exceptions) who are incredibly

wealthy and earn large incomes from their performances. Therefore, the income distribution is skewed, and many artists depend on financial support from the state or on private patronage. However, since the end of the 1970s, there has been a continuous growth in the number of festivals, leading to more demand for services from performers.

As a result of COVID-19, cultural life came to a (near) complete halt, leaving many artists without a job. Because this will undoubtedly have a major impact on labour market dimensions, the topic requires more in-depth research.

PART 2. Statistical mapping of the performing arts and festival industry

2.1 Quantitative analysis of the performing arts and festival industry

This chapter provides a statistical overview of the performing arts and festival industry. First, current statistics and trends from over the years are presented from a broad European perspective. The database used was Eurostat, the statistical office of the European Union. Thereafter, the chapter zooms in on performing arts and festival data in the specific countries in which the case studies were conducted (the Netherlands and Bulgaria). The emphasis in this chapter is on mapping statistics regarding employment, demand for performances, turnover and differences between places and genres.

Before diving into the specific data, it is important to discuss two relevant shortcomings. First, the dataset from Eurostat falls short in describing statistics from a GPN approach. The Eurostat database consists of two databases for services, industry and trade: the business demography (BD) database and the structural business statistics (SBS) database. The databases make use of NACE codes to measure economic activities. The codes and related activities do not clearly distinguish between the different production phases (creation, production, distribution, exchange and archiving). In addition, the statistics are inadequate as a tool to monitor market and stakeholder dynamics. Cultural and creative industries increasingly consist of hybrid organisations and relationships, making activities and value chains highly diversified and dynamic. The current statistics following the NACE classification are rather static and follow traditional sectors. Consequently, they are not entirely equipped to indicate the market dynamics of CCIs. Second, the extent, specificity and content of data collected differ between countries. Eurostat is designed as a tool to gather comparable data between Member States, which could be seen as a barrier to a coherent European dataset. Even though the NACE codes do simplify such comparisons, there remains a relevant difference in the degree of available statistical data between countries. Performing arts is one of the sub-sectors where data collection is poor and sometimes even non-existent (European Investment Fund [EIF], 2019). Thus, it is necessary to keep these shortcomings in mind while analysing the data and findings.

2.1.1 Europe

Performing arts are first and foremost considered a ‘presentation of live art to a live audience’ (EC 2017, p. 60). Examples of this CCI are theatre (e.g. ballet, opera, musicals), music festivals, dance and cabaret. Below, we describe the relevant NACE codes for each of the production phases (creation, production, distribution, exchange and archiving) in festivals and performing arts and explain some of their shortcomings. For each phase, we have distinguished between minimal and extensive NACE

codes. The minimal codes reflect the most essential economic activities, whereas the extensive codes include a more broader group of economic activities.

Table 5. Relevant NACE codes for the creation phase in the performing arts; code, title and scope

NACE code	Description	Minimal	Extensive
90.01	Performing arts	X	
90.02	Support activities to performing arts	X	
90.03	Artistic creation	X	
74.1	Specialised design activities		x

In the creation phase, a group of creatives conceptualise performances and logistics for an event. These activities are subsumed under the categories of ‘Performing arts’, ‘Support activities to performing arts’ and ‘Artistic creation’. In the extensive analysis, we included the category ‘Specialised design activities’. Although the economic activities of the creation phase are well reflected within the NACE classifications, a shortcoming is that the codes are rather broad. For example, while ‘Artistic creation’ does indeed measure the creation of a performance, it can also measure the creation of a book or a song. As such, when including these codes in our analysis, the results (e.g. number of enterprises active in the creation phase) may not represent reality.

Table 6. Relevant NACE codes for the production phase in the performing arts; code, title and scope

NACE code	Description	Minimal	Extensive
90.04	Operation of arts facilities	X	
90.02	Support activities to performing arts	X	
77.32	Renting and leasing of construction and civil engineering machinery and equipment		X

During production, logistics for the event are worked out. The management decides on a venue, obtains the necessary permits from the local municipality and seeks sponsors and financial investors. In addition, during the preparation, all technical equipment is tested for quality, and safety checks are performed. The NACE codes we used to measure these activities are ‘Operation of arts facilities’ and ‘Support activities to performing arts’. In the extensive analysis, we included code 77.32 ‘Renting and leasing of construction and civil engineering machinery and equipment’. Again, as mentioned above, these codes are rather broad and could include activities that do not concern the festivals and performing arts sector. For this reason, we put code 77.32 in the extensive analysis. In addition, some NACE codes were used for multiple phases (e.g. code 90.2 was used for creation as well as production) because the NACE codes are not detailed enough to properly distinguish between the different

production phases. However, when we retrieved statistics for the total production process of festivals and performing arts, these activities were counted twice.

Table 7. Relevant NACE codes for the distribution phase in the performing arts; code, title and scope

NACE code	Description	Minimal	Extensive
79.90	Other reservation service and related activities	X	

In the distribution phase, the promotion of an event takes place, and tickets are sold to consumers. These activities are hard to identify within the NACE classification system. As such, we included code 79.90: ‘Other reservation service and related activities’.

Table 8. Relevant NACE codes for the exchange phase in the performing arts; code, title and scope

NACE code	Description	Minimal	Extensive
90.0	Creative, arts and entertainment activities	X	
73.1	Advertising		X
58.11	Book publishing		X
58.14	Publishing of journals and periodicals		X
94.99	Activities of other membership organisations n.e.c		X

In the exchange phase, the actual event takes place. Depending on the event, this phase can take a few hours, a day or several days. During the event, almost all stakeholders become active, creating a temporary peak in the demand for labour. In the minimal analysis, we included code 90.0, ‘Creative, arts and entertainment activities’. For the extensive analysis, we included codes that focus on evaluation and the value of the event as perceived by key actors.

Table 9. Relevant NACE codes for the archive phase in the performing arts; code, title and scope

NACE code	Description	Minimal	Extensive
91.01	Library and archives activities	X	
91.02	Museums activities	X	
47.63	Retail sale of music and video recordings in specialised stores		X
85.52	Cultural education		X

In this last phase of the production process, the event is documented. Key NACE codes are ‘Library and archives activities’ and ‘Museum activities’. In addition, as some performances might be recorded for cultural education, we included codes 47.63 and 85.52 in the extensive analysis.

Results

The results consist of a description of the tables and concluding remarks, with a brief description of how the CCIs and their potential production networks are distributed across EU Member States and affiliated nations. Because the NACE codes are rather broad, we based our analysis on the minimal definitions. Data were from 2017.

The first table shows the total number of enterprises active in each phase of production in individual countries. It also adds up all production phases, thereby revealing the total number of enterprises active in the entire festivals and performing industry. Eurostat defines 'enterprise' as follows: 'The enterprise is the smallest combination of legal units that is an organisational unit producing goods or services, which benefits from a certain degree of autonomy in decision-making, especially for the allocation of its current resources. An enterprise carries out one or more activities at one or more locations'.

Table 10. Total number of enterprises active in the entire festivals and performing industry

	Tot. Creation	Tot. Production	Tot. Distribution	Tot. Exchange	Tot. Archive	Tot. cycle of production
European Union - 28	:	134710	281046	54,787	:	470543
Belgium	8,775	11208	6593	10,548	2311	39435
Bulgaria	1,209	2097	10171	2,688	8504	24669
Czechia	6,085	10163	1447	6236	20136	44067
Denmark	3,103	4733	2454	3,573	4562	18425
Germany	57,296	69742	25947	63,311	79169	295465
Estonia	2,496	2831	583	2,686	2002	10598
Ireland	6,755	8608	2665	7,386	14692	40106
Greece	8,335	11231	9953	9,343	22046	60908
Spain	39,445	51854	28409	45,037	115791	280536
France	53,595	71229	42429	65,800	188175	421228
Croatia	597	1104	1573	742	1767	5783
Italy	29,939	44443	52297	34,166	34308	195153
Cyprus	:	318	1015	40	0	1373
Latvia	1,992	2500	902	2,640	3814	11848
Lithuania	7,303	10067	1750	7,794	12765	39679
Luxembourg	392	512	342	425	561	2232

Hungary	13,901	16402	6424	17,092	31265	85084
Malta	920	920	201	920	0	2961
The Netherlands	81,723	101398	7606	88,153	86847	365727
Austria	11,454	13668	3117	12,595	9453	50287
Poland	:	9893	12543	6,933	0	29369
Portugal	23,889	26571	13337	25,320	56809	145926
Romania	8,475	10490	3810	10,695	15321	48791
Slovenia	5,110	5835	985	5,289	5927	23146
Slovakia	1,599	3348	5196	2,435	7626	20204
Finland	7,006	8306	2973	7,914	6684	32883
Sweden	:	8604	5126	1,766	0	15496
United Kingdom	33,780	41803	22033	39,583	52040	189239

Source: Eurostat, 2022

The data reveals that the most enterprises are active in France (421,228 enterprises), followed by the Netherlands (365,727) and Germany (295,456). The countries with the fewest enterprises include Croatia, Estonia, Cyprus, Luxembourg and Malta. However, this difference is largely due to different population sizes and the fact that the amount of available data differs from country to country.

When distinguishing between the different production phases, the statistics vary considerably. In some countries, most enterprises are active in the production phase (e.g. in Sweden, 55%). In others, the largest share of enterprises are active in the distribution phase (e.g. in Bulgaria, 41%, and Poland, 42%).

The table below shows the total number of employees active in each phase of production in individual countries. It also adds up all production phases, thereby revealing the total number of employees active in the entire festival and performing arts industry. Eurostat defines 'employees' as follows: 'Within the context of structural business statistics, an employee is a person who works for an employer on the basis of a contract of employment and receives compensation in the form of wages, salaries, fees, gratuities, piecework pay or remuneration in kind'.

Table 11. total number of employees active in each phase of production in European countries

	Tot. Creation	Tot. Production	Tot. Distribution	Tot. Exchange	Tot. Archive	Tot. Cycle of production
European Union - 28	:	69800	666523	88,119	:	824442

Belgium	7,647	8310	7588	8,956	2991	35492
Bulgaria	1,104	1880	16395	3,402	170198	192979
Czechia	1,754	2581	0	2259	15843	22437
Denmark	6,230	7447	12145	9,693	12018	47533
Germany	75,889	89986	123565	121,780	1153417	1564637
Estonia	1,097	1330	2544	1,798	3131	9900
Ireland	3,410	4215	10751	7,880	157022	183278
Greece	21,414	23128	8856	24,656	330232	408286
Spain	70,572	76634	53323	88,457	491536	780522
France	28,484	33645	86107	45,225	152061	345522
Croatia	547	1247	3885	960	8628	15267
Italy	11,866	14989	50728	24,427	85583	187593
Cyprus	:	309	2558	21	0	2888
Latvia	1,830	2306	3047	3,932	7909	19024
Lithuania	1,049	1542	3877	2,973	8585	18026
Luxembourg	118	161	0	168	1406	1853
Hungary	15,426	16461	10784	21,110	24593	88374
Malta	:	0	199	0	0	199
The Netherlands	22,402	24427	17690	48,387	538291	651197
Austria	5,924	7535	10843	9,330	27204	60836
Poland	:	3431	27564	7,125	0	38120
Portugal	3,496	5390	29261	6,033	44108	88288
Romania	3,572	5812	14026	10,111	18120	51641
Slovenia	595	834	1476	940	3549	7394
Slovakia	795	1586	9359	1,605	7258	20603
Finland	2,406	3256	7137	3,744	17870	34413
Sweden	:	2132	9952	1,218	0	13302
United Kingdom	92,095	108965	129299	164,705	1172135	1667199

Source: Eurostat 2022

The data reveals that the most employees are active in the United Kingdom (1,667,199), followed by Germany (1,564,637) and Spain (780,522). The countries with the fewest employees include Czechia, Estonia, Croatia, Sweden, Cyprus and Luxembourg.

In total, when adding all countries together, the majority of employees are active in archiving: 67%. This result is striking considering that archiving is a highly narrow category. This statistic suggests that the NACE classifications may not be well equipped to distinguish between the different production phases. As mentioned above, in some cases, the NACE codes are too broad, causing the results to show unrealistically high numbers. It is therefore important to invest in additional statistical sources that allow us to measure activities in different phases of production.

2.1.2 The performing arts and festivals industry in The Netherlands

State collected data

In 2021, the Dutch Ministry of Education, Culture and Science, requested the government organisation Centraal Bureau voor Statistiek (Central Bureau for Statistics [CBS]) to provide a statistical mapping of the employment and income position of artists and other creative professionals. The most recent data referred to the period from 2017 through 2019. The mapping is based on data from various surveys (the Labour Force Survey (EBB), the National Working Conditions Survey and the Self-Employed Labour Survey). The report from CBS provides insights on artists' demographic characteristics (e.g. distribution of age, gender and education level) and working conditions. In 2017–2019, there were an average of 164,000 artists in the Netherlands (CBS, 2021), respectively 2% of the entire Dutch employed labour force. Among that group, the CBS distinguished between visual artists (e.g. painters, photographers), design professionals (architects, fashion designers), executive professionals (e.g. dancers, singers), and writers, translators and other artist professionals.

With respect to festivals and performing arts, we explored the statistics of the executive professionals. This category includes musicians, singers, composers, dancers, directors and actors. Among the 164,000 artists in the Netherlands in 2017–2019, 47,000 were executive professionals (28.7%). The statistics show an increase in executive professionals: in 2010–2012, the group comprised 34,000 (of which men were more than 60%). The median personal gross annual income of executive professionals amounted to 29,000 euros in 2017–2019. Compared to the total group of artists, this income was slightly below average.

In addition, the CBS conducted a statistical analysis that focused on the demand side. According to the CBS (2018), the largest share of visits to Dutch professional art stages consisted of concert visits. In 2017, pop and classical concerts attracted nearly 8.7 million visitors. Compared to 2016, this was a slight increase of 1%. Of these visits, the majority consisted of visits to pop concerts. Approximately

15,200 pop concerts were organised, attracting 6.9 million visitors. In 2017, 4,700 classical concerts were programmed. Compared to 2016, visits to classical concerts increased by 5%, to 1.9 million visitors. Besides music events, cabaret is a popular art industry in the Netherlands, attracting over 2 million visitors in 2017. Furthermore, 1.86 million visitors enjoyed theatrical performances, while dance performances attracted 0.7 million visitors.

Sectorial data sources

The data collected by the CBS can be supplemented with data gathered by the Festival Atlas and by the Vereniging Nederlandse Poppodia en Festivals (Association of Dutch Pop Venues and Festivals [VNPF]). Both sources have a narrow focus on festivals and pop concerts. The Festival Atlas offers a data hub in collaboration with the Hogeschool van Amsterdam. In recent years, they mapped the geographical distribution, age and finance strategy of festivals in the Netherlands. In 2018, most festivals were organised in the province Noord-Holland (337), followed by Zuid-Holland (303). The five major cities (Amsterdam, Rotterdam, Den Haag, Utrecht and Eindhoven) accounted for 25% of all music festivals. Moreover, nearly a quarter of the music festivals in 2018 were relatively new: 23% of the festivals had only been in existence for three years or less. More than a third (34%) of the music festivals had been in existence for more than 10 years. In 2018, there were 88 new music festivals organised, which is 9% of the total 1029 festivals. Of that total, 76% had an admissions fee, while 24% were free of charge.

The Association of Dutch Music Venues and Festivals, founded in 1993, has also collected data about the festivals that are affiliated with them. Currently the association has 105 members. In 2018, these festivals organised a total of 15,733 activities, attracting 5,324,152 visits and providing work for 7,762 people. The employees consisted of volunteers (54%), trainees (4%) and paid employees (42%). The music events had a total of 161.9 million euros in income and 159.1 million in spending. Public subsidies covered 24% of the total income. The residual income mainly consisted of ticket sales and catering revenue (VNPF, 2019).

To conclude, these statistics provide some general insight into the festival and performing arts sector in the Netherlands and can be linked to the key festival characteristics (genre, budget and age). Most data focusses on music festivals, of which the pop genre is most popular.

2.1.3 The performing arts and festival industry in Bulgaria

The institutional infrastructure of the performing arts and festival sector in Bulgaria currently comprises a total of 51 state cultural institutes, 57 municipal cultural institutes (established by special legal acts by the executive power or local authorities) and over 150 organisations registered under commercial law, the Non-Profit Legal Entities Act and the Cooperatives Act. The performing arts in

Bulgaria include theatres and institutes of music and dance. At present there are 37 state theatres with almost 2,000 employees. Twenty-three of those are drama theatres, 11 are puppet theatres, two are theatre and music centres (in Kardzhali and Razgrad) and 10 are municipal theatres (four of which are in the capital). Bulgaria also has private theatre formations that dynamically change; there are about 20 with permanent activity.

In the field of music and dance, 14 state cultural institutes operate, providing over 2,750 jobs (550 in orchestras and about 2,200 in opera theatres, while some of the institutes outside the capital also receive local subsidies for maintenance and operation). There are one opera theatre, four orchestras, seven chamber orchestras, various choral ensembles, 24 brass bands and 20 folk ensembles, all of which are funded entirely by the municipalities. Activities of private music ensembles depend on their ability to secure resources and to provide for a specific niche market through project-based funding. There are professional music ensembles managed and financed by the Bulgarian National Radio, the National Music Academy, 'Prof. Pancho Vladiguerov', and the army and the police.

Within the scope of the Ministry of Culture's regulations, methodologies and rules, there are 20 performing arts festivals (half of which are theatre festivals and half of which are music and dance). In addition to these events, local municipalities and the community cultural centres (i.e. *chitalishte*) organise hundreds of other artistic festivals across the country. While systematic data and regulations exist for the permanent performing arts entities and groups in Bulgaria, performing arts festivals are practically not covered by a solid regulation system. This is largely due to the lack of a specific law on performing arts, thus hindering the ability to identify the key players, processes, trends and impacts of performing arts in general and festivals in particular in the society. Thus, a substantial part of this sector remains outside the perimeter of systematic policies.

The incomplete and unclear picture of performing arts festivals is also due to the lack of a relevant definition of the term 'festival'. This deficit prevents the setting up of a reliable inventory system for festival activities in the form of statistical standards, auditing and impact evaluation. Sustainable financing is another major issue of the sector. For example, the venues and facilities where Varna Summer International Theatre Festival performances take place do not meet the standards for staging contemporary performances. In addition, the public funding for performing arts festivals is limited to one year. The existing legal framework does not allow any multi-annual subsidies, ensuring the continued existence of the festival for three to five years.

Nevertheless, the case of Varna Summer International Theatre Festival is a good example of a successful artistic forum in Bulgaria. It has lasted over 30 years and is the fruit of a civic initiative and systematically organized and produced activities. The festival clearly has established itself in the national cultural calendar, filling the need of a truly international theatre and performing arts event. The festival promotes undisputed excellence in the field, and it is met with great interest from the audience while encouraging experimental projects that foster professional interest in the field. The professional organisational capacity developed over the years and the high professional standards and

reputation have led to a solid strategic partnership with the Ministry of Culture, the Varna Municipality and the Sofia Municipality. Despite its proven qualities and achievements, the festival’s funding is very modest and still incomparable to other international events of similar scale in the region.

The main sources of data for the statistical analysis of the performing arts and festival sector in Bulgaria come from the annual mapping of CCI in Bulgaria, conducted by the Observatory of Cultural Economics, Sofia. The mapping is carried out in the framework of a project called ‘Economic Contribution of Arts, Cultural and Creative Industries, Cultural Heritage and Cultural Tourism’, implemented with the support of Sofia Municipality and the assistance of the National Statistical Institute, which provided the data according to the methodology developed by the Observatory. The mapping survey has been carried out annually since 2011, with data covering the period 2008–2020. Enterprises in this sector include performing organisations, small and medium-sized enterprises and the non-governmental sector.

There are no statistics on festivals in Bulgaria, nor is there a systematic monitoring of the registration of visitors and their age and social profiles. Data on festivals has been gathered in separate studies, such as ‘Calendar of cultural events in the capital municipality’ (Tomova et al, 2013). The data below was extracted predominantly from OCE’s mappings and refers only to performing arts in Bulgaria.

Figure 1. Number of enterprises in the performing arts in Bulgaria, 2008-2020

Source: NSI/OCE

The data for the period 2008–2020 shows almost a two and a half times increase, from 434 in 2008 to 999 in 2020. The largest number of performing arts enterprises was observed in ancillary activities related to performing arts: 429 in 2020 (more than twice the number in 2008, 188). The largest increase in the number of enterprises was in non-formal education in the field of culture – from 42 enterprises in 2008 to 124 in 2020 (nearly three times more). In the exploitation of performance halls, the numbers remained relatively the same, with a slight increase from 14 companies in 2008 to 20 in

2020. In the performing arts sub-market there were more than twice the number of companies – from 190 in 2008 to 426 in 2020. The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic affected performing arts enterprises, causing a decrease of 31 enterprises.

Figure 2. Development of employment in the performing arts in Bulgaria, 2008-2020

Source: NSI/OCE

The analysis of the employment data in the performing arts sector for 2008–2020 shows an almost twofold increase – from 783 in 2008 to 1,407 in 2020. The largest number of employees was observed in auxiliary activities related to the performing arts – 2898 in 2020, or almost more than twice the number in 2008, 859. The largest increase was in the number of employees in the performing arts sub-market – from 311 employees in 2008 to 1,604 in 2020. In the exploitation of performance halls, the numbers remained relatively the same, with an increase of 23 employees in 2008 to 25 in 2020. In non-formal education, the number of employees increased from 387 in 2008 to 624 in 2020. The COVID-19 pandemic affected the commitments and activities of performing organisations, with a significant decline in employment in the performing arts. According to this indicator, the performing arts returned to its 2015–2016 national level.

Data on value added in the film industry for the period 2008–2020 shows an almost three-times decrease – from BGN 50,862 in 2008 to BGN 18,116 thousand in 2020. The highest added value was observed in the sub-market performing arts – from BGN 2,991 thousand in 2008 to BGN 10,110 thousand in 2020. The largest decrease in value added was to auxiliary activities related to the performing arts – from BGN 47,375 thousand in 2008 to BGN 6,583 thousand in 2020 (a decrease of nearly seven times). In the exploitation of performance halls, the value ranged from BGN 251,000 in 2008 to BGN 1,099 thousand in 2016; thereafter, it decreased to BGN 421,000 in 2020. In non-formal education, there was a relatively high increase in value added – from BGN 245,000 in 2008 to BGN 999,000 in 2020.

Figure 3. Development of added value in the performing arts in Bulgaria, 2008-2020

Source: NSI/OCE

Figure 4. Development of foreign direct investments in the performing arts in Bulgaria, 2008-2020

Source: NSI/OCE

Data on foreign direct investment in stage organisations for 2008–2020 shows a decline from 2008 to 2009 – an average of about 10 million euros, to the period 2017-2020 - between 429 thousand euros and 952 thousand euros in 2019. Data from the National Statistical Institute does not allow a breakdown by sub-markets because of confidentiality reasons.

Figure 5. Development of average gross payments in the performing arts in Bulgaria, 2008-2020

Source: NSI/OCE

Regarding the average gross salary in the performing arts, we can highlight the following trends:

- From the table presented above – which compares the average gross remuneration for the Bulgarian economy, the arts, CCIs, cultural heritage and cultural tourism – the lowest remuneration is in the performing arts sector: In 2008, it was BGN 920, and in 2020, it was BGN 9,087.
- The performing arts have slower wage growth compared to all other economic activities and are nearly twice the size of the CCIs.

2.2 Conclusions and open issues

Compared to the rest of Europe, there is a relatively rich set of statistical data available regarding the Dutch and Bulgarian performing arts sectors. The Dutch section mainly highlights statistics about music festivals and concerts, which can be explained by the popularity of music as a performing art. In 2017, almost half of the visits to performing arts were to music events. Digitalisation has made data collection easier than in the past, making it possible to keep track of ticket prices, visitor numbers and locations where events were held. However, there is still improvement possible. As mentioned in the introduction, quantitative data on the different production phases (creation, production, distribution, exchange and archiving) is scarce. The data is mainly focussed on statistics about employment, visitors and prices at the exchange phase as a 'final product'; it does not provide employment rates at different moments in the production process. For instance, the data does not provide insight into the different actors involved before events are held. In addition, stakeholder relations are still unclear. Data about what is exchanged between stakeholders to eventually create to the final product is not easily obtainable. Although Eurostat and national data sources offer interesting insights, they are unable to portray a complete and up-to-date picture of the size and dynamics of the entire sector. Hence, the festivals and performing arts sector could benefit from new methods of data collection that preferably keep in mind a value-chain perspective. By broadening the focus to the total production process, a better picture will be created of the variation and size of various actors and activities. In this way, relationships between stakeholders at different stages throughout production could be monitored. This increased understanding could, in due course, lead to a clearer picture of stakeholder networks and working conditions. In the next section, we further discuss the benefits of a GPN approach by means of case study research.

PART 3. The fieldwork: analysis and results

3.1 Case studies in the performing arts and festival industry: setting the scene

3.1.1 Unit of analysis

The CCS is characterised by its emphasis on unique aesthetic qualities, a near-endless horizontal differentiation (Caves, 2000) and volatile (cross-sectoral) collaborations. Those forms of collaboration usually comprise a number of actors who have different skills and who perform different functions, and the collaborations often cross the legal boundaries of firms. This particular way of producing involves, as a result, ‘complex teams – the motley crew property’ as well as ‘close temporal coordination of their activities’ (Caves, 2000, p.8). Watson (2012, p. 617) adds to this that ‘[t]he complexity of the [jointly produced product or service] necessitates the coordination of multidisciplinary skills and that it is not economically efficient to bring these together on a permanent basis (Lorenzen and Frederiksen 2005). Instead, the production must often be completed under severe time constraints (Hobday 2000; Staber 2004). Temporary networks, interpersonal collaboration and projects in the CCS are, hence, very much intertwined. As de Klerk (2015, p. 829) observes, ‘The dynamic environment in the industry is mostly project-based ..., thus often obliging these workers to find alternative employment between projects to optimise their limited work opportunities. Bricolage results from working arrangements structured by festivals or special assignments where creative workers move in and out of networks as they are needed.’

In this report, the GPN approach was used to analyse the large-scale production of goods. Some players in the CCS (e.g. part of the fashion industry) seem to fit this format of production quite well. However, at least a some of the activities in the CCS are rather different from the usual stakeholders in the GPN literature, which typically focuses on production networks, with big firms manufacturing extensive series of standardised goods. Instead of churning out large numbers of similar tangible products, the CCS is characterised by a predominance of small firms which focus on a small series (often just one) of goods and services. This focus requires more or less ad-hoc production networks which typically tend to have a different composition each time. A performance, a song or an album, a painting and the design of a theatre are all unique products which are typically also created by more or less ad-hoc production networks and which typically vary from product to product (Power and Hallencreutz, 2002; Power and Janson, 2004; Pratt, 2006).

It must be noted that some projects in the CCS are less volatile (say, the spring/summer collection and the fall/winter collection of a large fashion firm, which may rely on the same designers, suppliers and sellers). Such projects, therefore, resemble the type of networks which are prominent in the GPN

literature. In others (e.g. architectural design and festivals), networks likely vary much more in composition and can be more ad-hoc, displaying sequences of projects with different networks with various stakeholders.

In order to understand those volatile and project-based production networks in the CCS, we focussed on projects as the unit of analysis. This focus is in line with a whole body of literature on forms of collaboration in CCIs. In more recent economic-geographic studies (but also in sociological studies on the CCS), project-based working, which involves many organisational and personal social networks, has constituted the key component of the analyses (see Watson, 2012, for a good overview). Notably, studies on the labour conditions in the CCS have benefited from departing from a project-based approach. The important role of project-based working has been corroborated for many actors in the CCS (De Klerk, 2015).

In the CCS, then, the firm should not be granted a privileged ontological status; instead, the networks should be central. One could even reconceptualise the firm as a more permanent or sustained project, or as a collection of long-term projects (although evidently subject to recombination and change), which have been solidified as a legal entity. The temporal dimension of the project and, hence, of its network thus is a crucial variable in the case studies described below. This, evidently, ties in well with our GPN approach, which emphasises the role of networks. In the CICERONE project, however, we do not a priori conceive of these networks in terms of firms; rather, we focus on the interpersonal networks organised around a specific project. The issue of interpersonal relationships is also highlighted by Howard Becker (1982) in his *Art Worlds*. Such a focus also allows us to highlight the role of cultural value, which may trump economic value and the salience of other motives over profit maximisation, especially in the creation phase. These are distinguishing features of the CCS, and they have significant consequences for how its production networks function.

A more practical consideration for singling out specific projects is that it allowed us to come up with a more clearly justified selection of respondents – namely, those who were involved in a project. Therefore, it was easier to limit the number of respondents which a case should take into account (only project-related key lead actors, firms, strategic partners, strategic suppliers and customers).

3.1.2 Selection of cases

The main purpose of the CICERONE project is to provide a new foundation for policies affecting the CCS based on a production network approach. This approach can generate novel insights into how the CCS functions and how it affects society in social, economic and cultural respects. The approach that we followed situates the CCS in networks of production which comprise much more than just the creation phase. We used case studies to map the configuration of production networks, and we analysed relationships between actors in the phases of creation, production, distribution, exchange

and archiving. The case studies were, hence, intended to uncover linkages and mechanisms within these production networks to lay the foundation for better-informed policies – namely, policies which do not just go beyond the creation phase but which also take into account the spatial footprint and the governance structures.

The range of variation of business models within the CCS is large – not just between different sectors but certainly also within them. That variation refers to number of workers, turnover, type of products, barriers of entry, technology use, capital needs, end markets and strategies – to name just a few. They also differ in terms of power relationships, shape and organisation as well as the nature, complexity, and geography of the linkages of these networks. There are no data sets which comprehensively cover these characteristics. Forms of representative sampling are, in other words, not feasible – certainly not within the timeframe of the CICERONE project. Investigating this variation is, therefore, somewhat exploring uncharted waters.

We, therefore, opted for a judgmental selection of cases, whereby researchers select units to be sampled based on their existing knowledge – in our case, setting the research scene. The aim of this selection was to include cases representative of a sufficient range of variation in terms of key business model characteristics which could be easily assessed before the research itself (notably the number of workers and turnover). This approach resulted in sets of cases which can be seen as typical for significant parts of the population of CCS while also displaying sufficient difference to cover the variation (Gerring, 2007). Below, in the case study reports, each case study is positioned within the context of the broad sector.

The evident diversity of the CCS, however, has long been believed to be an obstacle for comparative studies, with researchers focusing mainly on highly specialised case studies (Klamer et al., 2006; Négrier et al., 2013). For us, however, this diversity presents an opportunity to analyse and bring to light the sector's richness (cf. Klamer et al., 2006; Négrier et al., 2013). To grasp how festivals and performing arts are organised from a production network perspective and how this relates to their sociocultural and economic impact, we selected case studies on the basis of four key variables: nationality, genre, budget size and event age. These variables have proven to be highly relevant in how festivals and performances are related to the development of partnerships, including their budgets and relationship to public policy goals (Négrier et al., 2013). Below, we briefly introduce our cases.

Lowlands

The first Lowlands festival took place in 1993. It was organised by MOJO Concerts and took place in Biddinghuizen, which is located in Flevoland. It has grown into one of the largest yearly festivals in the Netherlands, hosting approximately 250 performances and attracting over 60,000 visitors each year. Lowlands covers a wide spectrum of (pop) music genres, including rock, pop, hip hop, metal, electro,

techno and dance. Besides live music performances, the annual event is known for its additional coverage of theatre, film, comedy, literature, science and visual art. Regarding budget, the ticket sales are its most important source of income, making the event less reliant on cash flows from public subsidy or private patronage.

Nederlands Dans Theater: *Tell your mom you love your skin*

The second case study is the modern dance performance *Tell your mom you love your skin* by Nederlands Dans Theater (NDT, literal translation Netherlands Dance Theatre). Compared to Lowlands, *Tell your mom you love your skin* presents a very different profile. Modern dance, as Leila Sussmann (1998: 57) has noted, has been ‘from its beginning, an art for a circumscribed status group’, and ‘the modern dance audience is more educationally elite than the ballet audience.’ Second, *Tell your mom you love your skin* was intended from its very start to be an innovative modern dance work, thereby perfectly fitting with the mission and the long-standing tradition of NDT. Thirdly, NDT is to a large extent a non-profit organisation, with most of its funding coming from the Dutch national state and the city of The Hague. With these interrelated characteristics, *Tell your mom you love your skin* can be considered a unique case within the performing arts.

Amalyashi Festival

Amalyashi is a Dutch storytelling and theatre festival in Leiden which aims to connect and tell the stories of different cultures. The festival, first organised in 2021, is quite different from the Lowlands festival; it is much smaller in scope and budget. Because of the festival’s social goals, it received funding from the municipality and a few other public funds. With only one edition organised so far, the festival’s future is still uncertain.

Varna Summer International Theatre Festival

The Varna Summer International Theatre Festival (ITF) is a major international theatre event in Bulgaria. It takes place each year in the beginning of June in the city of Varna at the Black Sea coast. The festival is organised by Via Fest Foundation and is supported by the Bulgarian Ministry of Culture and the Municipality of Varna. The Varna Summer ITF has had 25 successful editions, presenting more than 600 performances from 37 countries from all around the world. Every year it attracts over 10,000 spectators. This case study allows for an interesting comparison between Dutch and Bulgarian festivals, considering their production networks and sociocultural and economic impact. Although its years of existence, scope and prestige are comparable to Lowlands, it differs in respect to its funding strategy, which is largely dependent on public funding.

The choice of the Varna Summer International Theatre Festival was based on its importance for contemporary theatre in Bulgaria. The festival organisers, Via Fest, have built a sustainable system of

partnerships, collaborations and communication on a local, national and international level: There is a rich production network that is sustainable over time. It is constantly evolving and enriching itself, enabling a wide variety of professional activities in performing arts to be promoted.

Putting the cases in the wider field of CCS

The four cases presented thus depict a rich and varied tapestry of production networks, which differ with regards to environmental and cultural influences, genre, budget size and age (from newly founded and small-scale to fully matured and institutionalised). However, notwithstanding their uniqueness, the events share a common characteristic in that they are complex goods that require close coordination between actors in order to manage specific resources from artists, producers, technical crews, agents, promoters, ticket distributors, investors, venue owners, public authorities and so on. The event organisers have to supervise and control flows between actors in different stages of production to make sure that everything is ready for the event (Getz & Andersson, 2010; EC, 2017).

The high degree of coordination and planning that goes into these events is precisely what the CICERONE research project seeks to study. Rather than focussing solely on a live event and its aftermath, our aim is to disentangle the events' production processes into different phases, for each phase highlighting the complex dynamics that shape the end product. In order to study these production cycles, we applied the GPN approach – a research tool and analytical framework which, although first and foremost based in research in manufacturing, has gained popularity in a wide range of sectoral studies (including services). By means of the GPN approach, we explored how event organisations collaborate with actors (e.g. city authorities, private sponsors, suppliers of equipment) throughout the year. These 'hidden' activities provide insights into how different actors create and appropriate value throughout production. In addition, the GPN approach allows us to situate the event and involved actors within the broader sociocultural and institutional context, by which we are able to understand how values, norms and policies at different spatial scales shape, constrain and undergird the production process (Coe and Yeung, 2015).

In order to gain insight into the festivals and performing arts sector, this CICERONE research project opted for a mixed-methods approach, applying both quantitative and qualitative tools. As such, different data collection methods were combined – namely, analysing statistical and theoretical literature and conducting interviews. The latter became crucial in our analysis of the selected case studies. Several semi-structured interviews with key actors were conducted through Zoom to gain insights into their resources and embeddedness as well as the flows and power relations between them. The interviews provided us with different and complementary ways to understand the events.

More specifically, we conducted a total of 36 interviews: 10 for Lowlands, eight for Nederlands Dans Theater, three for the Amalyashi Festival and 15 for the Varna Summer International Theatre Festival. Because of the different sizes of events, some cases required more interviews than others. To make

the fieldwork doable, we delineated the network by means of Coe and Yeung's (2015) typology of main actors: i) lead firms, ii) strategic partners, iii) specialised suppliers, iv) generic suppliers, and v) key customers. A lead firm has, by definition, a central position in a network and coordinates and controls production. Identifying the lead firm can bring methodological clarity as it serves as a starting point to establish the roles of other actors, their interrelationships and the related flows (Coe and Yeung, 2015). We are not, however, able to identify a clear lead actor in every production network because there are also configurations which do not display a vertical governance structure, but rather a much more horizontal one. In an event network, the lead firm is likely the festival or event management team. Besides the lead firm, strategic partners play vital roles in enabling the production process by providing key conditions for an event to be organised. The lead firm depends greatly on such strategic partners, who lay the foundation for such a network. Examples are local authorities, owners of venues, and private and public sponsors (Getz & Andersson, 2010). If these basic conditions are met, different types of actors enter the stage (sometimes even literally), and these independent suppliers are woven into the production network. These suppliers can be divided into specialised and generic suppliers (Coe & Yeung, 2015). Specialised suppliers offer advanced producer services and tend to have specific knowledge and skills which gives them a more powerful position than generic suppliers because they are able to take advantage of human resources and brand rents (Coe, 2015, p. 488). In an event network, tech-companies, a ticket distributor, media, and artists could be classified as specialised suppliers. Generic suppliers, on the other hand, typically offer low-value products and services, which are fairly standardised (Coe & Yeung, 2015). Examples are cleaning services or employees and volunteers who work during events. And finally, the consumers – the ones paying for and enjoying the cultural event – are the audience. Based on the specific roles and irreplaceable skills and knowledge in such networks, we decided to limit our interviews to lead firms, strategic partners and specialised suppliers.

Furthermore, because of the rich variety in this sector and the limited number of case studies that we conducted, the scope for generalisations is limited (Bryman, 2012). However, rather than random sampling, we selected cases according to the principle of 'theoretical sampling'. As such, we selected cases which differ in nationality, genre, budget size and event age. These four variables have proven to be highly influential in the ways events are organised and therefore allow us to compare diverse cases that showcase the sector's richness.

3.2 Case 1: Lowlands Festival

Source: *Festileaks.com*

3.2.1 Phases, actors, and locations

Phases

Creation phase: conceptualisation

Lowlands Festival is organised by MOJO, which annually organises over 150 concerts and festivals. MOJO is a Netherlands-based company that is owned by the large event organising firm Livenation. Because of Lowlands' considerable size, a few of MOJO's employees actively plan the event throughout the year. Shortly after the previous edition has finished, an evaluation phase starts in order to come up with improvements for the next edition. These early stages of reflection and conceptualisation take place at a local scale in MOJO's head office in Delft. Not much later, the core team of Lowlands consults with specialised suppliers and strategic partners to see whether and how their ideas can be worked out in concrete terms. Both MOJO and external actors have indicated that approximately 80% of Lowlands' design is fixed, while 20% changes each year. As Lowlands' project manager explains, this innovation is crucial:

Lowlands has always been MOJO's testing ground, so that's where most of the money and innovation is. In all areas, from showers to toilets to light, sound, video. Together with our supplier, we go down a certain path to take something to a higher level. After that, it becomes part of a supplier's equipment and he can apply it at other festivals as well. But Lowlands is where it will happen first. This quality difference in terms of production makes Lowlands a flagship.

Although large parts of the festival are standardised, the demand and urgency for innovation makes for highly interactive collaborations with suppliers and the municipality. Lowlands' contact person from the Dronten municipality (in which Biddinghuizen is located) stresses how they take on an active and supportive role throughout the creation phase:

We are an event municipality and we see MOJO as a strategic partner. We are in this together. And of course you have your own responsibilities and you have to comply with legal matters, but we see it as a joint project. (...) Our mayor is like that too: he advocates what can be done instead of what can't.

In addition to this supportive attitude on the part of the municipality, he emphasises how other strategic partners, such as the police, the fire service and the Municipal Health Service, not only assess MOJO's plans on feasibility but also actively try to propose ideas. According to him, this is due to everyone, regardless of their specific responsibilities, pursuing the same goal: 'to set up a safe and beautiful festival'. To conclude, the creation phase starts off small. Activities are centred around MOJO's core team but gradually expand to include key suppliers and strategic partners in order to work out ideas in concrete terms.

Production phase: build-up

The production phase starts three weeks before the Lowlands festival begins. This build-up phase is characterised by complexity because of the time pressure and logistics of coordinating a multitude of actors. As the director of Lowlands calls it, 'a logistical dragon'.

There are 1800 trucks coming in. They can't come in at the same time, so there is a really tight project planning. And if a supplier isn't there on time, they hold up the entire group.

Within three weeks, the festival site in Biddinghuizen is prepared for the three-day festival that will welcome over 60,000 spectators, thereby turning it into a 'small town'. Accordingly, in addition to the building of stages, the preparation of lighting, sound and video, and the placement of sanitary facilities, an enormous supply of food and drink has to be acquired and stored, part of which has to be brought to cold storages nearby.

The complexity and time pressure of coordinating each flow in the build-up means that MOJO's production managers are used to work days of 14–16 hour before the event. In addition to MOJO's coordinating role, the municipality fulfils an important supervising role since, in the end, the manager is responsible for spectators' safety. Hence, during production, several safety checks are completed by MOJO, an external party and the municipality.

Distribution phase: promotion and ticket sales

In the distribution phase, activities are centred around promotion and ticket sales. Chronologically speaking, this phase takes place months before the production phase. MOJO starts announcing the names of performing artists on social media and the Lowlands website near the end of January and beginning of February. Not every artist is announced at once in order to build suspense. Shortly after the majority of artists are made public, the ticket sales start (often around mid-February). This process has changed significantly because of Covid. A pre-sale is arranged for people who had tickets for the cancelled editions of 2020 and 2021, after which the remaining tickets are sold. Unlike many other Dutch festivals, there are no day tickets available, only tickets for the entire weekend (approximately 245 euros), which includes a place at a campsite (attendees bring their own tents) and transport by shuttle bus to and from a nearby train station. On its website, MOJO warns against fraud in the resale of tickets via Ticketswap, Viagogo, Marktplaats and other (online) providers, and recommends to only purchase an original ticket from Ticketmaster.

Exchange phase: the festival

Each year, Lowlands takes place during a long weekend in mid-August in Biddinghuizen. The location has five key benefits: (1) it has a license for night programming, which is highly difficult to obtain in the Netherlands; (2) the location used to be scalable, which, although now having reached a limit, has allowed Lowlands to grow in visitor numbers for many years; (3) MOJO has bought parts of the festival site and parking to ensure the continued existence of the festival and to eliminate changes in the environment that could endanger the festival; (4) MOJO has been working with the Dronten municipality for years, and this collaboration is therefore extremely efficient; (5) its distinct location, being at the same time remote and accessible, makes for an 'exotic' image, which impacts how people behave, according to the Lowlands' production manager:

Because Lowlands is in Biddinghuizen, people really see it as a kind of mini holiday. And if something is classified in your mind as a mini holiday, then you are willing to be there longer, but also to spend more money. (...) That mini holiday feeling is part of your experience.

Because of the considerable size of the site, Lowlands is able to showcase a diversity of performances on 12 different stages. Because of the large number of spectators and multitude of acts, these three days require close temporal coordination by MOJO's core team. In order to manage crowd flows and

secure a safe event, several actors have formed an emergency team to supervise and take action when necessary. MOJO's employee responsible for Lowlands' permits describes this as follows:

During the festival, we carry out most of the activities from the control room. It contains centralists who receive all information from different disciplines, so medical, fire protection, security. Uhm, LED screens are included, presentation. Those kinds of things. That's where the festival comes together. For us, this is the place to be able to monitor processes and to see, at a single glance, what is going on. We use 23 cameras. This image is very important.

Archiving phase

The archiving phase, in which the event is documented, mainly takes place at a national scale. The Dutch public broadcaster provides extensive coverage of the festival, and national newspapers reflect on the event. MOJO itself also actively documents the event and keeps track of statistics with regards to its visitors (e.g. profiles of visitors' age, gender, and education level) and their degree of appreciation. MOJO collects that data for the purpose of evaluation. In addition, it could be argued that the spectators are the most important archivers because they share pictures and videos of the event on social media, thereby reaching large numbers of people.

3.2.2 Relationships between actors

An analysis of the power distribution shows that MOJO is the lead actor. They are responsible for conceptualising the festival, promoting the event and coordinating the assembly of necessary actors at the right time in each of the production phases. Despite their crucial role, power is not as concentrated as one would expect. This is largely due to MOJO being highly dependent on various irreplaceable strategic partners and specialist suppliers with specific knowledge and skills (Coe & Yeung, 2015). In the areas of video, stage, light, sound and sewerage, few actors are capable of carrying out such a large assignment as Lowlands. The actors that are capable are among the largest in the Netherlands (e.g. Ampco Flashlight) or even operate worldwide (e.g. Stageco, Faber), and they do not experience high levels of competition. As explained by the director of Lowlands,

We have a lot of knowledge about which people are specialists in which field. With video it is Faber. They always have the latest equipment and employ the best people. They are not the cheapest but they are the best (...) Also, in terms of what we need for Lowlands, there are almost no other competitors to choose from. We know with certainty that we will need them in the coming years; their video and expertise. So in that case, we arrange for multi-year contracts.

MOJO stresses how they prefer expensive suppliers with proven expertise over cheap deals because they cannot afford a supplier to fail or cancel last minute and risk not being ready for the event. MOJO

then needs these key suppliers to stay healthy in order for them to continue working on Lowlands, as well as for them to innovate and invest in the newest technology. Therefore, MOJO is not inclined to 'squeeze deals'. However, this mindset was slightly put into question by the director of Ampco Flashlight (a lighting and sound company), who argued that, considering their expert knowledge and skills, its employees are underpaid:

We are never really in competition when it comes to Lowlands. They have discovered that if you look at the total palette that they have to offer there, only Ampco could do it. No other party could. But again, the price still has to fit within MOJO's revenue model.

He argued that, despite their expertise, Ampco Flashlight cannot enforce a raise in salary because they depend on MOJO to offer a great deal of employment. There is, then, a mutual dependency between MOJO and its suppliers in which, according to the director of Ampco Flashlight, MOJO has the upper hand. So, within the production network of Lowlands are a few largely fixed, specialised suppliers. The technical director of Lowlands explained how these collaborations have contributed to a higher level of efficiency:

Of course what you want most is people who have been involved in the project for several years, so that they also grow with it and better understand Eric's [director of Lowlands] way of thinking, so to speak. And in such collaborations, you can discuss about what to do and what not to do, which has a better effect than if Eric decided everything alone.

Production is characterised by constant interactions between MOJO's employees and key suppliers, who have experienced and assessed Lowlands' previous editions. Rather than arm's length deals, this makes for highly socially embedded relationships. Through processes of successive learning, actors gradually acquire knowledge from previous dilemmas and gain repetitive 'scripts', which allow the event to increase in efficiency.

In addition, by collaborating on Lowlands for several years, both the festival and the suppliers have built up knowledge and have grown. For suppliers, it is important to have a multi-year contractual agreement with MOJO because such a guarantee makes it easier for them to borrow money and invest in new equipment. MOJO is willing to draw up such contracts because they enable Lowlands to innovate. As an example, the director of Lowlands accentuated MOJO's relationship with MDT, a (previously) local sewage company. MOJO prides itself for its role in the company's success because they once convinced the supplier to invest in a new system specialised in timely events. They guaranteed to rent the company's equipment and thereby cover part of the risk: 'And so this company has grown from nothing to the company that is installing water and sewerage worldwide for the Olympics' (Lowlands' director). Accordingly, both MOJO and specialised suppliers benefit from long-term collaborations.

Finally, another key actor with considerable influence within the Lowlands’ production network is the municipality, which functions as a strategic partner. Both the municipality and MOJO emphasise how Lowlands is a joint project which requires strong teamwork. For MOJO, the municipality has a crucial position because of their role issuing permits and safety checks. For the municipality, Lowlands offers interesting positive economic externalities (i.e. nearby hotels and restaurants benefit from the event and its 60,000 visitors). Because of the municipality’s involvement in Lowlands, they have acquired a great amount of knowledge and skills when it comes to organising festivals. As a result, the Lowland’s project manager stressed how the municipality is ahead in a number of aspects and a leading force in the network. This was also confirmed by an employee of the municipality, who indicated that other municipalities wish to learn about their involvement in events as a public authority.

To conclude, although MOJO plays a leading role by coordinating the network, power is not as concentrated because of their dependence on a few specialised suppliers and strategic partners. Accordingly, it is essential for MOJO to retain the loyalty of these actors. The festival direction seems successful in achieving this, since external actors described the relationships as ‘stable and secure’, ‘pleasant’, ‘based on good faith and trust’, and ‘highly efficient’. These socially embedded relationships have contributed to Lowlands’ development and efficiency.

3.2.3 Positioning the case with the typology matrix

Table 12. Case 1: positioning the production network of Lowlands Festival in the typology matrix

PRODUCTION NETWORK PHASES	Local/regional	National	Intra-EU	Global	GOVERNANCE
Creation	X				
Production		X			
Distribution				X	
Exchange	X				
Archiving		X			
Network level					Hierarchical

An analysis of the power distribution shows that the MOJO management is likely to be the lead actor since they are responsible for conceptualisation of the festival, planning and coordination of various activities, promotion and distribution of tickets through their own channels, and coordination of the assembly of necessary actors at the right time in each of the production phases. Accordingly, in the creation, distribution and exchange phases, power is highly concentrated around the MOJO management. In the production phase, however, power is more dispersed since the MOJO management is highly dependent on various strategic and specialist suppliers. These actors have specific knowledge and skills, which gives them a more powerful position than generic suppliers (Coe

& Yeung, 2015). An important strategic partner is the local government of Biddinghuizen, which decides on the provision of the necessary permit. In addition, MOJO also seeks to attract various internationally renowned A-list artists, for which they have to negotiate considerably. Finally, in the archiving phase, the media and newspaper seem to occupy the most power. Nevertheless, throughout the process, the power is generally concentrated in the hands of MOJO.

3.2.4 Network dynamics

The spread of the coronavirus (COVID-19) has had major consequences for festivals and performances worldwide. For almost three full years, government measures have led artists and festivals to postpone or cancel their events. The same holds for Lowlands, which was cancelled twice in a row. For the edition of 2021, MOJO had already invested in the festival's build-up, before hearing one week before the event that new restrictions made it impossible to continue. Despite this loss in investment, the festival's future is not endangered. This is largely thanks to MOJO's established and institutionalised size and the fact that they are owned by Livenation, a global player in the live event industry that merged with Ticketmaster, thereby creating a degree of vertical integration within Lowlands' production network. According to our MOJO respondents, Livenation is not involved in the content and planning of Lowlands because they understand that specific cultural and local knowledge goes into organising such events. Instead, Livenation's involvement is more on the surface – rather than focussing on the project itself, it focusses on MOJO as a company. Even though Livenation is not involved in Lowlands, it does provide MOJO with financial security to fall back on if necessary. And of course, profit money from MOJO flows back to Livenation as well.

Despite MOJO's relative financial stability, they do worry about some of their specialised suppliers, which were heavily impacted by COVID-19. Examples are Ampco Flashlight (Lowlands' supplier of light and sound), which was forced to lay off over 300 employees, decreasing from 430 to 100 employees, and Stageco (Lowlands' staging company), which suffered a 94% loss of revenue. Whether these specialised suppliers will be able to recover and re-hire their employees is uncertain. During the crisis, many employees and freelancers active in the event industry started working in more secure and stable sectors such as construction. As a result, the event industry lost an important pool of expert knowledge and skills, which is not easily replaced. Both MOJO's employees and specialised suppliers stress the importance of experience and learning on the job. Rather than a formal education, the most valuable knowledge and skills are acquired over years, through processes of successive learning – by trial and error, actors learn what works and what does not.

So, despite MOJO being financially secure, the festival direction has concerns about some of its key, irreplaceable suppliers. As a result of the pandemic, the festival sector is struggling with huge staff shortages. For MOJO, finding the right people becomes a big task, as the sector has emptied out, and many people who previously worked for Lowlands have found work elsewhere. A loss of knowledge

and lack of experience with new employees may make it impossible for suppliers to offer the same high-quality services and to organise Lowlands as efficiently as former editions. The blow of the crisis and consequent loss of specialists, hurting the sector's wealth of experience, could therefore mean that it will take years for the sector to recover.

Besides the impact of Covid, two other crises were mentioned during the interviews. First, as a result of the Bataclan shooting (Paris, 2015), in which 89 people were killed during a rock concert, Lowlands increased measures to ensure spectators' safety.

The Bataclan shooting has permanently changed Lowlands, mainly backstage. Look, in the past, for example, if Flashlight came with twenty people and you were the boss of those 20 people, you received twenty entrance bands and twenty hotel keys: 'Do your thing'. Now, we want everyone who is on the site, individually with date of birth, place of birth, place of residence, all registered in their own name. He/she has to go and get the accreditation themselves and that is basically just a security thing. (Niels)

Although it requires a large investment to oversee and control this entire process, it is considered a crucial requirement to safeguard the festival and its visitors.

Second, Faber (Lowlands' supplier of video) mentioned how the prices of energy and containers have increased significantly. Many factories in China were closed because of energy shortages, limiting Faber's ability to acquire the necessary electronic components. Certain parts could no longer be produced. In addition, as a result of the Suez Canal obstruction in 2021, container prices rose almost 10 times. Materials of Faber and NEP (its parent company) were stuck during this crisis, resulting in high additional costs and creative solutions to carry out assignments with different materials. As a result of these increased shipping costs, Faber has decided to produce more and more materials themselves:

We started producing some things ourselves in Europe and the United States. We used to produce everything in China and the Middle East because it was so cheap, and for the price it was acceptably good. But the price is now so high that it is cheaper to have it produced in the Netherlands. In the country where you need it.

Thus, in recent years, the Lowlands festival has undergone several changes related to its organisation. Because of the Suez Canal obstruction and the energy crisis, some suppliers of Lowlands increasingly shift production to a national scale to save on shipping costs. In addition, the Bataclan shooting has permanently changed backstage production because of increased safety measures. Finally, in the coming years, Lowlands will have to deal with huge staff shortages. A major task will be to find experienced, specialised suppliers who can offer high-quality services.

3.2.5 Impact

Festivals and performing arts are considered merit goods and are valued for their sociocultural and economic benefits (Throsby, 2010). Positive externalities such as local employment, education, social cohesion, national identity, and pride and prestige are what makes festivals and performances eligible for European and national funding. Below, we discuss the economic, social and cultural impact of the production network of the Lowlands Festival.

Economic impact

Lowlands' most significant source of income is generated from ticket sales. A ticket for the entire festival costs approximately 245 euros. Based on the maximum number of visitors (60,000; the festival sold out in previous editions), this amounts to a total income of almost 15 million euros. Besides ticket sales, income comes from catering, sponsoring and subsidies. Lowlands has a percentage deal with catering operators, and part of the revenue generated by catering must be paid to the festival. Sponsorship and subsidies are less important cash flows. The festival normally receives a subsidy of approximately 200,000 euros to arrange high culture acts. In addition, as a way to stimulate and support European artists, Lowlands receives subsidies from the European Talent Exchange Program from Eurosonic. Sponsorship is also perceived as an extra flow that is not essential, but it is certainly appreciated.

From these sources of income, MOJO has to pay its strategic partners as well as specialised and generic suppliers. It is not possible to calculate Lowlands' exact costs because the organisers do not want to disclose what they pay artists. This can easily vary, from 1000 euros for lesser known bands to 300,000 euros for more established bands. Although MOJO does not specify how much they pay each artist, it is estimated to be about 80% of the total costs of the festival. This is partly because the asking prices of artists have increased due to digitisation and the massive trend of downloading of music. Touring has become a more important source of income for artists. However, Lowlands deliberately avoids hiring the biggest A-list artists. Besides the fact that these artists are highly expensive, it is also not feasible logistically, since the largest stage can only accommodate 30,000 spectators. The structure of Lowlands is therefore not designed for acts that everyone wants to see.

In addition, MOJO has to pay its specialised suppliers, who arrange for security, light, video, stages and sanitary facilities. As indicated above, some specialised suppliers are involved with Lowlands almost all year round. Lowlands' preparation is characterised by an ongoing production cycle in which MOJO evaluates the previous edition before embarking upon new ideas together with its partners. Hence, throughout the year, the event generates labour across various firms. Since there are no exact statistics available that measure these 'hidden' backstage activities, it is unclear how much employment precisely goes into organising the festival. However, the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic revealed how not only artists and event producers were heavily impacted but also a much

larger share of actors, including the self-employed. The crisis, therefore, partly uncovered how much employment is actually generated by these events.

The event mainly relies on goods and services from actors within national geopolitical boundaries. In the festivals and performing arts sector, global sourcing is not a common practice because of locally-oriented productions and 'linguistic, cultural, geographical and economic barriers' (EC, 2017). For instance, within Lowlands' production network, most specialised suppliers were based in the Netherlands. As explained by the director of Ampco Flashlight:

The sound and light sector is very much country bound because of national regulations on safety and permits. Germany has very different standards than Spain, for example. And there is also the language. Usually it is in English, but in France this is already too difficult. And because you also have high transportation costs, it is simply too difficult to compete with national firms. If you want to expand activities internationally, it will cost millions in investments.

Ampco Flashlight operates for '90% to 95%' of their business on a national scale. However, there are a few exceptions, such as Faber, Lowlands' supplier of video. The reason that Faber is able to operate worldwide can be explained by the fact that the company is owned by NEP, a large American event enterprise. This provides Faber with the opportunity to borrow equipment from sister companies. So, although there are some actors that work internationally, the majority are nationally oriented.

In addition, for Lowlands, the need to hire international suppliers is low. As an employee from MOJO explained, the Netherlands is ahead when it comes to organising festivals: 'We export festivals abroad. That says enough. People want to have that bit of Dutch identity and that DNA that organises festivals'. Companies in the Netherlands are frontrunners when it comes to logistics and planning backstage, but also in terms of sound. As the CEO of Ampco Flashlight argued,

The Netherlands has a head start and is truly leading in quality. You hear that from everyone. That is why so many artists come to the Netherlands. They know that the sound and everything is well arranged.

In addition to the national creation of jobs, Lowlands also generates jobs on a much smaller and local scale. As indicated by the Dronten Municipality, MOJO actively tries to encourage local job initiatives by 'searching for local products to purchase'. For instance, in the past few editions, food stands sold fries that were made from local potato farms. In addition, local rental companies, restaurants and hotels benefit, considering that the production crew stays overnight and sleeps in nearby bungalow parks over the course of three weeks. These local economic activities are also reasons for the municipality to get involved.

Social impact

Over the past 15 years, MOJO has been active in making the Lowlands' production as sustainable as possible. This is partly out of their own motivations to contribute to a better environment and partly out of mandatory legislation regarding how Dutch companies should deal with plastic disposables, such as cups, plates and cutlery. The legislation mainly relates to the reuse of materials and their environmental impact. Lowlands is thinking about solutions and technologies that can meet this legal standard. This mainly manifests in their choices related to transport, energy, waste, water and catering. Lowlands has therefore joined the Plastic Pact NL of the Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management. This new collaborative initiative is committed to reducing the amount of plastic packaging and increasing the festival's involvement in the circular economy (Lowlands, n,d). For Lowlands, this means that all disposable products are made of biobased materials, which are recycled or composted.

Another example is the solar park that was built in the parking lots of Lowlands. It covers an area of 35 hectares, making it one of the largest solar carports in the world. It consists of 90,000 solar panels, with which around 35,000,000 kWh of electricity is produced annually. It supplies approximately 10,000 households with green energy. This is equivalent to the power consumption of about 100 Lowlands weekends per year (Lowlands, n,d). In addition, 43% of the festival's CO2 emissions are caused by public transport to and from the festival. MOJO therefore encourages visitors to use public transport by providing free shuttle bus transport.

Finally, together with suppliers, agreements are made about the options for reducing the amount and type of waste. For instance, the public catering companies separate waste into bottles, paper, glass and plastic, and tech companies are increasingly using more sustainable lamps (LEDs) and video systems, making use of these as consciously as possible.

Cultural impact

Because of COVID-19, Lowlands and many other festivals were cancelled. According to the director of Lowlands, this was a major cultural loss. Although digital alternatives were organised, this could hardly ease the pain because of the festival's key characteristic as an experience good:

People really want to be there. An event is a gathering of like-minded souls. The content is almost like a filter. When you go to a concert or festival, you know that's where you meet your peers. People who like the same things. The gathering of like-minded people. Everyone is potentially a friend of yours. There are no confrontational groups. You are of the world. You can dance together. That's what people are now missing and crave for. Nostalgia for an event with peers.

Because of COVID-19, the director of Lowlands feels people are yearning for music festivals. For the summer, he expects a major peak and increase in demand. After the poor turnover and financial losses of the past two years, many companies in the festival sector look forward to this potential surge.

Lowlands' cultural offerings are diverse. According to the director of Lowlands, this diversity is what attracts people in the first place. Rather than hiring a few of the biggest A-list artists, Lowlands focuses on providing their audience with an array of genres, from small-scale and less experienced bands to bands from various countries:

We've always had a lot of bands from all kinds of nooks and crannies, but a lot of festivals don't. (...) You can actually see a shift to Europe in the professionalisation of the pop music industry. The Anglo-Saxons are facing increasing competition from the European market. (...) There are more and more European artists from Spain and France, for example, which is also encouraged. You have a few programs, Eurosonic for instance. Where you get money from Europe, to... ETEP is what it's called, European Talent Exchange Program. If I book a band from Bulgaria, I get 1000 euros or so.

Lowlands' cultural offerings extend beyond a diverse range of music and also focus on acts in theatre, film, comedy, literature, street theatre, science and visual arts. Part of this array of cultural offerings is financially stimulated by the Dutch ministry. The aforementioned potential and opportunity to innovate may well have resulted in Lowlands creating part of what we understand a music festival to be today.

Besides the cultural impact that Lowlands has on visitors, it also contributes to the cultural image of the municipality of Dronten. Because of its years of collaboration with MOJO, the municipality is ahead of other municipalities when it comes to organising festivals. They are often asked to share their knowledge. It brings them pride to be known as an 'event municipality'.

3.2.6 Conclusions

With an audience of approximately 60,000 each year, Lowlands is one of the largest festivals in the Netherlands and is highly regarded by the general public. Every year, the three days full of performances are broadcasted live on Dutch television. While the dominant social, economic, and cultural focus is on these three days and its aftermath, there are much more complex logistics preceding the event that go unseen. By means of the GPN approach, we sought to offer a more comprehensive perspective of Lowlands – one that zooms in on different actors and activities along all stages of production.

We identified and analysed the crucial activities – as well as the broader context in which these activities take place – that are necessary to organise Lowlands. Because of the festival’s considerable size, a few of MOJO’s employees actively plan the event throughout the year. Early stages of evaluation and conceptualisation are followed by consultations with specialised suppliers and strategic partners to see whether and how ideas can be worked out in concrete terms. Hence, throughout the year, both MOJO and the municipality and the dedicated suppliers and strategic partners prepare for the three days in August.

Perhaps the most important aspect when planning for Lowlands is the urgency to innovate in order to stay ‘hip’ and ‘relevant’. Every edition, MOJO is contemplating how to surprise its audience with something new, especially now that competition from other festivals is increasing. To achieve this innovation, MOJO depends on the input of a number of essential partners, with whom they have been working for years and who are hard to replace in the short term. Rather than arm’s length ties, this approach makes for deep, stable, socially embedded relationships based on mutual trust. While the suppliers depend on MOJO as an important customer, MOJO, in turn, relies on its partners to deliver the specific knowledge, skills and equipment necessary to develop new forms of performances. Over the years and through processes of successive learning, MOJO and its partners have gradually acquired knowledge and gained repetitive ‘scripts’, which have enabled them to become more efficient. In addition, by collaborating on Lowlands for several years, both the festival organisation and the suppliers have built up knowledge and expanded, and the production network has this way become more institutionalised.

The GPN approach has allowed us to analyse these sustainable relationships in detail and uncover a web of mutual dependencies as an essential part of the production network. Furthermore, it has revealed the motives of the actors involved. Despite irregular working hours and pressure to perform, each actor emphasised his or her intrinsic motivation to work in this sector. These motives were not reflected in the statistical mapping, which primarily focused on economic value. Because of this intrinsic motivation, many actors have been working in the festival sector for decades, gradually building up experience. This was also visible in the case of Lowlands, which showed an accumulation of knowledge within its network, allowing for a high degree of efficiency.

3.3 Case 2: Nederlands Dans Theater: *Tell your mom you love your skin*

Source: Rahi Rezvani

'...it seemed like whoever was exciting in the dance world had been creating at NDT'
NDT dancer

'And it [NDT] is a legend, of course, because of Kylián and the whole history of the house. So I have known of it since I was a very, very young student, really.'
Choreographer Alan Lucien Øyen

3.3.1 Phases, actors, and locations

On September 23, 2021, a new modern dance work called *Tell your mom you love your skin* premiered for the opening of the Amare cultural centre in The Hague. This large, eye-catching centre finally opened after a long and tortuous political struggle, a few construction issues and a series of lockdowns due to the pandemic. In addition to housing Nederlands Dans Theater (NDT), it is also home to the

Koninklijk Conservatorium and the Residentie Orkest Den Haag. Besides comprising a set of stages – including one specifically designed for large modern dance performances – Amare also has rooms for rehearsal, costume making, physiotherapy and management as well as a restaurant. Emily Molnar, the artistic director, specifically asked Alan Lucien Øyen, a Norwegian choreographer, to come up with a new and innovative dance work to celebrate the opening of ‘the house for the arts, events, education and cultural encounter’ (<https://www.amare.nl/nl>).

Figure 6. The new Amare theatre in The Hague

Source: www.denhaag.com

The adjective ‘innovative’ here is much more than just a cliché: innovation is at the very heart of the mission of NDT, and this aim permeates the whole organisation. Within the performing arts, NDT is a leader in terms of its international status and reputation, its scale and its explicit mission to innovate. *Tell your mom you love your skin*, then, should provide a window into the production network of a performance that is primarily focused on creating innovative cultural value. Below, we first provide a brief analysis of the economic context of modern dance and, more specifically, how NDT can be situated in this context.

A writer may start on their own working from home. The same can be said for many types of music. Modern dance is rather different. One needs at least a small group of dancers and a space for practicing (dancers have to practice on a daily basis), and quite soon one also needs sound and light engineers to make a performance happen. The threshold, then, for modern dance companies to be able to function is relatively high. In addition, modern dance is almost by definition a niche: ‘Modern dance is not, and probably never has been, a broadly familiar art’ (Sussmann, 1998: 57), and ‘[w]e also know that modern dance was, from its beginning, an art for a circumscribed status group’ (ibid., 61). Classical ballet can rarely survive on the market (Towse, 2010: 96), and this holds even more so for

modern dance companies, which cannot fall back on ‘old warhorses’, such as *Swan Lake* and *The Nutcracker* to generate a more or less certain stream of income (ibid, 97). Because of these factors, combined with an explicit focus on innovative performances, a different type of funding is required (Kloosterman and Brandellero, 2010; Kloosterman, 2014).

Innovation in the arts is difficult to measure. Still, it makes sense to think in Schumpeterian terms of introducing new combinations which may amount to a significantly higher level of non-conformity (‘the divergence of programming of an art institution from others in the field’, Brandellero and Kloosterman, 2010; 65). This non-conformity is closely related to the composition of the audience, according to DiMaggio and Stenberg (1985), who assume that audiences with higher levels of cultural capital demand higher levels of innovation.

In modern dance, innovation may comprise exploring new ways of performing with regards to combinations of moves, sound, light, costumes, stories and stage setting. Innovation combines existing elements with previous modern dance works in novel ways, and these may be found in other art forms (e.g. new music styles) and technology (e.g. the use of screens and digital technology). The essence of innovation is taking risks, an approach which is in marked contrast to the umpteenth performance of *The Nutcracker*. More generally, experimentation seems to be the essence of modern dance. According to Leila Sussmann (1998: 61) ‘Experimentation’ and ‘variety among choreographers’ are values by which modern dance has defined itself. It has no ‘academy’, no movement vocabulary common to all choreographers. It has sought to be an avant-gardist art, constantly pushing the boundaries of what dance might be. Each choreographer tries to ‘make it new’. The modern dance fans appear to share these values.’ This drive towards innovation is also contingent on the institutional embeddedness of each dance company because higher levels of public funding allow for greater scope for innovation and risk-taking.

NDT shows this in a very clear way: It is largely structurally funded by the Dutch state and the city of The Hague. According to NDT’s proposed budget of 2021 (which eventually was affected by the COVID-19 crisis), no less than two thirds of its total income of 15,036,433 EUR came from these two sources, with 7,423,061 EUR from the national government and 2,616,787 EUR from the city of The Hague (NDT, 2021a). This solid financial base enables NDT to largely eschew a standard repertoire and to prioritise cultural value above economic value – that is, to take risks. It, moreover, also provides the financial muscle to pay over 40 dancers; more than 20 people working in sound, light and stage set-up; and seven people working in the costume department. In total, NDT employs some 110 people (NDT, 2021a: 57).

The secure and sizeable funding and the size of the workforce of NDT are the necessary conditions to pursue and realise its mission, and according to its yearly report be ‘a leading contemporary dance company that profiles itself through creation, research and talent development’ (NDT, 2021a: 9). Its mission is ‘to present unique experiences and perspectives through dance’. To accomplish this, NDT is constantly pursuing innovation and collaborating with international choreographers and artists.

Given its reputation, it is also able to tap into an international pool of the best dancers. According to the choreographer of *Tell your mom you love your skin*, Alan Lucien Øyen, NDT has the ‘best people in business’. Its international orientation is also apparent from its touring map, which comprises Europe, the Americas, Asia and Australia.

The secure funding of NDT does not mean that attendance is completely irrelevant. As Heilbrun and Gray (1993, p. 121) have argued, the ‘motivation of a performing arts enterprise in the not-for-profit sector can be described as follows: over an appropriate period of time, the firm tries to maximise attendance, while presenting a repertoire that meets its own quality standards, subject to the constraint that revenues from the box office plus other sources must be sufficient to cover costs.’ In the case of NDT, these quality standards are evidently couched in terms of innovation, and these are the first and overriding concerns.

Right from its founding in 1959 in The Hague, NDT has aimed at presenting original, innovative works. NDT prides itself on its ‘nonconformist, progressive productions’, and many of the creations of NDT later become premieres for modern dance companies elsewhere, thus illustrating its pioneering role in global modern dance. In the 2021–22 theatre season, Nederlands Dans Theater staged no fewer than 13 world premieres (NDT, 2021b). NDT, thus, is clearly accustomed to a continuous cycle of generating new projects, which involve creating, practising, preparing the stage setting, performing, touring, evaluating and archiving. The whole organisational format of NDT is geared towards this cycle of new performances. ‘We are a creation-based company’ said NDT’s artistic director Emily Molnar.

Against this backdrop, in line with its core mission, NDT commissioned the young and upcoming choreographer Alan Lucien Øyen in 2021 to create a new modern dance work which would be premiered when The Hague’s prestigious new multifunctional cultural centre, Amare, would open. We chose this work, *Tell your mom you love your skin*, to better understand the production network of an innovative performance. Below, we offer a brief analysis, using key elements of the GPN approach in order to identify the phases, actors and locations that have been crucial in the trajectory of a choreographer’s first idea of a new modern dance work to its actual realisation on stage in front of an audience. We, thus, applied the GPN phases grid to explore the production network of the *Tell your mom you love your skin* performance. We did this in a critical way as because this neat sequence of phases fits the case at hand only partly. Nevertheless, this approach enables us to disentangle the network in a meaningful way and, notably, to understand the spatial footprint and governance structure of the network, and the relationship between these two aspects.

Locations

The geographical anchor point of the *Tell your mom you love your skin* project is the Amare building in The Hague. This is where it all comes together and from where the project is funded, coordinated, monitored, controlled, distributed, and archived. As we have seen, however, crucial inputs – notably

the choreographer and his team – come from abroad, even from outside the EU. In addition, NDT performances go on tour to the Americas, Asia and Australia. Most of the dancers of NDT also hail from abroad – for instance from Canada and Japan. Notwithstanding these international linkages, NDT is anything but footloose as it is dependent on the funding of the Ministry of Culture and the city of The Hague and, more concretely, the Amare building, which provides a first-class infrastructure (e.g. venue, sound and light facilities, costume department and exercise rooms).

To map the network of *Tell your mom you love your skin*, we conducted interviews with the key actors – the choreographer, the artistic director, dancers, stage manager, head of the costume-making department and the head of the firm making the props for the performance. Because of COVID-19 restrictions, the first batch of interviews was done through Zoom. After a gradual lifting of these restrictions in the Netherlands in the Summer of 2021, we conducted interviews on site. We visited the firm making the props, and we were present both at the final rehearsal and the premiere of *Tell your mom you love your skin* at Amare. We, thus, observed a crucial stage in the creation and production process as well as the first presentation to an audience.

After applying the different phases – creation, production, distribution, exchange and archiving – to the network of the *Tell your mom you love your skin*, we also considered the spatial footprint and governance issues from a theoretical point of view.

Table 13. Case 2: Key actors, their role and home base location in the production network

Function	Name	Based in
Artistic director	Emily Molnar (NDT)	Canada
Technical director	Eric Blom (NDT)	Netherlands
Company Management	Linda de Boer (NDT)	Netherlands
Company Management	Maarten van Herwijnen (NDT)	Netherlands
Dancers	16 dancers (NDT1)	Canada (4), US (4), Japan (2), Switzerland (2), Scotland, Denmark, Portugal
Costume making	Yolanda Klompstra (NDT)	Netherlands
NDT assistant	Francesca Caroti (NDT)	Netherlands
Choreographer	Alan Lucien Øyen	Norway
Light design	Avi Yona Bueno Bambi	Israel
Choreographic Assistant	Olivia Ancona (Team Alan)	US
Stage design	Åsmund Færavaag (Team Alan)	Norway
Sound engineer	Gunnar Invær (Team Alan)	Norway
Costume design	Stine Sjøgren (Team Alan)	Norway

Music	Hania Rani	Poland
Stage construction/making of props	Kloosterboer	Netherlands

Phases

Creation

NDT tends to follow a specific format for the creation of a new work. NDT hires an outside choreographer who brings their own creative team. While the dancers, management, supporting staff, and much of the in-house lighting and sound crew and stage production stay the same, the choreographers and their teams (typically consisting of a costume designer, a set designer, light designer and a rehearsal director) come and go. By commissioning choreographers from the outside, NDT aims to create a process of rupture and innovation.

When the contract with the choreographer is signed, there are few budget constraints – the strictest is arguably the *tourability*, which is the requirement that all the props should fit within one standard shipping container so that they can be taken on intercontinental tours (interview Technical Director). There are also budget constraints regarding the cost of the props and costumes, but they are more negotiable than the portability of the props (interview Technical Director and Costume Director).

This large span of artistic freedom was also given to Alan Lucien Øyen. He already knew artistic director Emily Molnar from her previous jobs, and they were for a long-time part of network meetings in New York (interview choreographer). She trusted him to come up with a new modern dance work that would live up to the standard and reputation of NDT. This trust was apparently so high that Alan Lucien Øyen ‘just about a week ago . . . gave us the first draft’ (introductory presentation by Emily Molnar on the evening of the premiere). In fact, Alan Lucien Øyen felt that he was given ‘carte blanche’. Moreover, he felt ‘super fortunate’ to be able to work with ‘highly trained dancers’ whose ‘skill set is very high’.

In the process of the creation of a modern dance work, there is a continuum from high involvement, interaction and co-creation between the choreographer and dancers to a choreography more or less scripted solely by the choreographer. In the first case, the preparatory phase is an integral part of the creation (and discovery) process. In the latter case, the dancers’ primary responsibility is to learn the moves; they are not so much subjects as (moving) objects.

In the case of *Tell your mom you love your skin*, there was much co-creation, and the dancers were actively involved. Alan Lucien Øyen referred to his willingness to stay open in order to create space for experimentation:

'Yeah, I mean, it's a feature of contemporary dance, I think very much more so that it's a place where the people are involved in the process, have a willingness and an expectation and understanding that they can go anywhere else. If you come into a classical, traditional ballet company, for instance, if we look at just dance, there's an expectation of: 'I imagine this kind of expression, I imagine this kind of dance, these are the steps.' Most often I'll show you the steps and teach you and you do them, or it's a story ballet where there's a clear kind of background. A lot more exists when you come into the process and there is more willingness to stay open. This is also, of course, depending on the ballet company. Some ballet companies are very open, some are very closed. But in contemporary dance companies that only do contemporary work, there's more often an understanding that, OK, we don't know where we're going, but we try. We are willing to explore.'

'In the beginning, I was also creating the steps myself. And then at one point I started working with dancers who were so skilled and had so much movement history in their bodies, that I felt like it was kind of limiting if I were to limit their vocabulary to my body, kind of. So I started collaborating with them and I also felt that they had a need and a want to create more.'

Choreographer Alan Lucien Øyen

Alan Lucien Øyen deliberately aimed for processes of co-creation because he wanted to have 'an open narrative' and was 'looking for a storyline with the dancers'. This was especially evident when dancers were asked to contribute their own storylines to the spoken word parts of the work – one of the more innovative, theatrical elements in *Tell your mom you love your skin*. Reviewers of *Tell your mom you love your skin* emphasised the prominent role of spoken word as an innovative element in modern dance (e.g. Lubberding, 2021).

The key elements in the actual process of creation of *Tell your mom you love your skin* thus came together at a local scale – namely, the Amare building in The Hague. These elements were supplied locally, the NDT facilities; nationally, the props; and internationally, a choreographer, stage designer, costume designer and sound engineer from Norway, a light designer from Israel, and dancers originating from a number of countries. The spatial footprint of this phase in terms of activities was highly concentrated, with people coming from abroad (including outside the EU). This spatial issue arises as these dedicated and strategic suppliers provide services which can only be delivered in a face-to-face setting: Rehearsing the movements of the dancers or setting the light has to be done on the spot in a process of intense interaction. So, crucial inputs for the creation were globally sourced.

Production

Production and creation, notably in the case of *Tell your mom you love your skin*, are hard to separate because they are intimately intertwined in a process of continuous interaction. During the final

rehearsal, we observed how works of the performance puzzle were coming together in a dialogue between the choreographer, his crew, NDT technical staff and the dancers. During this phase, they all negotiated with and navigated through the organisation and facilities of NDT. In this process, decisions with respect to light, sound and stage setting evolve.

The infrastructure of light and sound systems is already in place in Amare, but costumes and props are an integral and unique part of a performance. Regarding this infrastructure and the other items needed for the performance, one overriding concern was shared by the actors with respect to quality: the tolerance for substandard was very low, and there is high attention to detail. The suppliers, hence, have to be able to meet these requirements. In addition to having to meet the technical standards, they also have to understand the aesthetic elements which the choreographer and designers of the stage and the costumes want to project. In order to function within such a network, the actors involved should be members of a kind of a specialised art world (Becker, 1982) or artistic community (Cohendet and Simon, 2007: 591). That is, they 'share knowledge on an informal basis, they work in the same building, have lunch and go out together or they just chat online with peers in search of advice or technical solutions. They respect the social norms of their community that drive their behaviour and beliefs. Within a given community knowledge is continuously exchanged and can circulate through the existence of a local language understandable by the members only'. This shared value system and shared vocabulary not only comprises those who work for NDT in the Amare building but also stretches out to the dedicated suppliers.

We came across this sense of community belonging when we looked at the making of costumes. The making of ballet and dance costumes is a highly specialised craft because of the requirements regarding fit (all costumes are bespoke to achieve the best fit), stretch, colours and appearance. This work typically takes place in-house by the NDT costume department, which includes two distinct wardrobes: the 'making wardrobe', which incorporates the making of the costume during pre-production, and the 'running wardrobe', which takes care of the maintenance and continuity of costumes during a series of performances. When a capacity shortage arises, the making of the costumes is outsourced to a trusted dedicated supplier specialising in ballet and dance costumes.

We also observed these community characteristics in the attitude of the maker of the props of *Tell your mom you love your skin* – in this case, a dedicated supplier from the outside. Here as well, the maker of the props has to understand the wishes and the vocabulary of the stage designer. The making of props can be a demanding task because they are often custom, unique elements that have to meet very special requirements with respect to material, appearance, reflection, weight, robustness and tourability. Only a few firms in the Netherlands are able to meet these standards. In the case of *Tell your mom you love your skin*, NDT asked Kloosterboer Decor BV to make the large wooden squares (on special request of the stage designer, made from Polish pine) to hang from the ceiling above the stage. Kloosterboer specialises 'in design and construction of interiors for museums, exhibitions, theme parks, restaurants and decor for theatre, television and film' (Kloosterboer website). The firm is housed in three large construction halls and located in an unremarkable business park in Purmerend,

a suburb to the north of Amsterdam. Given the price of land in Amsterdam, such a large space would be very expensive and probably drive Kloosterboer out of business. In addition, it would probably also be quite hard for this firm to find the specialised carpenters (including women), welders and other highly skilled craftsmen in Amsterdam.

Kloosterboer has a long-term relationship with NDT based on mutual trust. 'Trust is the most important, if you betray that trust the client is gone . . . the price is less important than a more permanent relationship,' according to Jan Zijp, managing director of Kloosterboer. He added that they have to 'go with the image' projected by the designer. He and his colleagues also want to contribute to creating something of aesthetic and cultural value – they are indeed active members of the art world and the artistic community. Communication between NDT and Kloosterboer is cordial and informal, and they easily work together, building on a foundation of trust and understanding.

The issue of trust also emerged when discussing the logistics. NDT has a tradition of touring, both within the Netherlands and abroad. The transport is provided by a dedicated supplier. Therefore, the production activities for a project are the result of a co-creation process between NDT and external, project-based crews. And these companies and their products are not easily replaced.

'If those [touring companies] fail, we have a big problem. If Piet Smit goes bankrupt, I have no more trucks. One could say; well, then take another truck. But no, those trucks have moving floors, drive up to our address, have special lifting mechanics. An ordinary transport firm does not have these types of trucks if they are used to transporting flower bulbs or cheeses.'

Technical Director NDT

Distribution

It is hard to draw a boundary between the creation and production phases as well as between the production and the distribution phases. A modern dance work is created, rehearsed (or produced) and eventually performed in front of an audience (or distributed) at the premiere. If successful, NDT goes on tour performing that work in other places; in a sense, the work is being (re)produced every time it is performed. The package of movements, music, props, light and soundscapes travels with the NDT crew. The spatial footprint of this phase usually has a global dimension, as NDT regularly performs in the Americas, Asia and Australia.

As during the premiere, each performance requires the coming together of different actors and elements (costumes, lighting and sound systems, props) in one place at one time. It is the phase in which the ideas from the choreographer's mind are translated into reality. During this phase, NDT is very much in control. As Caves (2000, p.8) noted, 'The performing arts and creative activities involving complex teams – the motley crew property – obviously require close temporal coordination of their

activities', and this is exactly what NDT does. In terms of the two key dimensions of the GPN approach, this phase (although not neatly separable from the production phase) is global, and NDT is clearly the lead actor.

Exchange

Evaluation of a concrete project – a painting, book or modern dance performance – is an essential part of the CCS. From a production network approach point of view, this evaluation takes place in the exchange phase. From a sociological and geographical perspective, the evaluation is an integral part of an 'art world' (Becker, 1982), a 'creative field' (Bourdieu, 1993), or a localised 'ecosystem' (Scott, 2000). These social configurations not only comprise artists and support activities but also include 'curatorial practices and 'boundary personnel' who operate at the interface of creation, production and consumption, actuating as a filtering or selection process' (Brandellero and Kloosterman, 2020: 168). Evaluation processes, then, are deeply embedded in these socio-spatial configurations. Members of the audience make their own evaluations, but professional art critics and reviewers are a crucial element in this process. This also holds for the assessment of modern dance performances, which requires knowledge of an art form which has its very own language and tradition.

In the case of *Tell your mom you love your skin*, at the time of this research, there were only a limited number of reviews by these professional tastemakers. Moreover, these evaluation were all by Dutch reviewers because *Tell your mom you love your skin* had only been performed in the Netherlands due to COVID-19 restrictions preventing the possibility of international touring. The reputation of Alan Lucien Øyen as an innovative choreographer who combines dance, text, music and mime was mentioned by the reviewers (Hiskemuller, 2021; Wiel, 2021). There was, however, also a consensus among the reviewers that they lost their way in this dense performance (Embregts, 2021; Hiskemuller, 2021; Wiel, 2021). They appreciated individual moments of the performance. One wrote, 'Øyen's use of this trendy physical textuality, which works with words as movement, is beautifully set and individually rendered but after a while all the fragments end up feeling a bit the same' (Thunnissen, 2021). At the time of this research, it was arguably still too early.

Archiving

The preservation of modern dance works is rather more difficult than, say, that of music, films or books. Modern dance can only to some extent be captured through notation.¹ Still, archiving is of crucial importance for NDT. First, it is important because NDT may want to evaluate and reflect on a performance. Second, NDT may want to tap into its rich back catalogue and perform a work again (often in combination with a new one). Third, after being premiered by NDT, many works are performed by other dance companies in the world. Fourth, these archives may also function as a

¹ This seemed to be even more true for the Netherlands as Stokvis (1995: 77) observed that "Dance notation never acquired the same status as music notation and in Holland dance notation is not at all widely practised."

source of inspiration for choreographers and dancers and lay the foundation for new works. Archiving in the case of modern dance means first and foremost filming, and this is clearly of strategic importance for NDT. *Tell your mom you love your skin* was recorded by NDT's own film crew. By uploading on social media and YouTube, the images can also be used as promotional material to attract audiences and to inspire dancers and choreographers:

'They [NDT] are just known as a place that kind of excels all other places in terms of innovative, exciting, contemporary dance and new choreographies. Growing up, I was watching all the videos and all the content, as an online window into the company. I was just kind of swallowed by their world because they were so good at marketing. All the choreographers that are coming in, and it seemed like whoever was exciting in the dance world had been creating at NDT. So I thought, as someone who wants to be in creations and do this kind of thing, this is the highest place to go.'

NDT dancer

The process of archiving is first and foremost the responsibility of NDT. Access to its archives is, however, limited as there are also intellectual property rights involved regarding not only movements but also the setting, costumes and props.

The filming of performances acquired a new dimension during the pandemic. By streaming (behind a paywall), a global audience can, in principle, be reached in real time. Live streaming has rapidly become a new source of income for NDT. The premiere of *Tell your mom you love your skin* was also streamed, thereby adding a borderless online audience to the one in Amare.

3.3.2 Relationships between actors

The power structure in the creation phase of the *Tell your mom you love your skin* resembles that of Russian dolls, where each is positioned within (the power of) another, and so on. Although NDT chooses the choreographer at the start of the creation process and subsequently provides the key components of the performance (dancers, facilities, network of venues for touring, and the reputation of NDT), it aims to make as much room as possible for the choreographer (and their team): the 'carte blanche' that Alan Lucien Øyen mentioned. It effectively delegates much power to the choreographer in order to foster a climate of artistic experimentation and innovation. Nevertheless, the control of the network – both regarding in-house and outside suppliers – remains with NDT.

NDT is without doubt the lead actor throughout the different phases; it organises the production network from the creation phase to the archiving phase. Its control over the exchange phase is rather limited as this is where art critics and tastemakers come in. NDT derives its powerful position from its

combination of financial strength, the quality of its dancers, the supporting staff and its management, and its global reputation. This enables NDT to pursue its mission of creating cultural value in the form of innovative dance performances. This additive value of a work takes place not merely during the performance but also in the creation process. In the words of the artistic director Emily Molnar,

‘Process should be as important as the product and basically success should be driven by what was everyday life on the way to getting there. Of course, we have a masterwork that exists for 20 years? That’s phenomenal. But to say that’s the only measure of success is, I think, defeating the purpose and really working against innovation because the only way for innovation to exist is if it’s actually OK to produce a work that may never have a life. Everything you did along the way, you learned a bunch of new tools, so I can say, you know, for instance, what if we never do Alan’s work again? What we can still say is, but that self-directed environment was very new for some dancers and they learned something from that. That was a success, and they will bring that into the next process. And eventually it’s like a building block. It’s a long term project innovation, you know. And so it’s about creating a value system, I think, around an environment versus an actual end result.’

Emily Molnar, artistic director NDT

Becoming part of NDT is only for the few; it is highly competitive to get into the organisation. During the auditions, people line up on the streets.

‘In my youth, when I came to work at NDT, in ‘89 for the first time. They [dancers] would lie in a sleeping bag in the alley close to NDT, just to audition the next day. This is not a joke. They were sleeping there. Just like playing for the ultimate football team, like FC Barcelona. That happened when we were auditioning. From far and wide, from all over the world, people come to NDT. It’s not as extreme as those times, but for many dancers there is still one goal and one goal only: dancing at NDT. As a dancer you have one goal and that is ending up at NDT.’

Technical Director Eric Blom

3.3.3 Positioning the case with the typology matrix

Table 14. Case 2: positioning the case in the typology matrix

PRODUCTION NETWORK PHASES	Local/regional	National	Intra-EU	Global	GOVERNANCE
Creation				X	
Production				X	

Distribution				X	
Exchange		X			
Archiving				X	
Network level					Hierarchical

The production network of *Tell your mom you love your skin* is global in its creation, distribution and production phases, during which NDT is the lead actor. However, as mentioned above, in the creation and the production phases, the choreographer and his team have a lot of freedom to create. In addition, there are no neat boundaries between creation and production nor between production and distribution. The exchange phase, with its evaluation processes, was mostly national at the time of this research because *Tell your mom you love your skin* had only been performed in the Netherlands. In this phase, different actors are involved without any clear lead. Archiving is a core responsibility of NDT to preserve its performances. The trailers on YouTube are globally accessible and play an important role in international online communities focused on modern dance.

3.3.4 Dynamics: changes over time

‘Are we, as NDT, sixty years old, or sixty years young?’ is the question that NDT artistic director Emily Molnar posed in her introductory speech, in which she announced the *Tell your mom you love your skin* performance. Her question reflects an important attitude of the organisation which can be extended towards a larger segment of the contemporary dance and other cultural and creative sectors. What is the role of tradition, and how can one build on tradition to be innovative? On this point, Emily Molnar said the following:

‘Who are we then as a company in this climate right now in the arts? Who do we have to be? We’re in a new building, so there’s a lot of questions of what is our relevancy? The obvious is that we still are an international company. We are still making new work. But what does that mean when you have this other kind of environment around you? What does it mean to create? It’s also an extremely challenging moment, as you can imagine with COVID, with the fact that we travel so much as a company, what is it going to mean for the environment? What is it going to mean for us in terms of funding? You know, you can piece all of these questions together, but it’s so obvious to me that NDT will continue to be what we are just because we were.’

Emily Molnar, artistic director NDT

A key dynamic over time that is relevant in the field of contemporary dance has to do with the fact that in dance, the human body is the instrument and the canvas. An unescapable truth of using the human body as a (moving) cultural object or subject is that a process of aging occurs and affects what

can be created and produced by a person. Artistic director Emily Molnar recognised this as she recounted the hurdles that NDT encounters:

‘Well, two things happen. We lose our mid-career artists, and we shouldn’t. They basically leave the profession too early because I don’t think that we have developed them enough or given them enough stuff or enough tools. And also choreographers, I think, are having to overproduce. So then, they also get burnt out. And this also is connected.

As we are a profession that requires someone dancing, specifically classical ballet, because a lot of our lineage comes from classical ballet, even though we are not a classical ballet company, the training is similar. So we will have dancers like myself who were at a very young age, 10 years old, we were deciding to be professional dancers. It may not have happened, but we said, that’s going to be my focus. We are asking people to make that decision when most people are, you know, playing in the school ground or something, they start getting serious and thinking about what they’re majoring in in university in their late twenties. That’s exactly when most dancers are looking at the middle of their careers. When most people’s careers are taking off, a dancer’s career is in transition. So that makes us very different than others.’

Emily Molnar, artistic director NDT

3.3.5 Impact

Economic impact

The direct contribution in economic terms comprises obviously the 110 people who work for NDT in The Hague. To this, we could add the employment generated through outsourcing the creation of the props, the creation of the costumes (when NDT has insufficient capacity) and the use of logistical services when touring. As we have seen, when we looked at the production network of *Tell your mom you love your skin*, NDT demands very high quality. As in the case of the maker of the props, this focus on quality when outsourcing pushes a supplier to meet these standards – that is, making unique, custom objects which require skilled craftsmanship. This, in turn, helps a supplier to review and, if necessary, upgrade its production process.

We can also look at the indirect economic contribution of NDT. It is both a niche oriented and large scale cultural amenity (Kloosterman, 2014: 2417). NDT accordingly caters to the demanding taste of connoisseurs and is housed in a high-profile flagship building in the very centre of The Hague. Although its threshold in terms of cultural capital is relatively high, NDT can still attract large crowds by tapping into large catchment areas of national and often even international scope. Admirers of modern dance

are sometimes willing to travel long distances (Kloosterman, 2014: 2519-20). NDT, hence, adds to the quality of place in The Hague, making it more attractive for particular (typically highly educated) categories to visit, work or live. In addition, a performance in Amare of *Tell your mom you love your skin* in the main theatre hall, which has a capacity of 1300, seats also generates instant demand for the local hospitality sector.

Social impact

In a sense, the careers of dancers, athletes and models are similar. They all are based on physical performances and require not just talent but also perseverance and stamina. Their careers also typically start at a relatively young age and tend to end in their thirties. However, whereas top models and top athletes are able to negotiate (sometimes exceptionally) high wages, the labour conditions and wages of the world-class dancers of NDT are rather modest and determined by the Dutch national collective agreements for dancers. For dancers, then, the wage starts at 2304 EUR for beginners and tops at 4027 EUR for experienced dancers (gross monthly wage per 1-1-2022; *Cao Toneel en Dans; 1 januari 2022 – 31 december 2023*, 2022: 40). Not even the most financially conservative dancer can save enough during their active career to live off. Like many other forms of artistic labour, these dancers have a strong intrinsic motivation to make art (Caves, 2000). As Throsby (2010: 81) states, 'They have a positive preference for working at their chosen profession', and 'they derive psychic income from practice as an artist'. Their work with its strong sense of self-expression, then, generates positive affective qualities (Gill and Pratt, 2008: 15).

On a different level, labour conditions are also relevant with respect to their innovative potential: how can modern dance continue evolving and innovating given the limits of the bodies producing those movements? Emily Molnar sees opportunity in training and choreography:

'We need choreographers that are going to continue to invest in body because the dancers that are entering into the professional field now can do things that we could never do 20 or 30 years ago. The training is maturing, so the physical body is actually getting smarter with each generation, but not always showing up in this ability to actually rigorously investigate. So we have to train that as well. But I would say that we haven't actually touched the limits of what the body can do.'

Emily Molnar, artistic director NDT

Cultural impact

NDT is a global player in innovative modern dance. According to Alan Lucien Øyen, he was 'invited' and 'honoured' to work with NDT:

'And it [NDT] is a legend, of course, because of Kylián and the whole history of the house. So I have known of it since I was a very, very young student, really'

Alan Lucien Øyen

One could argue about the cultural impact of *Tell your mom you love your skin* given its relative modest exposure to audiences at the time of this research. Still, as a niche-oriented and large-scale cultural amenity, NDT has a significant cultural impact on a local, national and global scale. More recently, NDT has been aiming to become more diverse in terms of dancers, choreographers and audience.

3.3.6 Conclusions: *Dancing in the dark*

We used a production network approach to analyse how *Tell your mom you love your skin* evolved from an idea into a full modern dance performance. *Tell your mom you love your skin* is locally anchored through funding and a well-developed infrastructure of both hardware (stages, exercise rooms, lighting and sound technology) and software (staff with its knowledge and networks). However, like other projects of NDT, *Tell your mom you love your skin* is also globalised in its collaboration with creative sources (the creation and production phase) and in its performing for audiences across the globe. NDT is the lead actor in organising the networks of creation, production, distribution and archiving. The exchange phase and the evaluation of the performance fall mostly outside the direct control of NDT. In the case of *Tell your mom you love your skin*, this stage was still confined to the Netherlands because touring abroad was not possible because of the pandemic restrictions.

Within the wider population of the CCS, *Tell your mom you love your skin* is a niche-oriented, large-scale project requiring a large staff and an expensive infrastructure. In this regard, it resembles opera and classic ballet performances. These kind of CCS endeavours are often funded by the government – state, city or both – in many countries because the sale of tickets cannot cover the total costs, including those of using the theatre or performance hall (Towse, 2010; Throsby, 2010; Kloosterman, 2014). The economic benefits are hard to quantify, but these expressions of what traditionally is defined as high culture are seen as important for the image of the city and even the country. These niche-oriented and large-scale cultural and creative projects usually presuppose a certain knowledge or cultural capital to be able to appreciate the performances. Given the distribution of this kind of cultural capital, these projects tend to cater to a higher-educated, middle-class audience. City-level policymakers in many countries even see such projects as positive location factors for highly skilled workers. The cultural impact, in addition, is considered a goal in itself: the preservation of timeless creations ranging from Bach's *Matthäus Passion* to Mahler's *2nd Symphony* to Stravinsky's *Rite of Spring*.

The *Tell your mom you love your skin*, however, although part of a niche-oriented and large-scale project, is rather different. Preservation is not the aim; innovation is. The whole organisation of NDT is geared towards creating cultural value through innovative modern dance performances. This mission is shared from the top of the management to the stage crew of NDT. The strong foundation provided by the state funding allows NDT to pursue that mission wholeheartedly. In their study on the *Cirque du Soleil*, Deborah Leslie and Norma Rantisi (2019: 261) showed how this outfit transitioned ‘from a business model focused on aesthetic innovation to one predicated primarily on profit and shareholder returns there is a shift away from an unregulated creation space and the open and adaptable script.’ NDT, by contrast, has the ‘independence and freedom to experiment’, which ‘can foster thinking outside the box and the forging of novel and innovative products’ (ibidem: 257). NDT, thus, has the power to take risks and be innovative (Castañer and Campos, 2002).

Viewing the *Tell your mom you love your skin* performance through the lens of different levels of embeddedness, we can observe the following configuration. The funding structure is part of the macro-level of embeddedness. The provision of the hard and soft infrastructure is first and foremost at the meso-level – more precisely, the environment offered by the Amare building in The Hague. The social networks comprising linkages to choreographers and suppliers are conspicuous forms of embeddedness on a micro-scale. The *Tell your mom you love your skin*, then, is the product of a complex, interlocking social process with different actors jointly engaged in the creation of something culturally worthwhile.

3.4 Case 3: Amalyashi Festival

Source: www.facebook.com/Amalyashi

3.4.1 Phases, actors, and locations

The first edition of the Amalyashi Festival was organised in Leiden, the Netherlands, in October 2021. The first part of the name 'Amalyashi' means 'hope' in Arabic, while 'yashi' stems from Bemba (the language spoken mainly in north-eastern Zambia); it means 'a lot of stories'. Hence, the objective of this storytelling festival was to bring hope through a lot of stories.

Organiser Tommy Sharif took the initiative. As a storyteller and actor, he has extensive experience and connections within the Dutch performance industry. He has told his story many times, for many different audiences. Arriving in the Netherlands as an Egyptian refugee in 2014, he was forced to start with nothing but an ambition to share, connect and 'build bridges'.

As he developed within the sector, he decided it was time to open the stage for others to tell their stories. With the help of his wife, friends, contacts, foundations and the municipality, he managed to create the concept and carry out the first edition of the Amalyashi Festival, with hopefully many more to follow.

The Amalyashi Festival can be distinguished from the other case studies in terms of location as it was a five-day festival, hosting 50 performances, carried out in three different locations: Leiden, Leiderdorp and Oegstgeest. Therefore, it was time-and-place specific but not based on one location and without an overnight program, like Lowlands. In a sense, the Amalyashi Festival was a collection of performances. Therefore, they did not need to apply for a permit for a festival.

The choice to perform at three different locations was for several reasons. Because the means and time did not allow the organisers to book one spot that was large enough to host the many performances, they had to opt for free or affordable venues and centres that are dedicated to helping and hosting these types of projects. Moreover, because the Amalyashi Festival strives to show the diversity and multiplicity of its collection of stories, and to connect different people in different neighbourhoods, it makes sense to perform at different locations to attract a wide audience. In Tommy Sharif’s words,

‘It’s brilliant to do that, yeah, give others a place to perform, yeah. Uh, teach them if they want to perform, but they don’t have enough experience. Give them the experience, teach them how to play. That was important for me. And we were supposed to do the same last year, but everything was stuck because of the Corona.’

‘I thought, Why we don’t make a festival in Leiden that goes every year? Yeah, and we make this mix. Beginners, experienced, in the middle. And our plan is give ideas, not just entertaining, because a lot of people do entertaining and no give like cabaret like, but they let people think they watch something and they think they get new ideas about different cultures. Yeah. Let them connect together through storytelling and, uh, theatre through arts.’

Organiser Tommy Sharif

In the table below, we can see activities and the different (interviewed) actors and the corresponding activities in each GPN phase.

Table 15. Case 3: Production phases, actors and their roles in the network

	Creation	Production	Distribution	Exchange	Archiving
Actors involved	Tommy Sharif, City of Leiden, VSB Foundation	Tommy Sharif Ahraf, storytellers and artists	Louisa	De Bakkerij	
Activities	Generating the idea, applying for loans and subsidies	Finding artists, preparing for the festival and the shows	Selling tickets and advertising	Promotion and performing	Recordings and next-years repeat

There are many more actors involved, and all from different backgrounds as that is what Amalyashi Festival is about.

'From the top of my head, in the performances, we have a young musician who's Dutch, he's from the South. Ok. And there is also, Sophie who's Dutch. There is a guy from, I think, from Wales or Northern Ireland, Ireland, I'm not sure, but it's from Great Britain. There is a Somali woman. She's a refugee. There is a Dutch Indian performer. There is also, let me think, um. A Dutch singer as well. Uh, there is a Greek actor, American actor, actress. Also an Irani. And an Egyptian. Yeah. Also Syrian, and there's even Palestinians. It's amazing. Actually, I didn't think about all these nationalities.'

Organiser Tommy Sharif

3.4.2 Relationships between actors

Creating a new festival is difficult. It involves a high level of risk in investment because of the requirement of a physical location and upfront labour costs. These structural entry barriers in the production market, in combination with the importance of social capital and generally low profit margins, make it difficult for new festivals to be successful and to achieve a critical size (EC, 2017). In contrast to Lowlands and the Nederlands Dans Theater, the Amalyashi Festival's future is still uncertain and depends on whether it will receive additional funding from the municipality.

Hence, when analysing the governance dynamics between actors, the municipality plays a crucial role in the realisation of the festival. The first edition of the Amalyashi Festival relied heavily on extra assistance and funding from the municipality and the VSB foundation.

Taking a closer look into the role that these two institutions played in assisting Tommy Sharif clarifies what they find important and what is considered 'worthy' of aid in the festival sector these days. The assistance went beyond financial support; both the municipality and the VSB foundation offered advice and consultation. To decide whether the Amalyashi Festival was eligible for assistance, the municipality of Leiden and the VSB foundation determined its added value through a score board, which ranked the applicant's submission by its most important themes and topics. It is interesting that the VSB foundation and the municipality considered similar themes important, but there were also some differences.

3.4.3 Positioning with the typology matrix

Table 16. Case 3: positioning the case in the typology matrix

PRODUCTION NETWORK PHASES	Local/regional	National	Intra-EU	Global	GOVERNANCE
Creation				X	
Production		X			
Distribution	X				
Exchange		X			
Archiving	X				
Network level					Horizontal/dispersed

The performers (storytellers, actors, musicians) come from many different countries and often carry a story of their migration or refuge to the Netherlands. That story often appears in their performance.

The Amalyashi Festival had hosted one edition at the time of this report. The goal of the organisers was to make it a annual event. Whether this is realised is up to the money flows of sponsors and subsidies.

3.4.4 Impact

The societal impacts of the production network of the Amalyashi Festival are co-constructed through the funding, subsidies and help that they received. In other words, organisations and institutions recognised a potential societal impact, and this was why those actors became involved.

A representative of VSB foundation clearly spoke to how Amalyashi intersects the societal domains:

[Within VSB foundation] we have the domains Art & Culture and Human & Society and both of them can finance projects. We also look at the artistic quality but we focus primarily on the societal urgency. Amalyashi Festival touched upon both, which is often a good sign. We call those 'intersect projects' and those are more likely to receive a donation. The idea, also departing from a more intersectional approach, is to become more fluid in the assessment of these type of projects.

Economic impact

The economic impact of the Amalyashi Festival is negligible at first sight. It is clearly a new festival. Naturally, it is not easy to organise a festival from scratch, especially one that is directed towards an

audience that is generally difficult to involve and reach. Organiser Tommy Sharif strived to realise the festival regardless and therefore consulted various venues located in and around the city of Leiden to host the performances. The choice to spatially spread out the festival was grounded in the idea to involve people living in the surrounding areas.

It is a small-scale festival in every respect: from publicity to number of visitors to revenue to cultural yields. However, that is what makes this case so interesting. The effort and hard work required in every stage of the production is telling of the intrinsic motivation behind the festival – a dream come true for Tommy Sharif.

Social impact

The social impact of such a small-scale, local festival is obviously rather modest. Still, as a grass-roots initiative by recent migrants to the Netherlands, it empowers the organisers, performers and audience – categories of actors which strongly overlap. It helps them to find and navigate their way in Dutch society by dealing with grant-giving institutions, such as the VSB and the municipality, as well as by finding venues for the performances. Such a small-scale festival, accordingly, also generates social capital – both in terms of closer ties between the organisers, performers and members of the audience and in terms of ties between the organisers and representatives of the public sector and NGOs. This social capital may help create a basis for a recurring event. Many festivals start small, and some of them grow into much larger events. The Amalyashi Festival took place in October 2021 in between COVID-19 lockdowns. This timing, of course, has not helped to move forward the concept of the festival.

Cultural impact

The cultural impact of the festival is very much in line with its small social impact. The festival, though, gives voice to migrants who would have a difficulty in making themselves heard in other ways. The storytelling enables recent migrants from different countries to share experiences and to reflect on their lives. The small-scale character also means there are low barriers to participate. One small-scale festival may have a limited (though still valuable) cultural impact, but a number of such small-scale festivals based on bottom-up initiatives might contribute to a significantly richer and more diverse cultural environment. The skills and the knowledge accumulated in organising the Amalyashi Festival could, when disseminated, help to stimulate other such initiatives.

Bringing together different stories and different backgrounds was the mission of the Amalyashi Festival. With a festival that focuses mainly on storytelling as mode of entertainment, it opens up a space for creativity. Telling stories is one of the oldest forms of entertainment in the world, and Amalyashi brands the storytelling exercise as effectuating a direct impact.

Case 4: Varna Summer Festival²

Source: Festivallinks.eu

Varna Summer International Theatre Festival is the most prestigious forum for theatre in Bulgaria. It was established in 1993 as an initiative to actively promote the public importance of the performing arts after the changes in 1989. The festival usually takes place June 1–11 at the premises of the Varna Drama Theatre. In 2004, after the establishment of the Via Fest Foundation, the management of the festival became more professional and expanded its scope and importance.

² Acknowledgement: Nikolay Yordanov - Executive Director of the Via Fest Foundation; Vera Stoykova - Director of the Varna Puppet Theatre; Desislava Georgieva - Head of the Festivals and Projects Department at the Culture and Spiritual Development Directorate of the Varna Municipality; Ina Bozhidarova - Chief Expert at the Performing Arts and Arts Education Directorate of the Ministry of Culture; Asen Terziev - Member of the Board of Trustees of the Via Fest Foundation; Ilko Ganev - expert in media relations, marketing and advertising at the Via Fest Foundation; Daniela Dimova - Director of the Theatre and Music Production Centre - Varna; Kalina Wagenstein - Director of the Art Office Foundation; Venelin Shurelov - artist responsible for the graphic vision of the festival; Anna Alexandrova - organizer of the festival logistics; Kosta Bazitov - deputy director of the Art Office Foundation. Krassi Tancheva - Project Manager at the British Council - Sofia.

The case study 'Varna Summer International Theatre Festival' corresponds to the typology of a major international festival in the performing arts – in this case, a theatre festival. The choice of this case study allows showing the specificity of a geographic location – Eastern Europe, Bulgaria, Varna. Typical for this location is the importance of public funding (both at municipal and national level) for carrying out festivals.

After World War I, large, sustainable artistic forums were established in Europe, such as the Salzburg Festival in 1920. A few years later, in 1926, the Summer Music Festivities was founded in Varna. The Varna Summer International Theatre Festival successfully continues the nearly 100-year festival tradition in Bulgaria. Founded in 1993, the festival is the most prestigious and largest forum for theatre in Bulgaria since 1989.

The performing arts market in Bulgaria has undergone serious transformations since 1989. For a long time, the only forms of ownership and organisation in the theatre were state and municipal theatres, and it was as early as the 1990s when the first private theatre companies began to appear. Today, there is a wide variety of state, municipal and private theatre organisations in the performing arts sector. The role of state support – by the means of public subsidies, distributed for projects - remains decisive for their existence. Therefore, in Bulgarian economic literature, the public subsidies-based market is referred to as quasi-market (Tomova, 2002) – e.g. an incomplete market. This context predetermines the characteristics of performing arts festivals and theatre, in particular. Today, different national theatre organisations participate (among others) in the Varna Summer International Theatre Festival with their selected productions.

The Varna Theatre Forum reflects ongoing processes of transformation. Initially, the festival was an initiative of the civic Bulgarian Theatre Association. The association unites most of the publicly funded state and municipal drama theatres. After 2014, the 'Via Fest' Foundation was created for this purpose to manage and organise the festival. The festival is held every year in the month of June in Varna, the third largest city in Bulgaria, located on the Black Sea coast, also known as the 'sea capital of Bulgaria'. From the beginning, the festival selection have included private theatre companies for the festival programme. After 1995, the festival started to involve international productions. The festival Board of Trustees Nikolay Yordanov and Asen Terziev share:

During the first three or four years the event was held as a national festival, and later it acquired international dimensions. However, as the relationship became extremely complex, with the advent of more and more market relations in the sector, we decided that it was not normal for theatre directors to choose the person who would sign contracts with them. And in reality, the directors' association today is almost non-functional, because most of them, although they are municipal or state or private theatres, have increasingly divergent interests. The competition and all this led to the formation in 2004 of a new structure called the Via Fest Foundation - Varna Summer International Theatre Festival. (Interview 1)

Figure 7. Board of Trustees of the foundation Viafest (from left to right, Assan Terziev, Tzvetana Maneva, Nikolay Vordanov)

In its 30 editions so far, the festival has held nearly 1000 events – theatre performances, seminars, creative workshops, conferences, concerts and screenings of plays. A total of 197 international

productions and co-productions from 40 countries have been realized (Interview 5). In 2020, COVID-19 forced the organizers to hold the festival in digital format, with streaming of specially selected performances. Long before that, in 2011, the British Council’s National Live Theatre project was included in the festival programme with screenings of performances.

The project was presented to the British Council by the National Theatre with the idea of promoting performing arts in an innovative way to reach wider audiences. As the interviewee from the British Council - Bulgaria shared: *“The British Council then initiated European projects in different countries, locally with its partners. So, the British Council – Bulgaria contacted the Varna Summer International Festival, and we presented this project”* (Interview 12). These two occasions shatter the notion of classical display and distribution of theatrical products. We see the emergence of digital elements in the value chain. This digitalisation in the distribution and display phases provides evidence of a new business model entering the festival network.

The case study interviews covered 12 actors in the festival’s production network, representing relatively balanced scope of roles and responsibilities across the value chain. They include four representatives of the Via Fest Foundation (the organisation responsible for the festival), two representatives the Varna municipality in management positions, one expert in the Ministry of Culture, two directors of host theatres, one representative of a partner NGO, one representative of a foreign cultural institute in Bulgaria (a traditional partner of the festival), as well as one collaborator involved in the festival programme implementation. The production network of the Varna Summer International Theatre Festival has clearly defined phases, but they are uneven in terms of duration and intensity.

Key features

Table 17. Key characteristics of the Varna Summer Festival

Founded	1993
Location	Varna
First edition in Varna	1993
Latest edition in Varna	2022
Frequency of occurrence	Every year
Month	June
Usual duration	11 to 12 days
Type	Theater
Regulations	Representative
Audience	For all
Content	Experimental
Range	International
Organizer	Non-profit organization
Type of participants	Professionals
Places	Prevaillingly indoors
Access	Paid/digital edition – free access

3.4.1 Phases, actors and locations

This case study synthesizes a mix of issues, possible solutions and perspectives for sustainable policies. The Via Fest Foundation is the leading organisation in the production network of the festival. The foundation was established in 2004, initially as a professional unit to support the festival’s founder, the Bulgarian Theatre Association. Subsequently, it gradually concentrated on becoming the organizer and main driver of the event. The foundation, thanks to its sustainable network of actors, has developed a well-organised expert capacity to participate in consultations, debates and initiatives for the drafting of European directives, conventions, statistical standards, funding programmes, changes in national legislation, sub-regulatory documents and drafting of strategic documents for the development of the sector.

Actors

The Ministry of Culture, as a key partner of the Varna Summer International Theatre Festival, implements policies at a national and local level as the supreme central executive body with the right

of legislative initiative. As a member of the EU Council of Ministers of Culture, it also participates in the process of drafting European directives, regulations and standards for the cultural sector. The ministry has the power to formulate and implement the key principles and foundations of the national cultural policy. It creates the necessary regulatory and administrative environment in which all players in the sector operate, guaranteeing its efficiency and progress. Together with local government institutions, the Ministry of Culture is directly involved in the development of infrastructure and strategy in performing arts.

Varna Municipality and Sofia Municipality, as bodies of local self-government, adapt the general legal and regulatory frameworks for the specific needs of their cities and regions. Through their participation in the National Association of Municipalities in the Republic of Bulgaria and the Committee of the Regions in the EU, they interact, albeit indirectly, with festivals as forums for maintaining local identity.

National and international festivals (more specifically, from the region of Southeast Europe), participate in the creation phase of the International Theatre Festival 'Varna Summer' with their programs and ideas. Their joint membership in various national and international branch associations is the basis for various initiatives to support the sector, both at the European, national and local level. The foreign cultural institutes and cultural centres in Bulgaria participate in the creation and dissemination phase of the festival. Thus, they promote their national cultural contents in the host country more effectively. On the other hand, their collaboration with Varna Summer International Theatre Festival contributes to their awareness of the key artistic trends at the national and international level. The acquired experiences increase the capacity for closer European collaboration and integration through the performing arts, creating a sort of 'European added value'. Foreign cultural institutes have important roles in their countries' cultural and foreign policies.

Various local cultural institutions – the Theatre and Music Production Centre, the Varna Puppet Theatre and the Sofia Municipal Theatre – are actively involved in the phases of creation (with consultancy), production (with their own performances in the festival programme), distribution (through their marketing and advertising units) and display (with venues, equipment and technical teams). Their partnership with the Varna Summer International Theatre Festival influences cultural policies at both a local and national level for better regulation of the sector and for the implementation of prominent local cultural activities.

Art Office Foundation is involved in the creation, presentation and exhibition phases. The established capacity for monitoring and international cooperation contributes to cultural and social activities as well as to policies for promotion and professional development of authors, playwrights, directors, actors, choreographers, musicians, visual artists, managers and PR experts.

Professional schools, universities, research and training programmes, and curricula in arts and culture provide the most important resources for the festival – namely, the creative human capital that fuels

the creation, production and archiving phases. There is an extensive network of arts schools that educate children from the age of 6 years to a PhD degree. The active involvement of teachers, pupils, students and PhD students in the various activities of Varna Summer International Theatre Festival support their professional competences and skills in a real working environment. It is important that the professional biography of most of the current festival team members begins with internships and training during earlier festival editions.

Sectoral organisations in culture and the arts include trade unions and employers' associations as well as collective copyright management bodies. They are directly involved in the production and exhibition phases of the festival programme by sharing established expert capacity with the festival team; establishing international contacts; and providing training facilities, offices and other forms of cooperation. Their involvement in a European and national context is particularly necessary and relevant to ensure the creation of good regulations, guaranteeing remuneration and copyright regulation in the context of the penetration of digital content sharing platforms.

Participation of schools and universities ensures strong social outcome of the festival during the display phase. Part of the audience of the festival are art and literature teachers. Together with their students, they often attend relevant festival events and organise meetings with participants in the programme. This contributes to creating an interested and competent audience.

The public media, such as the Bulgarian National Television, the National Radio and the Bulgarian Telegraph Agency, as well as the private media, contribute significantly to the distribution and archiving phase. They operate in accordance with European, national and local regulations to ensure access to information content, to promote an aesthetic education and to ensure media pluralism.

Museums, art galleries, libraries and archives participate in the display phase, as they become venues for numerous festival events and also play a role in the archiving phase.

Community cultural centres (*chitalishta*), as local cultural associations with a specific status in Bulgaria, are involved in the formation of audiences for all kinds of arts and engagement in the display phase. As organizers of amateur performing arts and practices, often using their own venue, they are involved in the creation and production phases. The *chitalishta* network comprises several thousand centres across the country; thus, it has leverage for influencing national policies in developing specific indicators and equitable standards for assessing the impact of the performing arts.

Tourism plays a role in the Varna Summer International Theatre Festival, predominantly in the creation, distribution and exhibition phases. Its influence at the national level is associated with the regulation of policies by the Ministry of Tourism and the Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works, aimed at creating an appropriate infrastructure to support new cultural tourism products and to promote Bulgaria as an attractive cultural tourism destination.

Phases

The creation phase is the longest in duration, around eight months, with relatively low intensity. The final result and, therefore, value crystallises in the festival programme. In its content, the festival programme is a unique creative product, a peculiar ensemble of personal participation, performances, seminars, conferences and debates. The production phase is characterised by a relatively shorter duration of 2–3 months and a higher intensity of the proceedings. The end result of its implementation is the programme content in terms of structure, thematic focus and dates of delivery. The third and fourth phases, dissemination and display, are characterised by the shortest implementation period and the highest intensity of delivery. They take about a month to implement and include media services and the use of communication channels, the adaptation of infrastructure, the accompanying logistics and the implementation of festival events. The fifth phase, archiving, is characterised by a relatively long implementation period and the lowest degree of intensity. The added value is the metadata and the diverse scientific output.

Figure 8. Case 4: phases of the production network

Creation

The main participants in the creation phase are the Via Fest Foundation, Art Office Foundation, Ministry of Culture and Varna municipality. Other key participants are the foreign cultural institutes in Bulgaria (e.g. the French Cultural Institute, the British Council, Goethe Institute - , selector of Bulgarian theatre production (until 2015), as well as the international theatre festivals in Sibiu, Istanbul, Belgrade, Ljubljana.

In the creation phase, the festival programme takes shape. The festival programme is built as a mosaic of four modules. The 'Bulgarian Selection' module focuses on theatrical developments on the Bulgarian stage and highlights the significant and innovative achievements of the current season. The 'International Programme' presents leading artists and trends in different types of theatre. The 'Parallel Programme' is open to various partnership initiatives, discussions, workshops, theoretical conferences, lectures, book presentations, exhibitions and concerts. In 2008, together with the Art Office, the module 'Showcase' was launched. It selects innovative and mobile Bulgarian productions, aimed both at the public and at specially invited selectors and programmers of international festivals.

The leading organisation, Via Fest Foundation, is involved in the realization of the festival, together with two key funding partners, the Ministry of Culture and Varna Municipality. Among the main co-organisers in the creation of the programme, the Art Office Foundation with its special programme 'Showcase' has an important place (Interview 8). Other partners are also involved in the implementation of individual projects, in the form of cultural centres (e.g. the French Cultural Institute and the British Council) as well as organisations working on projects for the Creative Europe Programme (Royal Concertgebouw Orchestra - Amsterdam) (Interview 3).

From 1993 to 2015, the creation of the official programme selection, which included only performances at Bulgarian theatres, was entrusted to a special programmer by the Board of the Bulgarian Theatre Association. The artistic director and executive director of the association undertook the task of making the programme one of international participation, with accompanying events. Each edition of the festival was accompanied by a special motto, in the creation of which the selector played a major role. After 2014, when the Via Fest Foundation was established, the responsibility for the overall appearance of the programme was assumed by its board of trustees.

The festival content is dominated by the presentation of previously created performances. Because of limited financial opportunities, original productions are rare.

As usual, the preparation of the festival programme goes through the following stages:

- Analysis of proposals for the realization of guest performances (artistic qualities, financial parameters, mobility, technical compatibility, audience interest and the possibility of presentation in Sofia and other places in the country)
- Evaluation and selection of new productions on the Bulgarian stage
- Planning performances for the Showcase module

- Planning side events
- Negotiating funding with key partners.

Asen Terziev, member of the board of trustees of Via Fest explains the programming process:

In terms of the Bulgarian selection, the main criterium is artistic quality. We work with a wide range of professionals with whom we consult titles. The Bulgarian programme has to represent a good artistic achievement, and with regard to the International programme, there are two other criteria. The productions have to connect with the audience's expectation and we are always looking for a balance. We have to work with the audience to develop them and not alienate them from the content of the programme. The whole process of programming the content is a specific kind of game between formed attitudes and provoking curiosity among the audience. (Interview 5)

Like any creative activity, this phase in the production chain generates results with the highest added value. The focus is on ideas, dialogue and communication with partners.

The spatial distribution of the Creation phase is at local, national and European level. There are different cities in Bulgaria and Europe (e.g. Sibiu, Istanbul, Belgrade, Ljubljana, Amsterdam, etc.) where the selectors have watched and selected a theatre production. Selectors are also invited to Varna Summer Festival. In this phase, there are virtual activities, such as online negotiations and correspondence with partners.

Production

Along with the main organizer of the festival, Via Fest Foundation, selected theatre companies from Bulgaria and Europe participate in this phase. Representatives of other organisations creating side events are also involved.

In the production phase, the selected programme content is structured. The production of the programme includes six elements:

- 1) original productions created by the organisers;
- 2) selected Bulgarian theatre production and co-productions with foreign partner;
- 3) international selection of productions;
- 4) performances by host theatres in Varna city;
- 5) Showcase programme for theatre exchange;
- 6) accompanying programme of seminars, conferences and round tables with the participation of researchers and other festival programmers and organisers.

Although after 2015 the festival programme had no overarching motto, the production phase of the programme is shaped around key topics and messages, which shape the overall festival content and specific accents in the programme (Interview 9).

Typically, the production phase goes through the following stages:

- Creation of an image and graphic vision of the publication based on the adopted graphic concept of the festival and its respective replicas for the needs of the different information, communication and advertising channels;
- Negotiating programme participation and partnerships;
- Programming in detail the selected events in the main programme as well as the accompanying programme;
- Negotiation of stages and technical support for the events;
- Ensuring the necessary human, financial and material resources.

The production phase is characterised by a relatively higher weight of standardised services in the areas of legal, financial and technical planning. At the same time, activities with creative participation and high added value, such as graphic design and various activities to adapt the universal messages and ideas in the festival programme to the specific local context, are also implemented. The production of original theatre works also takes place in this phase.

Image 1. Module „Showcase’ meeting, Varna 2019

Source: *Via Fest*

The geographical location of this phase is a reflection of the location of the already selected and invited participants – namely, Varna, Sofia and other cities in Bulgaria as well as European cities whose theatres present their product.

Distribution

The main actors in this phase are the experts in the organisation responsible for the festival (Via Fest). They are involved in media content creation, public relations, marketing and advertising. The contractors are printing houses, public media (Bulgarian National Television, Bulgarian National Radio, Bulgarian Telegraph Agency) and private TV and radio stations, internet publications, blogs and so on. Dissemination is carried out by implementing information, communication, advertising and marketing activities. The aim is to engage audiences using conventional and digital channels. These include press releases, annotations, posters, leaflets, catalogues, newsletters, banners and social media posts. In the distribution phase, all products and services of the festival are promoted. In this phase, contracts can still be signed with those spaces where the show will take place – in Varna. The location of this phase is focused more in Sofia and less in Varna.

Figure 9. Case 4: tasks and phases of the production network of the Varna Summer Festival

Exhibition

The main participant in this phase are the host theatres that offer venues for the festival programme: the Dramatic Theatre ‘Stoyan Bachvarov’, the Puppet Theatre (in Varna) and others. Exhibition of the festival content is ensured also through the network of cinema theatres, through project collaborations (e.g. NT Live and Met Live) that involve cinema networks in shopping malls across Bulgaria, the House of Cinema (Sofia), Cinema City Cultural Centre (Sofia), and Varna Summer International Music Festival (through the Intermezzo project).

Image 2. National Theatre Live - Screening, Varna 2012

Source: Via Fest

The core festival production is presented in various venues across the city: from traditional theatre venues (Varna Dramatic Theatre and the affiliated Puppet Theatre), the Festival and Congress Centre Varna, to non-traditional spaces, such as the City Art Gallery, the English Courtyard of the Regional History Museum, the Roman Baths, public squares and other open urban spaces. The organisations that provide venues for the festival programme are major partners and specialised suppliers to the festival. They are entitled to present their production at the festival. Some of them assume more than one role for the festival. For example, the Drama Theatre 'Stoyan Bachvarov' in Varna is a partner, a specialized provider (its stage is used) and a creator of performing arts production for the festival (a theatre play to be presented within the festival programme).

Since 2007, in cooperation with the Sofia municipality, Via Fest hosts a spin-off of a Sofia-based festival called 'World Theatre in Sofia'. Its program has expanded ever since, forming a specific profile by programming performances, workshops and conferences. Since 2011, in partnership with the British Council in Bulgaria, there have been live broadcasts of performances of the Royal National Theatre in London (NT Live) in movie theatres. In Varna, such programmes take place in partnership with key cinema venues, such as the Festival and Congress Centre in Varna and the multiplexes in shopping malls. In Sofia, they are in partnership with the House of Cinema and the Cultural Centre Cinema City. In 2014-2019, the America for Bulgaria Foundation implemented the Metropolitan Opera Live from New York (Met Live) project, demonstrating the unexpected possibilities of a new performing arts

experience through the hybrid of opera, film and television. Screenings took place in a few large Bulgarian cities, including Varna, in the framework of the International Theatre Festival and the Varna Summer International Music Festival. In recent years, the Varna Summer International Theatre Festival joined forces with the Varna Summer International Music Festival to promote concerts and dance performances through the joint project Intermezzo.

The rich accompanying programme deserves special attention. It encompasses a variety of activities engaged in the overall shape of the functioning of theatre art today – namely, the creation and promotion of new theatre texts, the sharing of valuable experience related to the production process, the involvement of young artists, conferences, discussions of performances, debates and so on.

In the context of COVID 19, capacity has been created to carry out activities in a fully online format by streaming specially prepared and subtitled recordings of performances prepared by the organisers.

The dissemination and exhibition phases are characterised by relatively the highest weight in the use of standardised services related to the overall logistics of events. Creative activities retain their territory mainly in the adaptation of non-traditional spaces for theatrical performances as well as the numerous side events related to creative workshops, debate and discussion of contemporary theatre issues.

Of course, the exhibition also has a strong creative character because in this phase, the theatrical performance itself happens in front of an audience.

This phase takes place locally and nationally. It occurs mainly in the city of Varna, but different projects extend to Sofia, Plovdiv, Ruse and all the larger cities of Bulgaria, which have cinemas in the malls. (The festival as distributor becomes part of the global networks of the Metropolitan Opera and National Theatre in London).

Archiving

The archiving phase has a number of main participants. First are the organizers from the Via Fest Foundation specialize in culture publications. Second are Homo Ludens, lecturers and students mainly from the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, the Institute for the Study of Arts, the National Academy of Theatre and Film Arts 'Krastyo Sarafov' in Sofia, the National Academy of Arts 'Nikolai Pavlovich' in Sofia and the New Bulgarian University in Sofia. They participate by publishing analyses, assessments, critiques and briefs about the festival.

The archiving phase is carried out by registering and systematizing metadata on the organizers' own website and blog <http://Via.Fest.org/>, including participants, events, dates, venues and graphic design of the individual editions. Relevant for this phase is the critical reflection on the festival content

presented in conference proceedings, analyses in specialized cultural publications, monographs, studies and scientific conference papers.

The archiving locations are mainly concentrated in Sofia, where the main information about the events is stored in analogue and digital form.

Image 3. Pippo del Bono Performance, *Orchidee*, Varna 2014

Source: *Via Fest*

We can assume that the festival creates, adds or shares value through various activities, services and products. These activities take place in different phases:

- 1) the festival programming takes place at the creation phase;
- 2) the Bulgarian productions created produced for the festival (Via Fest is the producer) happen across the phases of creation, production and exhibition;
- 3) the market for Bulgarian drama productions in the 'Showcase' module spans across creation, distribution and exhibition phases;
- 4) the products and services created in partnership ('Parallel Programme'), including discussions, workshops, theoretical conferences, lectures, book presentations, exhibitions and concerts, happen at distribution and exhibition phases;
- 5) products and services created in partnership with the festival, which add value in the distribution and exhibition phases, such as the projects *Intermezzo*, *Met Live* and *NT Live*.

Figure 10. Case 4: Varna Summer International Theater Festival network scheme

3.4.2 Dynamics – phases, actors, locations

The Varna Summer International Theatre Festival is expanding and enriching its content. The idea and creativity phase was initially focused on presenting new and current theatre productions by various Bulgarian producers. With the passing of time, the festival has engaged in increasingly diverse areas of activity: the festival organisers’ original productions, the presentation and discussion of new theatre texts, the integration of new aesthetic ideas and theatrical techniques, an exchange through the Showcase programme, and the creation of interdisciplinary content between theatre, music and dance. This diversity has led to the involvement of new participants, including partners from abroad, authors, scenographers, costume designers, choreographers, musicians, dancers, theatre managers and selectors.

In the production phase, after the establishment of the festival as the most prestigious theatrical forum in Bulgaria, the practice of involving different selectors in the composition of the program content was dropped. This is a logical consequence, the result of the established in-house capacity of the organisation responsible for the festival. The stated motto for each year has also been dropped. After the initial intention of making the festival a national event, international participation has become increasingly important. Thus, the programme content opened up for an active international exchange that was missing in the Bulgarian theatre scene. Dropping the previous motto allowed the

festival to open up to much more diverse themes in each edition, without losing the identity and appeal of each individual programme on its own.

The dissemination phase was enriched with new information channels, successfully balancing traditional means of information dissemination, advertising and marketing. New entrants include internet publications, bloggers and providers.

The exhibition phase underwent the most visible transformations and developments. This dynamic reflects the expanding partner network and new communication opportunities. The first important aspect of these is the usage of new non-conventional performance spaces in Varna: public squares and archaeological sites. The second direction of development is the spin-off festival of World Theatre in Sofia, which promotes some of the most interesting international productions. The third direction of expansion and renewal is through the projects NT Live and Met Live, in the case of which the distribution and exchange phases are intertwined. The new actors in the network that stand out are the Sofia municipality, the America for Bulgaria Foundation, veues in Sofia (Sofia Municipal Theatre) and cinema theatres in malls of larger cities.

Influence of Covid-19

The new pandemic conditions made it difficult to build on the capacity already established. The festival included programming content and distribution of productions through online broadcasts and screenings. These new activities involved a professional subtitler, translators, streaming services, cinema theatres, and technical and administrative teams from the Cinema City Mall in Sofia, the Festival and Congress Centre in Varna and the Cinema House in Sofia. The organizers also used PR services, specifically for this digital edition, as well as many media partnerships.

3.4.3 Relationships between actors

The network associated with the Varna Summer International Theatre Festival was developed to satisfy the urgent need of the Bulgarian theatre scene for dedicated fora to present, discuss and analyse contemporary theatre. Before 1989, the functions of such a forum were carried out by national theatre reviews, held every five years. After the socio-economic changes of 1989, these reviews were discontinued. Varna Summer Theatre Festival was the first major international theatre event of that scale in Bulgaria. It was founded in 1992 by the directors of public theatres (state and municipal), who united to set up the Bulgarian Theatre Association. Their main goal was to create a theatre festival in Varna for showcasing the contemporary productions of Bulgarian theatre companies. The festival received support from the Varna Municipality, the Ministry of Culture and the Drama Theatre 'Stoyan Bachvarov' in Varna. The Bulgarian Army Theatre in Sofia plays an important role in the festival as well. The festival's first edition was in 1993.

Today, the organiser's legal entity, Via Fest Foundation, carries out the internal relations based on aesthetic and creative guidelines. The main programming, coordination of events, selection and creative decisions are carried out by three people: Asen Terziev, theatre critic and researcher (lecturer at the National Academy of Theatre and Film, Sofia), and Tsvetana Maneva, a renowned actress and lecturer who has been actively involved in the festival and who was originally its artistic director. Previously, the festival's selection was done by Nikolay Yordanov (Interview 1).

The festival has relied on its long-standing strategic partnerships and relationship with public institutions to ensure its sustainability over the years. Stable strategic support at local (Varna Municipality) and national (Ministry of Culture) levels has enabled the organisers to focus on the substantive aspects of programme selection. With each subsequent edition, the Varna Theatre Festival has increased its value and has established itself as a widely acknowledged platform of the Bulgarian theatre and performing arts.

The internal relations between the festival and its clients – namely, Bulgarian theatres and theatre companies – are based on solidarity and on the common will to defend their right to exist and create. This relationship originated in the early 1990s, when the very existence of subsidised arts in Bulgaria was in doubt. Intense debates about the public funding of culture were common, in the context of the profound economic and social transition from a socialist to a market economy. Some radical neoliberal politicians called for a drastic reduction of the extensive network of public cultural institutes and appealed that most of them should function on market principles. Artistic creators were accused of being the pawns of the previous totalitarian government, engaged in propaganda functions.

In response to the neoliberal critics, the festival's organizers framed their work as both a showcase of artistic achievement and as a marketplace of ideas for young performing artists.

The 'marketplace' function of the festival is provided by the Art Office Foundation (a professional consultancy firm in arts management and programming). It developed a permanent module in the festival programme – the Showcase. The programme also involves various arts universities and programmes: NATFA 'Krastyo Sarafov', New Bulgarian University and the National Academy of Visual Arts 'Nikolay Pavlovich'. Kalina Wagenstein, Art Office Foundation explains the 'Showcase' programme:

The idea for the [Showcase] programme was to show a production that is not too local and could be physically transported. These are basic criteria for the programme. We avoid a lot of text, so that people can watch it. Then the programmers from Varna Summer have the last word. We are also involved in the selection of the projects. (Interview 8).

Common service providers support all phases of the festival. This includes offices, logistics, communications, marketing and advertising, and software.

Dedicated service providers are predominant in the set-up phase. These include selected participants in the festival programme who have delegated rights in creative authority. The participants in the selected programme should not be perceived as a classical type of business service. They are in fact contributors or co-creators of symbolic and social capital; they build the festival's status as the major performing arts event in Bulgaria, also reflecting international trends. Each selected theatrical performance and each participant contribute to the co-creation of the artistic and social value over time.

In the production phase, the specialised suppliers are concentrated on the creation of innovative theatrical productions. Although original productions and co-productions are rare for this festival, they do occur and are usually based on novel playwriting or involve acclaimed contemporary theatre directors. Nikolay Yordanov explains what leads their choice of theatrical and hybrid productions in building the festival programme:

We have created several shows that I am proud of and they have received great international acclaim. For example, Galin Stoev's 'Archaeology of Dreaming', based on Ivan Vyrypaev, who later became a world known playwright. We staged for the first time as own production the 'Psychosis' by Sarah Kane, directed by Desislava Shpatova, which then has got the opportunity to be performed on the stage of Sfumato Theatre (Sofia) for a dozen performances and had two invitations abroad. This year, despite the difficult situation, we produced a show that is a hybrid between theatre and music with the renowned director Yavor Gardev and the composer Petar Dundakov. We co-produced some performances and a few other productions, that were made possible by the subsidy and distribution of performances that could come to Varna; later they were programmed by the theatres programmed across country. (Interview 1, Nikolay Yordanov)

The production process involves a creative team involving a number of distinct players: author, director, set designer, costume designer, choreographer and composer. The process also involves workshops for the production of costumes, set design, props and other accessories, technical support, multimedia and so on. The commissioning of production is carried out by the organizers of the Via Fest Foundation, whereas the creative crew has full aesthetic freedom to develop the creative product. The production realization within the festival framework is different than the predominant typologies of production networks of publicly funded repertory theatres in Bulgaria. In the case of festival-produced products, the size of which they can more directly influence, the artists involved do not receive monthly salaries. Instead, they receive fees for the time involved in the creation and production, In this sense, they have no responsibility to ensure more performances and audiences for their production.

The production value builds on the free sharing of ideas, the testing of new forms of artistic expression, and the mastering of unconventional spaces for art. The finished theatrical production is

subject to negotiation between the organisers and the host venues, distributors and other festivals (without specific requirement to generate profit). In this case, the aim is to affirm the image of the festival as a space for experimentation and as a platform for new art forms.

Structuring the programme content is key in the production phase. This phase includes artistic highlights, the choice of works and venues and the planning of side events where trends in contemporary theatre are debated. A variety of partners are involved in this process, with a wide degree of autonomy – artists, theatre critics, universities and specialist publications.

The local state cultural institutes – the Drama Theatre ‘Stoyan Bachvarov’ (Varna) and the Puppet Theatre (Varna) – play a key role in the display phase by providing their stage spaces and teams. They participate in the programme with their own productions for which they are entitled to the box office revenues. Their own technical teams are involved in the festival production, for which the tech crews receive additional remuneration on top of their monthly wages.

Hence, from the point of view of the GPN approach, the local cultural institutes’ involvement is twofold – adding value through their participation and capturing value through the privileged position of actively communicating within the network and enriching their own production. Vera Stoykova, Director of the State Puppet Theatre – Varna, explains the importance of their collaboration with the festival for their theatre:

The festival programme always includes not only the participation of our productions, but also other projects. Each year one of our performances is selected to be part of the main programme. In some years Varna Drama Theatre also shows a second performance. We have also participated with a chamber opera production. We are dreaming of a co-production with an internationally renowned director to work with the theatre company and realize a co-production. The stages provided by us are compensated by the festival organizers as overheads - electricity, telephone communications not only during the festival, but also about three weeks before its start.

Our partnership with Varna Summer is important for new contacts, because many people come to the theatre for the first time. Our care for everything that happens here fascinates them and collaborative attitude developed. A team from the theatre is working for the festival. Deputy Director Annie Alexandrova handles the check-in of festival participants and guests. Krassimira Hristova, the curator of the Museum who speaks three languages, is also part of the organizing team during the Varna Summer. The technicians actively cooperate. Certainly we all help in whatever way we can, such as with actors reading a text for a performance, etc. [...] We take part in the selection of Varna Summer with judgements related to incoming proposals for a guest puppet show or to recommend our own title to become part of the programme. (Interview 2, Vera Stoykova)

The network in the exchange phase includes other local cultural venues, such as the Festival and Congress Centre in Varna – a popular venue for concerts, performances, film screenings, exhibitions and conferences (branch of the National Palace of Culture in Sofia, state commercial company that also receives funding by the Ministry of Culture). The Regional History Museum in Varna and the City Art Gallery are institutes financed by a mixed state and a municipal subsidies. They rent-out spaces for various festival events, including archaeological sites, such as the Roman Baths.

The distribution phase delegates a great deal of power to local cultural institutes and in particular their advertising and marketing units. This is done through the use of established advertising and marketing channels to attract audiences. In the short term, local cultural institutes lose audiences and revenue by making their stages available for the festival, but they find unconventional solutions to continue their activities even during the festival. Vera Stoykova explains the value of non-conventional spaces:

During the festival, we promote outdoor formats or use non-conventional spaces, which immediately attracts audiences' interest. We take our activities even to the big shopping malls. For many years we had a very good relationship, they also became part of the event - it was like they were opening a second stage. (Interview 2)

In the long run, local cultural institutes rely on enriched opportunities to sustainably nurture local audiences' curiosity about new theatrical forms and performing arts. At the same time, new forms of promotion through social networks, despite their advantages, contain serious challenges that organisers need to take into account. Ilko Ganev, Media relations at Via Fest clarifies:

Advertising collides with the rules of the community, and since ads are read by robots, if you use substandard advertising, you are in danger of falling into the group of those who break the accepted rules. Thus the need for uniformity of meaning, the rejection of metaphors and any figurative or symbolic representation of content. This unification of communication comes in handy for people who are more narrow-minded, lacking depth. (Interview 6)

This is one of the reasons why organisers supporting the promotion of performances continue to rely on the traditional means of connecting with audiences. Daniela Dimova (Varna Theatre and Music Production Centre) emphasises:

The simplest and most direct contact is the personal meeting with the viewer. The salon inspector knows most of our spectators personally. I (director of the theatre), on the other hand, at most of the performances and premieres personally go out in front of the hall and meet the audience before the beginning. They are encouraged by this and very often share their impressions during the intermission and even make recommendations for including a particular title in the repertoire. (Interview 7)

Archiving as an activity is centralized by the organizers of Via Fest Foundation. Limitations in its application stem from the copyright regulation. Much of the festival production is accompanied by restrictions on video and photo capture of performances. Yordanov and Ganev share how the organisers keep and display the full documentation of the festival programmes and history. Due to the lack of physical space, they keep only digital archives.

We maintain collections in digital form only. We (the Via Fest organizers' foundation) have a very small space that is rented, and we practically can't afford to maintain a room in which to keep any relics/archive. But in return, the digital space gives us endless possibilities and we take very seriously our website, which we maintain with scientific precision so that events that have happened can be reconstructed on it. (Interview 1)

For the archiving, especially for the advertisement from this year, I've started to systematize on a large external disk all video ads, images etc. and store them by types and dates (Interview 6)

The results of the archiving are used, disseminated and objectified with the help of the research community engaged in the study of processes in contemporary theatre. This community includes the Institute for Arts Research at the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, the National Art Academy 'Nikolay Pavlovich' and the New Bulgarian University. They build on the value created by the organizers.

Based on the analysis, we assumed that there are no substantial barriers to entering the market of performing arts festivals in Bulgaria but that there are barriers for a festival organisation to survive in this market (i.e. to be sustainable over time). The role of public funding is decisive for a festival of this scope and scale in Bulgaria –no large festival can sustain itself on only ticket sales. This is a small, subsidised market, which is a limitation in itself. The established players have already gained a market advantage in the performing arts market; they receive public funding as part of the so-called annual cultural calendars of the city municipalities. In addition to already receiving public funding, these players have built a brand and a name that give them competitive advantages; thus, there are barriers to the entry of new festivals on the market.

We conclude that the Varna Festival is a complete ecosystem, with diverse programme elements (modules). This allows value to be created by all its creative partners.

The programmes include, for instance, specialized workshops for young playwrights to read, create and develop texts under the supervision of famous playwrights. These workshops enable new dramaturgical ideas, create opportunities for talent development and add educational value to the festival network. Educational value is also created by the volunteers who are students majoring in theatre. The daily festival newsletter, for example, is written by students in their third or fourth year of theatre studies.

Image 4. Performance *Hakanai*, Varna 2018

Source: *Via Fest*

The Showcase module promotes productions by young artists who may be invited to perform abroad. This unique market of authors and productions focuses on innovative creative ideas and explorations. Besides the uncontested cultural and educational value for the audience, the festival is an important meeting place for a large number of Bulgarian theatre directors, who watch new Bulgarian and international stage productions. The annual conference is a place for discussing cultural policy issues as well as professional matters in contemporary theatre aesthetics, all of which impact the entire theatre field and its systems in Bulgaria.

Socio-cultural embeddedness

Festivals, as peculiar 'global players' in the contemporary cultural environment, have contradictory tendencies. On the one hand, they appear as a kind of carrier of supranational civilizational processes; they remove social, racial, political and economic prejudices. On the other hand, festivals threaten to deprive themselves of a healthy dose of responsibility towards the place where they are held.

The overall programming and management of the Varna Summer International Theatre Festival is concentrated in Sofia. The organizing team combines its commitments with creative, teaching and research activities. In reality, they stay in Varna no more than a month every a year. Although the programme is created in Sofia, its value is generated and distributed in the host city, Varna. A relatively

small part of it returns to Sofia – more as a response to the theatrical Varna Summer through the World Theatre in Sofia programme, where certain theatre productions are distributed and shown. This local activity has financial support from the Sofia city council.

The way Varna Summer is organized is similar to some other European festivals. For example, the iconic Avignon Theatre Festival in France has its main programming organisation in Paris, where most of the theatre professionals are concentrated. The responsibilities for organising a festival of this scale are carried out by an individual organisation dealing with Avignon, by the central funding of culture (Ministry of Culture and Communications of France) and by the local level (i.e. the city council). In this sense, Varna Summer follows one of the business models that is traditional for major international stage festivals in Europe. Its core team consists of theatre professionals with a wealth of experience and at the same time actively seeks to connect with both local audiences and local theatres. As Assen Terziev explains, the festival concept and business model reflect two aspects.

On the one hand, the programme should be thought of with the idea of the specific characteristics of the local audience and its horizon of expectations. The second direction is to work very actively with all the local partners and host venues. (Interview 5)

The motivation of the organizers is related to the presentation of the best of the Bulgarian theatre scene, opening to the world and generating opportunities for more active exchange. The motivation of the key funding partners of the festival – the Ministry of Culture, the Municipality of Varna, and later the Municipality of Sofia – is driven by the idea of promoting flagship events in the national and local cultural calendar. The motivation of the hosts (who provide the local infrastructure, such as stages, venues and technical teams, and who have the opportunity to show their own productions at the festival) is driven by the opportunity to become involved in new artistic trends, active learning, international networks and possibilities for future creative projects.

3.4.4 Positioning with the typology matrix

In terms of the adopted typology, the Varna Summer International Theatre Festival unfolds in its different phases with a variable concentration of responsibilities and activities. The main organizer of the initiative undergoes a significant transformation. Initially established as an association of theatre directors, the organisational structure of the festival has transformed into a foundation concentrated in a narrower circle of professionals. The interests of professional associations are no longer as important, as the demands of specific competencies for the realization of an event that reflects the achievements and trends in theatre.

The creation phase – when the festival programme is shaped – is concentrated in the leader organisation, Via Fest Foundation. Funding from the strategic partners, the Municipality of Varna and

the Ministry of Culture is secured every year by a project proposal submitted by the Via Fest Foundation. Another strategic partner, the Art Office Foundation, contributes its expertise and capacity for engaged communication among the participants from Bulgaria and from abroad. Art Office helps set up a 'bank of ideas' that feeds a special festival programme called 'Showcase'. Via Fest does the final selection for the 'Showcase' programme.

Strategic partnerships are established by the leader organisation with foreign cultural institutes in Bulgaria as well as with festivals in the region of South East Europe. The creation phase unfolds on the basis of concentrated, systematically planned and targeted activities at national and international level (mostly from EU countries).

In the production phase, the responsibilities are decentralised by delegating certain rights to partners, such as the host theatres in Varna, Sofia and occasionally other cities as well as by delegating rights to the Art Office Foundation, the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences and the Art Academies in Sofia. These partners are delegated the autonomy to manage and administrate the predefined programme framework by the leader organisation. Activities are predominantly concentrated at local, regional and national levels.

The distribution phase has many elements in common with the production phase, such as the dynamics of implementation and the allocation of responsibilities. Its specificity is that there is even more autonomy of the partners, which include the Bulgarian public and private media (both electronic and print) as well as foreign managers of theatre companies and festivals, mainly from the EU.

Such decentralisation has naturally led to festival programmes that include broadcasts (via streaming or recording) of performances by the British National Theatre (NT Live), in partnership with the British Council, and by the Metropolitan Opera, in partnership with America for Bulgaria Foundation. Increased distribution capabilities using global communications technologies have made it possible to organize the 2020 festival edition online, during the COVID-19 pandemic.

The display phase is concentrated in local and national boundaries. The leader organisation delegates a wide autonomy to the host partners, including technical teams, stages and exhibition spaces in the urban environment. As the festival grows, the show goes beyond the local boundaries of the host city and attracts important strategic partnerships in the capital, such as the Sofia Municipality and Sofia Municipal Theatre.

In the archiving phase, power is again concentrated in the leader organisation. At the same time, compared to the creation phase, part of the generated value stems from the activities of the partners, the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences and the Academies of Arts. This work focuses on research and analysis as well as the production of scientific outputs in specialised and periodical publications for a wider audience. Thanks to online-based archives, the results of this phase have a global dimension.

Figure 11. Case 4: Power distribution in the production network of the Varna International Theatre Festival

3.4.5 Dynamics over time

The development of the festival exceeded the preliminary plans of the organizers, and the organisational and programming activities have achieved a new professional level. Nikolay Yordanov explains that the administrative and artistic power has been transferred from the Bulgarian Theatre Association to the Via Fest Foundation, established in 2004.

In the first 3-4 years, the festival had a national scope, later acquired international dimension. However, as the relationship became extremely complex, with the sector becoming more market-driven, we decided that it was not normal for theatre directors to choose the person who would contract with them. In reality, the Association of theatre directors [from which the festival originates] has been almost non-functional, as most of the members (state or municipal theatres) have increasingly divergent interests. Competition and all this led to setting up the Via Fest Foundation in 2004 [...]. The board of trustees includes Asen Terziev, Tsvetana Maneva and myself. (Interview 1)

The Municipality of Varna and the Ministry of Culture maintain their role as strategic partners with financial authority. After the festival became international, new partners in the creation phase joined

(mostly the foreign cultural institutes, embassies and other). After 2007, the need to multiply foreign performances led to the creation of the 'World Theatre in Sofia' in partnership with the Sofia Municipality. In terms of programming, Via Fest has the freedom and the authority to select both national and international artistic content, regardless the financial authority, considering the limitations, explained by Terziev below:

We work with a wide range of professionals whom we consult on the titles. The Bulgarian programme presented must represent a good artistic achievement, and in terms of the international programme it must meet two other important criteria: First, they must be able to connect with the audience's expectation...The whole process of programming content is a kind of game between formed attitudes and provoking curiosity of the audience. The conditions of perception are also of great importance – providing subtitles, possibly in two languages. The third criterion is entirely pragmatic. It has to do with the stages we have and the spaces we can use in Varna. This is the main reason why over the years the individual festival selector has dropped out, because it has happened to like, for example, a performance that turns out to be practically unfeasible on the stages we have here. And one more important criterion - the economic one, because the funds we receive compared to other festivals, even in the region, are still very insufficient. (Interview 5)

The history of the festival has shown that power and value creation in the network undergo development, which leads to dispersion. The funding of the festival is an opportunity for administrative power over the Via Fest Foundation by the Ministry of Culture, the Municipality of Varna and the Municipality of Sofia. This administrative power has proven to be formal because the festival makes its own management decisions. The funding gradually includes sponsorships and grants from the festival's many partners (the British Council, Cervantes Institute, Goethe Institute, Polish Institute, Italian Cultural Institute, Czech Centre, Austrian Embassy, etc.). These cultural centres also provide material support in various forms (e.g. help with the purchase of copyrights, mobility of troupes and productions). This last financial source expands the festival's network and adds to its international image. The total budget of the festival is around 200,000–250,000 BGN, 10–15% of which is private funding from grants and sponsorships. During 2020, the year of COVID-19, the festival happened online, and the funding was about 120,000 BGN.

The source of creative power is the selection of productions, which takes place at the creation stage. Each invited theatre and production becomes branded through its participation in the festival. Our story shows a gradual expansion of the experts involved in the selection – a selector, then the members of the Via Fest Foundation and later the creator of the Showcase module (Art Office Foundation). In the same way, the creators of the festival delegate managerial authority to the theatres whose stages they use in Varna.

Obviously, these transformations in time have made the Festival better and more visible – proof that the International Theatre Festival 'Varna Summer' has acquired the 'European Festival' label - a

European quality certificate, attributed by the platform ‘Europe for Festivals – Festivals for Europe’, initiated by the European Festival Association. In 2017, the festival was among the winners of the ‘remarkable festival’ label, with a nomination for the platform’s award.

3.4.6 Impact

Economic impact

The Varna Summer International Theatre Festival actively collaborates with local cultural institutions in Varna. Performing arts in the city of Varna, Bulgaria, are key for the local cultural ecosystem. As of 2019, though, their main source of funding was the national budget, with about 6.5 million BGN (3 million EUR) per year.³ About 1.5 million BGN (800,000 EUR) of the total funding of performing arts in Varna came from the revenues of these institutions as well as additional funding from the Municipality of Varna.

Of that total of about 4 million EUR, nearly 80% is spent locally for salaries; hence, that revenue flows into the local economy. This traditional funding system has enabled the largest theatre festival in Bulgaria to take place in Varna for 30 years to date.

The organisation and programming of the International Theatre Festival ‘Varna Summer’ technically takes place in Sofia, where the Via Fest Foundation, the lead organisation in the network, is based. Nevertheless, the benefits from the festival’s organisation and implementation are generated predominantly in Varna. Every year Via Fest Foundation (the leader) realizes about 40 events here, which are complemented by up to 10 more events in the capital. The festival uses the local (and at times regional) infrastructure and venues in Varna, which offer the following capacity: 800 seats in the Festival and Congress Centre, 440 seats in the Varna Drama Theatre, 330 seats in the “branch” stage of the Drama Theatre, and 130 seats in the Varna Puppet Theatre. The capacity of the performance spaces is extended by the Regional History Museum and the City Art Gallery, which varies depending on the director’s and scenographer’s concepts and needs. Some events take place in the urban environments with free admission. In Sofia, the main venue is the 350-seats Sofia Municipal Theatre hall, and its 70-seat chamber hall.

Every year the festival in Varna registers about 10,000 visits, of which about a third are free of charge – dedicated to street theatre, conferences, seminars, exhibitions. The average ticket price is 13 EUR. Around 25% of the capacity of events with paid admission are free of charge for official guests, accredited journalists and festival participants.

³ Theatre and Music Production Centre /dramatic theatre and opera/ and Puppet Theatre.

The total budget of the festival in 2019 amounted to about 350,000 BGN (180,000 EUR). The main financial sources are (almost equally) the Ministry of Culture, the Municipality of Varna and the organizers' own income from admission tickets and sponsorships. The total festival budget does not include support through direct funding from the partnerships of foreign cultural centres (those are paid directly for activity). The cost of paying the festival staff is up to 30% of the festival's total budget (100,000 BGN or 50,000 EUR). Yordanov explains the cost and income structure:

We have tried to make sure that the subsidies that come from the Ministry of Culture, the Municipality of Varna, and the international cultural centres involved go to the productions, and that all other costs are covered by us. This means that the ticket revenues cover our activity. I find it very respectable, because public money actually goes to pay the work of artists and festival events, while all the other infrastructure costs, let's call them so, are covered by the revenue that these activities could bring in. (Interview 1)

In addition to the Varna festival, the replica of the World Theatre Festival in Sofia in 2019 is additionally supported by Sofia Municipality, with 65,000 BGN (33,000 EUR), and the Ministry of Culture, with BGN 15,000 (8,000 EUR).

Unfortunately, there is no data on the services offered by the hotels and restaurants. The festival is attended by about 500–800 participants as well as experts and special guests. They stay on average three days in local accommodations, at average hotel accommodation rate of 25 EUR/night, plus about 10 EUR per diem. Vera Stoykova sheds light on the relations with local economy.

All the restaurants around the theatre are partners with the festival and give a discount and everyone eats there. Especially in the evening when after all the performances they gather to talk. The whole centre becomes lively, chatty, fun... A lot of taxis are used... Souvenirs are bought less, but no foreigner has left without buying rose oil or Bulgarian cosmetics. We have such shops which are very popular. (Interview 2)

On that basis, we estimated an average of 2,000 or more overnight stays directly connected to the festival, which is equivalent of 100,000 BGN (50,000 EUR) for hotel accommodation. Another 40,000 BGN or more (20,000 EUR) flow into the local economy from local transport, restaurants and additional services. Most of the above costs are covered by the lead organisation and are included in the total budget of the festival. There are no figures for local services provided to the festival's audience that comes from outside Varna. Nevertheless, Dessislava Georgieva from Varna Municipality is hopeful about the potentials from the festivals for the local economy.

It strikes me that many of the small and medium sized businesses in the city in the restaurant and service industries are starting to show willingness to come together, to be able to be mutually beneficial and that culture and the arts are a very direct route to the people. If all the portfolios come together around the fact that culture, arts and festivals are an

important resource, as it had happened in Edinburgh, that's a perfect example. (Interview 3)

Although based on approximations, the data presented illustrate the contribution of the Varna Summer International Theatre Festival to the entire spectrum of the local economy: consumption, local services, taxes, fees, and so on. The lack of an adequate monitoring and evaluation system prevents a more specific analysis in the contribution of the festival to the local economy.

In terms of the phases of the GVA, the economic contribution of the festival is most pronounced in the production phase and is demonstrated when a large proportion of local services are used.

Social impact

The number of workers involved in the festival is dynamic and varies depending on the activities in the different phases. Six experts are permanently involved. Most of the collaborators are hired in the production and display phase, such as coordinators, organisers, technical teams, interpreters and press-office employees. Their number varies according to the complexity of the specific tasks. In most cases there are between 30 and 50 civil servants and volunteers. Most of them live permanently in the host city, as Yordanov shares:

In terms of staff, we initially had three people on the Foundation Board itself, but we gradually brought on three more people as permanent staff. So the team that is employed year-round is six people, plus a pool of additional contributors for specific campaigns. [...]. During the festival in Varna or in Sofia, dozens of people are involved from the cities themselves - each with their specific expertise. (Interview 1)

The festival uses the professional services of the employees of the two state repertory theatres in Varna (the Theatre and Music Production Centre in Varna and the Varna Puppet Theatre), which employ about 350 people altogether. About 270 of those are employed in creative activities, such as actors, orchestra musicians, ballet dancers, singers, stage designers, directors and choreographers. Together with the administration, technical services and support staff, they form the necessary human capital to ensure a wide range of activities related to the realisation of the festival, including various partnerships. The technical teams and the marketing and publicity units of the drama and puppet theatres are used to the greatest extent as service providers. Individual members of the administration in the local cultural institutes are involved as collaborators in the organisation of the festival. The director of the production centre says:

"We provide a very large part of the technical service of the festival, and the technicians employed are paid extra for their participation in the festival. If the organizers hired outside contractors, it would be much less quality"(Interview 7)

The festival receives significant support for the organisation by the state commercial company, the Festival and Congress Centre in Varna, which is a regional division of the National Palace of Culture in Sofia. The centre has the necessary capacity, and it functions as an open stage for performances, concerts and film screenings all year round. It employs about 40 people.

The network of partners in the exhibition phase is enriched by other regional and municipal cultural institutes in Varna that provide spaces for exhibitions, performances, and other accompanying events (e.g. Regional History Museum, City Art Gallery), that employ a about 120 people (artists, curators, art historians, historians, archaeologists, administration).

Local partner organisations have extensive experience in implementing projects related to socially important causes, such as art-therapy activities, as well as actions for overcoming the negative consequences of drug addiction (Interview 2)

These capacities developed by the local partners to work on social causes, contribute to specific projects related to the festival. The organiser of festival logistics shares:

There was a unique performance from the UK where the participants were in wheelchairs. We had to find a hotel where the troupe could be accommodated with all possible approaches and organisation of their stay. They were all brilliant. It was a unique occasion for me and is my most vivid memory as something completely different. It was also unique as a performance.’ (Interview 10)

The activities aimed at educating audiences with a focus on school and university students, as well as the numerous workshops and conferences during the festival, can also be added to these effects. An objective obstacle to their fuller deployment is the timing of the festival – the end of the school year and the culmination of the student application campaign. The presented effects accumulate most actively in the display phase.

Cultural impact

The most significant cultural impact resulting from the festival is the joint participation of artistic groups from different countries around the world. For Bulgaria specifically, such a forum is an opportunity for meeting and exchange between publicly funded and private theatre formations. As far as Varna is concerned, the festival brings current trends in Bulgaria and world theatre to the local level. Nikolay Yordanov is confident that the festival contributes to regional development. *“If you look what is happening in theatre, you will see that the city besides Sofia, that is implementing the most serious theatre projects, is Varna.’ (Interview 1)*. He is also convinced that the festival has contributes to forming a competent and enlightened audience:

'In Varna an audience has been developed and nurtured over the years by this, as well as by other festivals. I mean here the role of the music festival, of the International Ballet Competition, of the Golden Rose Film Festival, the festival for animation and so on. All this creates cultural audiences with needs. For what we are showing in Varna, nowhere else outside the capital there is a prepared audience to show to.' (Interview 1)

Image 5. Meeting with the team of the London Globe Theatre production of Hamlet, Varna 2014

Source: Via Fest

The interaction of the Varna Summer International Theatre Festival with the abundant festival events in the city brings significant and wide-ranging cultural benefits, not only in terms of creating a common artistic content but also as a system of organisation. The dynamics it brings to the local cultural scene are noticeable by the Varna municipality:

Working for the festival was the first time I met a team like this, that monitors so closely the quality of work in all phases and types of activities for carrying out the events. I have tried to multiply this experience more in the activities of the municipal administration. (Interview 3)

Some of the participants interviewed gave rather unconventional, metaphorical assessments of the festival's impact – for example, that the festival sets perspectives, which in some cases shock and take the local community out of their comfort zone. The festival programme provokes new sensations and

experiences in the public, which are not always perceived in a straightforward way. Visual artist Venelin Shurelov considers the festival as an ‘intruder’ or a ‘conqueror’.

The Varna Summer Festival is an intruder in the city. It is a must have! It is also mandatory to have it and this feeling that a horde of intruders has arrived here and inhabits our shared space. The peculiar thing is that we are hostile to what we don't understand, suspicious when we understand too easily and proud when we decode. It is these three levels that are associated with some degrees of possession. Perhaps this is the connection between Varna and the guests, that they will gain a sense of belonging to the event that is taking place on their territory, when they develop the ability to interpret, to understand, to grasp, to be part of the game of encoding and decoding that is a theatrical event.’ (Interview 9)

Such precedents have far-reaching cultural implications. They help the local community to be more sensitive both to its own identity as well as to be more perceptive to valuable international experiences.

3.4.7 Policy

Over the past decades, Europe’s festivals and performing arts sector has suffered from severe budget cuts. In many countries, including the Netherlands, public subsidies were made increasingly restrictive, forcing festivals and performing arts organisations to become more creative. In order to fund their performances, organisations increasingly started collaborations with private sponsors (EC, 2017). However, in the past two years, the sector has suffered an even harder blow because of COVID-19, when public cultural life in many countries came to a near complete halt. Although little is known about its exact impact, it is clear that the biggest challenge for the festivals and performing arts sector is helping event companies financially recover from the crisis. An important task is to find solutions for the major staff shortages and loss of expert knowledge and skills. These experienced employees are not easy to replace, hence policymakers should support the recovery in the sector. Long-term changes were initiated by the pandemic, and support measures need to be implemented in order to fully optimise support for the sector and to enhance its societal potential.

The case study of Varna Summer International Theatre Festival displays a variety of actors in the field: policy and governance actors (the Ministry of Culture, Varna municipality and Sofia municipality); state, municipal and private theatre companies, and NGOs (Via Fest Foundation, Art Office Foundation); educational institutions (general or specialised arts schools and universities); cultural and creative industries (graphic designers, media, publishing and printing houses, internet providers, etc.); tourism industry actors (hotels, tour operators); and local services (transport, restaurants). This involvement, in turn, makes it possible to understand processes, business models and policies.

The Varna Summer International Theatre Festival is a representative case study also because of its sustainability over a period of almost 30 years. The development of the festival also reflects the turbulent changes in the sector related to the changing socio-economic conditions in Eastern Europe. The political institutions of state and local government have transformed from an authority, to a partner of civic and entrepreneurial initiatives. To these characteristics should be added various global dimensions. The effects of intercultural dialogue and globalisation processes correspond actively with the rapid development of information and communication technologies.

In its development, the Varna Summer International Theatre Festival has integrated a successful business model in creating and developing an array of achievements: its own capacity; diverse networks of partnerships, including political institutions; and sector partners, including festivals from the city, the country, the Balkan region, the EU and the world (North America, Asia, Australia).

The festival, unlike the prevailing practice, focuses not only on promoting performing arts but also on the entire process (i.e. value chain), including the creation of its own productions, co-productions, special modules for new dramaturgy, commitment to the realization of young theatre-makers, debates on important social topics and issues, education and audience development. Over the years, the festival has evolved, improving and enriching its artistic programming, expanding its scope across performing arts genres (including traditional theatre, street performance, crossover concert events, dance theatre, contemporary dance, experimental dramaturgy and many more).

Innovation is important for the Via Fest team – both in terms of programming and contemporary staging. The initiative for live broadcasting the performances of the Royal National Theatre in movie theatres, or the Met Live, are an example. Besides the opportunity to use new technological means, such projects reach out to new audiences.

The COVID-19 pandemic contributed to better capacities for risk anticipation, analysis and mitigation as well as for addressing new challenges; these are key for resilience. The digital edition of the festival in 2020, which presented 10 international productions and offered 72 hours free access for each production, generated 32,000 unique audience visits from around the world. This helped the otherwise local festival, to gain recognition from a large international community as never before.

3.4.8 Conclusions

The role and impact of performing arts festivals go far beyond the cultural and artistic sector. They have undeniable potential to contribute to the development of regions and to add value to the CCS. The absence of clear definitions, well-developed standards and measurable indicators remains an obstacle for tracking their social and economic impacts and their spillovers into other sectors.

A number of possible solutions emerged in the interviews with the Varna Summer International Theatre Festival case study participants. One solution is a firm commitment by the competent public institutions to improve performing arts venues and facilities, including non-conventional spaces and renovating cultural heritage sites and urban environments. The festival could only benefit from multi-annual subsidies, longer-term and predictable planning, clearly defined priorities and evaluation systems by the funding bodies. Such measures would truly enable the sector to thrive.

Arts festivals are increasingly coming into the public policy spotlight. In order to stimulate their development and improve the regulatory framework in which they exist, we suggest the following specific measures:

- Define the term 'festival'. In this respect, festivals need to be perceived as part of the intangible cultural heritage. Stakeholders need to appreciate the impact they have on different aspects of public life.
- At the European level, it is necessary to formulate specific standards for festivals to be included in the Eurostat system.
- In national legislation, festivals should be a subject of a detailed inventory and systemic data collection, which could assess their artistic, social and economic contribution to the formation of gross domestic product.
- In festivals, the implementation of these tasks would enable festivals to take their rightful place in regional and local policies. In this way, festivals would also be able to maximise their potential for regional promotion and international exchange.

PART 4. Conclusions

4.1 Conclusions

Above we consider the production networks of several cases in the festivals and performing arts sector, using the GPN approach. In this sector, like all other CCS, we encountered a huge variety in size, scope, genre, budget, market niche, aims and strategies. Our selection of cases, hence, was an explorative endeavour in mapping the production networks of this key CCS. We selected one large festival in Bulgaria, the Varna Summer International Theatre Festival, and one in the Netherlands, the Lowlands festival. We also analysed the production network of a small, local festival initiated by recent migrants. Furthermore, we unpacked the production network of the modern dance performance *Tell your mom you love your skin* by the Nederlands Dans Theater. Even a small festival and a modern dance work, let alone large multi-day festivals, are quite complex products which necessitate close coordination between many actors.

Even with this small sample, we are able draw a few general conclusions. First, the GPN approach is useful in analysing the festivals and performing arts sector. Unravelling the production networks into different phases does make sense because it shows how the different components come together over time and which actors are involved in these processes. Having said that, as Throsby (2010: 25) has observed, there is no simple, neat sequence in the CCS, and '[t]he apparent linearity of the value chain may be replaced, for some cultural products, by something more akin to a value network, where multiple inputs, feedback loops, and a pervasive 'value-creating ecology' replaces a simple stage-wise process.' This is also what we found in the cases of the three festivals and the modern dance work. The phases creation, production, distribution and exchange with the audience often overlapped. In addition, the realisation of the festivals and the performances were often processes of co-creation requiring constant exchanges.

The Amalyashi Festival is on the other end of the spectrum when compared to Lowlands Festival. Amalyashi debuted in October 2021, with little experience in the Dutch festival sector. It was carried out at three locations that were not directly connected to one another. Visitors bought tickets for individual shows instead of one ticket that gave them access to all shows. The biggest contrast between the festivals may be their business models. While Amalyashi relies on voluntarism, funding, subsidies and external assistance, the other festivals function as a well-oiled efficiency machine, generating financial revenue. This difference shows how it is much harder for new festivals to build this type of knowledge while also being in a cutthroat environment.

Still, there are some parallels to be drawn between the festivals that seem so different. For example, the main goal is to connect the artist and the public. A festival is about opening a space where the public can meet the artist; by doing so on a large scale, a festival attracts a wider audience than a single performance. Another key element that comes forward in both festivals is about the connection

within and between the audience: It is not only about watching a performance and hearing a story; it is about connecting and building bridges with each other.

In the case of the Varna Summer International Theatre Festival, several actors are involved in the creation phase (the Via Fest Foundation, Art Office Foundation, Ministry of Culture, Varna municipality and several foreign cultural institutes). A similar kind of collaboration can be seen in the firms supplying the sound and light for the Lowlands Festival. These were actively involved in designing the setting of the performances and, hence, much more than just subcontractors. The same can be said regarding the *Tell your mom you love your skin* performance where the choreographer and his staff, together with the dancers and the supporting technical staff were all involved in developing the performance. These are, of course, significant findings showing how real-life production networks in the CCS are more iterative and complex than the basic GPN approach suggests. This approach, thus, first opens up the box of the production network and then reveals more intricate patterns

It is important to consider the governance of the network and, more precisely, which actors can be seen as initiating, organising, monitoring and controlling the network. In other words, can we identify lead actors? Complex projects, such as the two large festivals and the *Tell your mom you love your skin*, performance inevitably require some kind of central coordination to bring all the different elements together at the right time and in the right place. In these three cases, we can indeed identify one actor in charge of dealing with the 'motley crew property' (Caves, 2000). The Amalyashi Festival is too small to necessitate a complicated governance structure. The Via Fest Foundation coordinates the Varna Summer International Theatre Festival; MOJO plays that role for the Lowlands festival; the Nederlands Dans Theater organises the network for *Tell your mom you love your skin*. These actors are central in their respective production networks and are involved from production to archiving. The fact that these actors play such a central role does not imply that they are not dependent on dedicated suppliers and strategic partners. In this sense, these networks are based on intensive forms of collaboration.

These forms of collaboration refer to the embeddedness of the production networks. For the festivals and performing arts sector, we can observe the following patterns of embeddedness.

First, with respect to societal embeddedness, all four cases display a strong involvement of the public sector, which sets the rules for festivals and performances. Furthermore, both in the case of the Varna Summer International Theatre Festival and the Nederlands Dans Theater with *Tell your mom you love your skin*, the public sector at the national level is also prominent in providing funding. The respective national governments view these institutions as important not just for internal purposes but also for international cultural reputation. Still, the cases can all be labelled as hybrid in the sense that state, market and civil society actors (volunteers) work together to make each event happen. On a higher level, we can point to the EU regulations, which allow for easy cross-border travel for performers.

Second, in terms of more local or territorial embeddedness, all four cases show strong ties – first and foremost with the local government, which provides facilities for the performances. Lowlands, the Varna Summer International Theatre Festival and the Nederlands Dans Theater have long-standing ties with the Varna municipality, Biddinghuizen and The Hague, respectively. Given the long-term commitment of the lead actors to these places (and vice versa), local ecosystems of catering, hospitality, transport facilities and so on. have developed, thereby further strengthening the anchoring of the events to these places.

Third, assessing the network embeddedness – that is, the linkages between different actors – in the four cases reveals that the key relationships are not so much at arm's length but are firmly embedded in long-term bonds between actors. They understand and trust each other so that complex assignments regarding light and sound can be executed without extensive contracts covering every possibility. Trust reduces transaction costs. The long-term relationships, moreover, foster investments in specific expertise and technology. This has become ever more important with processes of digitalisation, which have fundamentally altered the production process. In the creation, production and exchange phases, digitalisation has introduced special video technologies; experimentation with art forms, such as virtual stages and holograms; and stronger amplifiers and audio speakers to reach larger groups. The well-developed network embeddedness of these projects facilitates these innovations.

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Appendix A. Methodology

A1. Research methodology

Introduction

The general aim of the CICERONE research, and in particular of WP2, is to understand the role of CCS in the local development of EU countries starting from the configuration and dynamics of their global production networks (GPNs). This work package is based on a case study approach combining quantitative with qualitative research. The former is aimed at positioning the sector along a number of dimensions, while the latter will uncover the more in-depth aspects of the GPNs of the selected sectors. While the project adopts a prevailing qualitative, it also envisages secondary data analysis. The case study approach is coherent with the research aim because of its ability to cover both a contemporary phenomenon and its context.

This appendix presents the main methodological issues of the WP2, some of which have been pointed to at the beginning of the reports.

Methodology stands for the systematic examinations of procedures and modalities of explanation that are used for the analysis of empirical data.⁴

In social sciences, empirical research may adopt a descriptive or an explorative logic; however, all research is always informed by a theoretical apparatus, even though the connection between theory and empirical research takes different connotations in the different disciplines/fields. Notably, epistemology draws a distinction between explanation and comprehension. Explanation implies the search for a stable nexus of causality between two (or more) variables, independently from the social and historical context. The underlying assumption is that we should be able to identify universal laws explaining the nature of observations (like in the so-called hard sciences). Comprehension refers to the traditional Weberian conception of understanding the meaning of the action for social actors. Such a meaning is influenced by institutional, normative and cultural dimensions that are spatially and historically specific. Reality is not simply described, but it is read, analyzed and interpreted.

In a situation where universal laws are inapplicable, the logic is to search for empirical generalizations. In order to move towards empirical generalization, social sciences make use of models or typologies starting from Weberian insights. Weber describes ideal types as 'mental constructs, formed by the

⁴ Selvin, H. C. (1958). Durkheim's suicide and problems of empirical research. *American journal of sociology*, 63(6), 607-619.

analytical and one-sided 'accentuation of one or more points of view and by the synthesis of a great many diffuse, discrete, more or less present and occasionally absent concrete individual phenomena, which are arranged according to those one-sidedly emphasized viewpoints into a unified analytical construct'.⁵ Through ideal types, reality is recomposed and synthesized starting from classificatory categories, so to help researchers to identify dynamics and mechanisms that underlie social processes.

Traditionally, empirical research is based on either qualitative or quantitative methods (or both). The distinction between the two has a technical nature: the choice depends by many elements, such as the research questions, data availability or the approach that leads it.

The choice of the method: the case study

Among many qualitative methodologies, case study research investigates into a real-life phenomenon in-depth and within its situatedness and embeddedness context.⁶ Such a case can be an individual, a group, an organization, an event, a problem, or an anomaly.⁷ Contrary to the quantitative logic, the case is chosen because it is of interest⁸ or for theoretical reasons.⁹ Unlike in experiments, the contextual conditions are not delineated and/or controlled, but part of the investigation.

In the case study methodology, the selection of cases is a crucial phase, and generalization of results is mostly based on that. There are two modalities to select case studies:¹⁰ random and information-oriented selection. Random selection is usually chosen to avoid systematic biases in the sample; in such circumstances, the sample size is decisive for generalization.

In social science research cases are generally not randomly selected because it is difficult to in depth explore a huge sample. In this case, the generalizability of case studies can be increased by the strategic selection of cases. Information-oriented selection implies that case studies are selected based on the expectations about their insights into processes, agency, strategies (information content). Cases bring new knowledge either because they have a strategic importance in relation to the general problem or because they help to test the validity of the theory. Case studies allow cross-country comparison: the different contexts shed light on different dynamics related to economic circumstances, national and local regulatory framework, labour market, local culture and know-how,

⁵ Weber, [1904] in Rossi P. (1974)(ed.) *Lo storicismo contemporaneo*. Loescher, Torino: 124-125.

⁶ Ridder, H.G. (2017). The theory contribution of case study research designs. *Business Research*, 10(2), 281-305.

⁷ Burawoy, M. (2009). *The extended case method: Four countries, four decades, four great transformations, and one theoretical tradition*. Univ of California Press; Stake, R.E. (1995). *The art of case study research*. Sage, London; Yin, R. K. (2014). *Case Study Research Design and Methods* (5th ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA

⁸ Stake, R.E. (1995). *The art of case study research*. Sage, London

⁹ Eisenhardt, K. M., & Graebner, M. E. (2007). Theory building from cases: Opportunities and challenges. *Academy of management journal*, 50(1), 25-32.

¹⁰ Flyvbjerg, B. (2006) Five Misunderstandings About Case-Study Research. *Qualitative Inquiry*, 12(2).

and so on. According to Robinson¹¹ the choice of the territory assumed as the basis of the comparison (being it a nation, region or city) should be carefully chosen in relation to the single case study rather than assumed a priori.

Research design and research steps

WP2 is based on a mixed methods approach of investigation. This means using both quantitative and qualitative tools; primary and secondary data allow a complex research design composed by several interconnected research dimensions: an industry description, an analysis for the identification of the case studies and the case studies themselves.

Industry description

Quantitative data was used to have a factual overview of European GPNs in CCI together with literature and desk analysis.

Literature analysis and quantitative (secondary) data were used to explore and describe the features of each industry, its quantitative consistence and its European production network, its role in the European economy, the territorial distribution of its companies and the typical business models.

- 1) Literature review – for each industry
 - a) Configuration of the PN (input-output structure) in industry X
 - b) Prevailing governance typology in industry X (e.g. power relationships, barriers to entry, value adding mechanisms, labour processes/skills ...) + possible governance typologies considering single interfirm relationships
 - c) Key socio-institutional dimensions affecting network configuration/dynamics (e.g. fiscal incentives, property rights, labour legislation, path dependent cultural aspects) at various levels (European, national, regional)
 - d) (possible) Changes over time (e.g. digitalisation, technologies, ---) + possible firms upgrading processes (value capture strategies)
 - e) (possible) National variations and specificities (e.g. the French film industry is very much supported by national funds)

Statistical mapping of production network of CCS in Europe

Statistical data at the EU level (by Nuts 1, 2, 3 if possible) on number of firms, employment, VA, ... relative to the *different network phases* (e.g. creation, production, distribution, etc.) composing the PNs of the 8 selected CCIs.

¹¹ Robinson, J. (2011). Cities in a world of cities: The comparative gesture. *International journal of urban and regional research*, 35(1), 1-23.

Case studies in WP2

One of the strengths of the research lies in the fact that the great variety of case studies share a common unit of analysis. This is the production network of actors, firms, organisation involved in projects, which is very much in line with a whole body of literature on forms of collaboration in the cultural and creative industries. The benefits of a such project-based approach are according to Allan Watson as follows:

“... first it moves beyond [solely] structural analyses to allow for an understanding of the importance of agency in project work; second it allows us to move on from firm-level analyses to develop an understanding of the complex social networks involved in [production networks]; and finally it moves on from research at the meso-level on inter- and intra-firm networks to provide micro-level analyses of project work.”¹²

It enabled the whole research to take into account agency *and* structure as well as their interaction, thereby heeding the view of Powell and Smith Doerr¹³ who conceptualise networks both as relational forms and structural ones.

As anticipated, cases were selected on the basis of their informative power and of the theoretical expectations about their insights. Moreover, two other empirical-based dimensions were taken into account when selecting the case studies, namely, the feasibility of the empirical research and the geographical span of the case studies which are simultaneously located mainly (if not entirely) within the EU limits and cross the borders of a single European country.

Such a choice aims at bringing new knowledge on the contribution of the European CCS to local development, sustainability, social cohesion and (local) identity. Furthermore, as already discussed, an information-oriented selection of case studies increases the generalizability of results.

In details, theoretically based case study selection was grounded on the review of the existing literature on CCS and their organizational forms¹⁴ assuming a novel viewpoint. Three common aspects underlie this choice.

- a) GPNs in CCIs, as in any other industries, are characterized by differential power relations. Powerful actors (the lead firm) are those who drive networks and make things happen: as explained, their ability derives from their control of key resources, namely physical, economic, technological but also social, political and immaterial ones. The control of resources however

¹² Watson, A. (2012). Sociological Perspectives on the Economic Geography of Projects: The Case of Project-Based Working in the Creative Industries. *Geography Compass*, 6(10), 617-631, p. 618.

¹³ Smith-Doerr L, Powell W (2005) Networks and Economic Life. In Neil Smelser and Richard Swedberg, eds. *The Handbook of Economic Sociology*, Russell Sage Foundation and Princeton University Press.

¹⁴ Different disciplinary insights have been used drawing upon the literature in business, economics, sociology, economic geography.

does not automatically imply that the actor is powerful until power is exercised. Rather than being matter of actors' position in the network (more or less marginal actors), power should be conceived as the capacity to concretely exercise control within it. Governance identifies the authority and power relationships that affect how resources – material, financial, human, etc. – are distributed and flow along the chain. Following Gereffi it is possible to distinguish between, two typologies of networks: the producers- and the buyer- driven chains. Governance as drivenness embraces therefore a broad idea whereby governance refers to the whole chain dynamics: this concept is meant to capture the power that lead firms exert over other participants and to highlight its ability to govern the chain by making decisions about where, how and by whom goods/services are produced. In the identification of concrete governance typologies characterising a specific industry, the concept of governance as drivenness is one important aspect.

- b) Relationships between lead firms and the other actors in the network differ across industries due to the particular features of the products/services produced, to the production process and the organization of that specific industry. The configuration and coordination of global production networks are also shaped by the expansion of demand and markets. Goods and services' demand needs to be created and sustained among final consumers and end users (i.e. think about the increased role of merchandising). It is therefore important to satisfy customer pressures, (i.e. price, quality), the so-called time to market (i.e. time imperative) as well as the basic access to the market and to new markets (i.e. in emerging economies). Finally, the choices and strategies of production networks are also influenced by financial considerations, which relate both to firms' activities and to their shift to non- manufacturing ones. A second aspect to consider when selecting concrete case studies should therefore concern issues of product/service complexity, production capabilities, demand dynamics, markets' features, technological content, financial pressures, etc.: as the previous one, this aspect refers more to technical, organizational dimensions and demand, that are shaped primarily by the industries' internal logic.
- c) As underlined, the innovativeness of the CICERONE project lies in the application of the GPNs perspective to the CCIs. Whilst a vast array of studies has concerned the manufacturing industry, considerably less attention has been devoted to the cultural and creative industries. The empirical work required by the project intended primarily to make a contribution to the understanding of the eight industries considered by the project at European level. Nonetheless, the empirical research aimed also to account for the broad institutional context in which production networks operate. Institutions do not only influence chains' dynamics but should be considered constitutive of these networks in ways that are critical for understanding their social and economic consequences: institutions were therefore not be considered external to the networks even though they are not strictly connected to inter-firms' relationships.

For each industry, case studies numbers range between two to four, according to the identified typologies, complexity of the case studies, availability of interviewees and so on.

Case study analysis

The empirical research based on case studies (namely the production network of projects) was carried on through the exploration of the single network-nodes and their relationships. Qualitative data was used to produce novel knowledge in the field and constitute the base for further research.

The explicative power of the selected case studies lies in the fact that the analysis is able to produce a 'substantive' representativeness of the EU CCS rather than their statistical one; in other words, case studies analysis allows understanding dynamics, mechanisms, relationships, etc. useful for explaining the functioning of such industries.

After selecting case studies, the empirical investigation was carried out using interviews, observations, ethnographies, digital ethnographies. The key dimensions of the analysis are: the network configuration and its geographical footprint; the governance dimension (power relations; value creation); the variety of embeddedness forms; the impact on socio-economic development.

As already indicated, production networks are socially and territorially embedded, beyond their organizational embeddedness. Societal embeddedness places economic actions within a multilevel institutional and cultural framework. Territorial embeddedness appreciates the differing ways in which firms are anchored to different places and to its specific resources and features, for instance the local culture, labour forces, policies, raw materials and so on. Ultimately CCS industrial dynamics in Europe was analysed both in their ideal-typical sense (by accounting for the specific industry-level characteristics affecting inter-firm linkages) and with concern to the differentially embedded nature of their economic activities. Attention was paid also to the ways in which actors mobilize and deploy resource, forge alliance, shape regulatory structures through discursive constructions and mechanisms that legitimate the GPN configuration, i.e. eco labels, fair trade, ethical labour, environmentally friendly productions, etc. Consideration was also devoted to any relevant policy (or the lack of it) at the different stages in chain, which may affect the way in which the whole chain is configured. Policy analysis implied to look at different kind of policies, i.e. cultural but also industrial as well as regulatory and trade policies. Additionally, policy and policy environment were addressed in their multiscalar nature.

A unifying matrix focusing on the two key dimensions of power and spatial footprint allowed synthesizing the case study results by conducting a series of comparisons in different contexts. In addition, the systematization in the matrix is designed as a tool for policymakers in support of better CCS-relevant policies.

Research strategy

Preparing the interview

For each node of the production network, interviews were made to all the informed people that were considered suitable to understand the mechanisms at play in the node. The number of interviews was decided by the team according to the availability of interviewees and the information to be gathered. Three or four pilot interviews were recommended in order to recalibrate / reorganise the interview script; in some cases, interviewees were not available for the interview, but they were asked a number of key questions via mail: this solution was adopted if no alternative was possible. Empirically, the field was accessed through a company, which represents a node/phase in the network; starting from that, the whole network (both relations among phases and phases themselves) is explored.

As usual, at the beginning of each interview, the interviewer presented him/herself and presented the research. The interviewee was given a leaflet containing information on the research and its political as well as on the specific role that the EU can play in this field.

After the signature of a consent form on the part of the interviewee, the interviewer started recording the interview. Interviews were done in person or in videoconference when the situation requires. Each case study gathered qualitative data on a number of topics, which are detailed in the next section containing the interview outline:

- The interviewee profile
- The organization profile
- The network configuration
- The governance structure and strategies
- The embeddedness
- Policy
- Contribution to development

Qualitative data gathering

All interviewees allowed recording the interview with digital recorder. Interviews were then transcribed *verbatim*, pointing out emotional status only if particularly relevant.

Each interview was labelled and stored using all the following variables:

- Industry
- # case study
- Phase of the production cycle
- # interview (within the phase)
- Geography (Nuts3)
- # interview (within the industry)

- Date (DD/MM/YY)

Interviews coding

A two-step codification was used:

- 1) Codification of the interview according to the homogeneous excerpts on the basis of thematic areas identified for the research:
 - Network configuration → CODE: NET-CON
 - Spatial organization of the networks → CODE: GEO
 - The governance of the network → CODE: GOVERN
 - Embeddedness → CODE: EMBEDD
 - Institutional conditions → CODE: INSTIT
 - Policy → CODE: POLICY
 - Contribution of the production network to the development of European regions → CODE: EU_DEVELOP
 - Any other relevant issue that we might "discover" → CODE: OTHER
- 2) Codification of all the excerpts in each of the previously identified thematic areas (input-output structure, its spatial organisation, governance, institutional conditions, role in the EU development, other) based on relevant analytical categories.
 - Ex. Mechanisms of value appropriation; modalities of cooperation among organisations; upgrading mechanisms, working conditions, social/cultural embeddedness; any other new element

A2. Interview outline

Profiling the case study

A first step in the interview outline was to profile the interviewee and her or his organization, company, or agency.

Interviewee's profile

Themes to analyse:

- Position within the organization/agency/company/etc.
- Years spent in the position
- Main responsibilities
- Years spent in the organization/agency/company/etc.
- Years spent in the industry
- Years spent in the field
- Competences required for the job
- Any other relevant theme

- What is your job position within the organisation/agency/company/etc.?
- How many years have you been working in this position?
- What are your main responsibilities?
- How many years have you been working in this organisation/agency?/company/etc.?
- How many years have you been working in this industry?
- What are the main skills/competences required for your job?

Organisation profile

Themes to analyse:

- Brief history of the organisation
- Core business
- Legal nature of company
- Employees
- Any other relevant theme

- What does your organization/agency/company/etc. do/develop?
- What is the main activity performed by your company/organization/agency/etc.?
- What is your core business?
- Is your organization/agency/company/etc. independent or is it a part of a bigger company? (if yes) how responsibilities with the headquarter are distributed?
- How many employees does your organisation/agency/company have?
- Can you briefly tell me about your or organisation/agency/company? (*gather some information on its history, key moments, etc.*)

Network configuration

The second step of the interview outline aimed at shedding light on the whole cycle of cultural production from creation to final users (actors involved, roles, geography). In what ways is the industry X articulated/organised? How does the division of labour occur in the industry? Who are the main actors? Their roles? The geography?

The sketch of a diagram together with the interviewee can be a very useful tool at this stage: we suggest to use a large sheet of paper and start with the interviewee in the middle; then add the other organisations/agencies/actors/... involved in the different phases (locate the phases at the corners of the paper). Use this diagram as a map throughout the whole interview.

- Among the projects (services/activities/goods/event) that you briefly presented us, let us consider now the chosen one (possibly it should be one that involves an extended/extra-local/European/international network). Please, help us to identify the whole cycle of cultural production and your role in it.
- Who are the actors that are involved, together with you, in the carrying out of your project (i.e., customers, intermediaries, consumers/audiences, etc.)?

Actors involved

Possible actors involved:

- Artists, composers, designers, creatives
- Producers
- Suppliers, impresarios
- Audience, customers
- Intermediaries, dealers, experts, critics
- Media, influencers
- Archivists
- Any other relevant actor

Themes to analyse for each actor:

- Description of the actors
(Who they are? Big or small organizations/groups, independent, subsidiaries...)
- Role played by the actor in the network
- Type of resources mobilized (financial, economic, reputational, technological resources...)
- Any other relevant theme

- Who do you work with?
- Who are the people that are involved in the realization of the project?
- Who are the suppliers that are involved in the realization of the project?
- Can you tell us more about them?
- (i.e. SME / large organizations, public/private, local/global, independent/subsidiaries, etc.)
- What kind of resources do they mobilize in the project?
- (i.e. a service, an idea, technical or professional knowledge, raw materials, a semi-product, a final product, financial assets, etc.)
- Who are your customers? or your audience?
- Do you sell directly to the final consumer?
- Are there any actors in your business that you would define as intermediaries? Why? For instance, because they help your product/you to be visible, or they “translate” your work for the audience, or they appreciate particularly your work.
- Is there anybody that helps you in promoting your products/projects? (e.g. art curators, advisors, critics, etc.)
- Do they have an impact on your business? How?
- What do they do precisely?
- What does their intermediation consist of?
- Could you give me an example of a situation in which intermediaries were useful to your business?
- How did you come in contact with this intermediary?
- How did they find you?
- Has your relationship with intermediaries changed over time? Why?
- Do media and influencers play a role in your business?
- How do they impact on your activities?
- How do they get to know you?
- Let us consider the social media. Are there any influencers on Instagram/Facebook/etc. that have an impact on your strategies/activities?
- Have your own accounts an impact?

- Do you use them to promote your project?
- Have you or has your organisation got an archive of your projects (creations/services/activities/products)?
- Have you or has your organisation been part of a show/exhibition/etc.?
- Does collecting exist as a practice in your business?
- (If yes), Who are the collectors? Does a collecting market exist?
- Who decides on what will be archived and in which form?
- Have your projects ever been part of a collection?
- Are there any museums/institutions particularly important in your sector that collect major/innovative works?

Spatial organisation

Themes to analyse:

- The geography of the network
- The issue of physical distance
- The management of distance (if relevant)
- The management of communication (if relevant)
- Any other relevant theme

- Where are the actors/organisations of the network located? (Use the diagram to identify actors)
- (consider all the phases of the PN)
- Have you ever experienced any problem due to the distance? (for instance, dealing with something implying face-to-face communication; the need to check a process personally; ...)
- How do you communicate with the different actors in the network?
- Do you need to travel a lot?
- How is the geographical distance managed?

Governance

What kind of relationships govern and regulate the network organization in the Industry X? What are the economic, socio-institutional, political aspects affecting inter-firms' dynamics?

Relations among network organisations

Themes to analyse:

- Type of relationships between actors (formal/informal)
- Decision-making process concerning the project. (who decides, autonomy / cooperation / subordination, participation)
- Existence of standards / conventions to follow
- Resources: type of resources that the interviewee can mobilise, whether they are specific or generic, easy to find or difficult, locally based, ... type of resources that the interviewee needs, whether they are specific or generic, easy to find or difficult, locally based, ...

- What's your role in the network?

- What [actor/organisation x's] role in the network? (Use the diagram to identify actors)
- How do your customers/suppliers/partners/... choose you?
- How did your customers/suppliers/partners/... get to know you?
- What are your relationships with customers/suppliers/partners/... based on?
- (i.e. trust, competences, flexibility, quality, price, uniqueness, etc.)
- Has your relationship with customers/suppliers/partners/... changed over time? Why?
- Has your relationship with your customer(s)/audience impacted on your business in terms of production/profit growth, number of people working in the company/organization/agency/etc., visibility, etc. Could you quantify it?
- Do your suppliers/partners provide you with standard projects?
- Have you ever asked them to customise their products for you?
- Do your suppliers/partners provide special goods/services that are difficult to find?
- Do your suppliers/partners provide special goods/services that only they are able to provide you?
- Have you ever developed a project together with suppliers/partners?
- How do you select your suppliers/partners?
- How did your suppliers/partners get to know you?
- Have you ever had any problems with suppliers/partners? how did you solve them?
- Has your relationship with suppliers changed over time? Why?
- Do you have direct relationships with the consumers/audience of your project?
- (if yes) How do you manage it?
- Does audience/final consumer participate in your creation/production/distribution/exchange/archiving processes? How?
- How important are audience/consumers' preferences/judgments for your projects/business/activity?
- Does their judgment affect your creation/production/distribution/exchange/archiving processes?
- How are your relations with your customers/suppliers/partners/...regulated/governed?
- (i.e. formal agreements, informal accords, individual contracts, codes of conducts, etc.)
- Have you got any exclusive agreement with your customers/suppliers/partners/...?
- Does it include non-disclosure clauses?
- Does it include the use/concession of technologies/knowledge that are protected by (any kind of) agreement that you cannot use/replicate for other processes?
- (If yes) what kind of agreement?
- Who decides how to create/produce/develop/make/provide/etc. the project that you carry out?
- Does your customers/suppliers/partners/...participate in such a process?
- Do you have a say in such a process?
- Has your customers/suppliers/partners/... their own margins of autonomy in such a process?
- Do you have your own margins of autonomy in such a process?
- Can you/your customers/suppliers/partners/... negotiate terms and conditions of the creation/production/distribution/exchange/archiving/etc. process?
- Is there any quality standard to be respected in such a process?
- What are the consequences in case of non-compliance with the contract/standard?
- Do you envisage any kind of reward for your best suppliers? What does it consist of?
- Do you have any knowledge of the destination of the project (service/activity/good) that you produce/ create/develop/make/provide/etc.?
- In your opinion, how easy would it be for you to replace your other customers/suppliers/partners/...with others?

- In your opinion, how easy would it be for your customers/partners/... to replace you with other suppliers/partners?
- What do you/ does your company/organization/agency do better than others in your industry?
- What is your specific asset/advantage with respect to others?
- How important is reputation in your business? What elements are crucial for it?
- How do you build your reputation?
- How do you make yourself/your organization/agency/company known?
- Have there been any crucial moments in your organization' history/your career that have changed your reputation?
- Have there been any people that have been particularly important for your career/your organization' growth?

Price and value

Themes to analyse:

- Mechanisms at play in the price and value formation (decisions, relevant aspects such as brand, status, reputation, production...)
- Actors involved (or excluded) in value/price formation
- Any other relevant theme

- Who decides the price of the project that you exchange with your customers/suppliers/partners/...?
- On the basis of what dimensions?
- (i.e. market position, competencies, reliability, reputation, brand, design, technology, etc.)
- Can you/your supplier(s)/customer(s) negotiate the price? On what basis?
- With respect to such a price do you think that your contribution is adequately rewarded?
- Could you tell us how much it costs the realization of the project that you exchange with your customers/suppliers/partners/...?
- How often do you receive a non-monetary reward for your work? What do you receive instead?
- Does the price of the service/activity/good that you exchange with your customer(s)/supplier(s) allow you to run your activity/business according to legal and social standards? Why/Why not?
- Do you know the final price at which the project (service/activity/good) is sold?
- In your opinion what are the elements that contribute to determine the final price of the project?
- (it might be the price of the final good, the price of the ticket of a concert/show/exhibition but also the price of the whole exhibition/festival)
- Do you think that the final price of the project is appropriate? Why?
- Do intermediaries impact on decisions about the price of your project? How?
- In your opinion does the final price of the good/service reflect its value?
- In which stage of the production cycle (refer to the diagram) is the value of the project mostly created?
- Who are the actors/organisations in the PN that gain the most from the realisation of the project? Why?

Working conditions, labour and collective actors

Themes to analyse (when applicable):

- Profile of the workforce/associates/collaborators/partners
- Recruitment process and wage definition
- Organisation of work
- Presence and role of trade unions in the organisation/agency/company/etc.
- Presence and role of trade unions and/or business/trade associations in the industry
- Any other relevant theme

- Do you have employees/collaborators/associates, etc.?
- How is your workforce composed?
(i.e.: percentage of professionals/consultants/technicians/workers, etc. out of the total, but also percentage of women/men, percentage by ethnicity, etc.)
- How is work organized in your organization/agency/company, etc.?
(i.e.: on projects, regular working time, piece rates, etc.)
- What types of contracts does your organization/agency/company mainly apply to them?
(i.e.: fixed-term contracts, permanent contracts, agency staff, freelancers, consultants and contractors, etc.)
- Do they work mainly full time/part time?
- Where do they mainly work?
(i.e. offices, ateliers, workplaces, at home, in co-working spaces, etc.)
- What aspects do you mainly consider when selecting the workforce?
(i.e. skills, formal training and education, experience, reputation, flexibility, technical knowledge, etc.)
- Do you employ foreign professionals/workers? Why?
- Do you have internships? Do you have any specific agreement with schools/universities in this respect?
- How do you set salaries and working conditions for your workforce?
(i.e.: collective agreements, plant level agreements, informal agreements, individual negotiation, etc.)
- Does your organization/agency/company set any productivity incentives/bonus for your workforce?
- Do workers have a say in the activity carried out by the organization/agency/company?
- Do your workers must respect any codes of conduct?
- Do your workers must respect any non-disclosure agreements/clauses?
- Are trade unions present in your organization/agency/company/etc.?
- What are their main claims?
- Have they ever helped you? When?
- Do they influence your business? How?
(i.e. through the bargaining process, strikes, demonstrations, disputes, etc.)
- Have you had any conflicts with unions recently?
(If yes), Could you tell me what was the issue?
- How did you negotiate your positions?
- What is the role of business associations/trade associations/etc. in your industry? (at different levels: local/regional/national/international)
- Do you participate in some of them?
- (If yes), How is this beneficial?

Skills and knowledge

Themes to analyse:

- Main skills/competencies/resources required in the industry
- Skills/competencies/resources that make the interviewee / organization crucial / important for the network.

- What kind of skills/knowledge/competencies/technologies/etc. are involved in/needed by your production/creative/distribution/etc. process?
- Do you have any specific expertise that makes you irreplaceable to your partners?
- Do you find skill/knowledge/competencies/technologies in the local labour market or do you need to acquire/buy them from abroad/very far from you/in a difficult way?
- Do you provide any training programme to your workforce? Who decides for them?
- Does/do your customer(s) play a role in such a process?
- (i.e.: sending consultants/technicians/skilled workers, organizing training programmes, etc.)

Innovation

Themes to analyse:

- Main innovations for the industry and the specific economic activity
- Impact of innovations on the cycle of production
- Impact of innovations on relationships with partners
- Impact of digitisation
- Any other relevant theme

- How do you keep yourself informed on the latest technologies/innovations/trends/etc. that are relevant for your business?
- (i.e.: fairs, contests, consultants, journals, magazines and sector publishing, etc.)
- What is the most important/recent innovation that has been introduced in your creative/production/ distribution/exchange/archive process?
- (focus on different types of innovation: product, technological, stylistic, in the distribution, ...)
- Who/what urged this innovation?
- How did this innovation impact on your business?
- (Please, explore the different implications of this innovation)
- Did it allow you to develop new organizational capabilities?
- To hire new/qualified workforce?
- To reach other customers or/and enter new/different markets/businesses/activities?
- To acquire new/better capabilities?
- How did innovation impact with your work?
- Have you been asked to acquire new skills?
- How did this innovation modify your relationships with the other actors/organisations of the network?
- Have you ever needed/solicit collaboration with schools/universities/ laboratories/education centres/etc. for developing/learn any innovation?
- (i.e. for finding skilled professionals/workforces and/or for developing new skills/competencies/knowledge)

- Is there any research centre with which you cooperate to research and develop new services/products/ideas? Are they private, public or are they the result of public-private partnership?
- Has digitalisation had an impact on your activity? How?

Embeddedness

Relations between the production network and the region

Themes to analyse:

- Resources that the territory/context offers and relevance for the activity carried out
- Advantages/disadvantages connected to the area
- Role of Institutions
- Policies
- Any other relevant theme

- What kind of resources can this territory offer to your organization/agency/company, etc.?
- (Here's a list of possible items that you may explore: know-how, traditions; logistics; skilled labour; research structures, academies and schools, innovation hubs, incubators; geography and natural resources);
- For instance, with reference to social resources:
- What kind of social resources can the community of this area offer to your company/organization/agency/etc.? (i.e. local work ethos/culture, informal relations, attitudes towards the economy, openness to innovation, diversity, social values, cultural activities, etc.)
- In what ways are they relevant for your activity?
- Do you think that the local community supports your economic activity? (If yes) In what ways?
- Would you say that it is strategic to be here? Why?
- What factors keep you here?
- Has this territory a special reputation in your industry's tradition? How do you benefit from it?
- (i.e. territorial brand that may help your activity?)
- What are the problems of the territory that impact on your organization/agency/company, etc.?
- Do institutions (regional, local authorities, ---) in this territory encourage economic initiatives in your industry? In what ways?
- Do institutions (i.e. region, local authorities, ---) encourage cultural initiatives in this area? In what ways?
- Does the economic and institutional context in which you work help/hinder your activity? How?
- (focus on fiscal requirements, industrial policies, labour regulation, environmental standards, trade policies, etc.)
- Do you think that the existing policies at regional level are adequate to the needs of your organization/agency/company?
- (focus i.e., on innovation policies, labour and tax regulation, incentives, industrial policies, etc.)

- Do you think that the existing policies at national / international level are adequate to the needs of your organization/agency/company?
- (focus on innovation policies, labour and tax regulation, incentives, industrial policies, trade policies, intellectual property right agreements, etc.)
- Has your organization/agency/company, etc. tried to influence policy making?
- Has your organization/agency/company, etc. benefited from policy initiatives developed in industries connected to yours?
- Do you participate in some regional-funded project/initiative?
- In your opinion what should be done at a policy level to promote/help your industry/activity?

Contribution to socio-economic development

Themes to analyse:

- Socio-economic impact of the PN on the region
- Birth/decline of new/traditional job/economic activities connected to the PN
- Birth of new professional/technical schools/courses connected to the economic activity
- Collaboration with institutions/universities/schools
- Participation of the interviewee/organisation in local cultural/social initiatives
- Economic/social/environmental sustainability
- Any other relevant theme

- Does your involvement in a network of (global) activities impact on the economy of the region you work in? In what ways? (i.e.: incomes, employment and wages, local taxation, touristic trends, etc.)
- Has your participation in the network favoured the birth/diffusion/expansion/decline of new/traditional jobs/professionals and/or economic activities connected to it?
- Has your participation in the network favoured any collaboration with universities or local schools?
- Has your participation in the network favoured the birth of new professional/technical schools/courses/etc. connected to your activity?
- Has your participation in the network favoured the development of local cultural and social initiatives?
- (i.e.: festival, fairs, competition and contests, community revitalization programs, urban regeneration, etc.)
- Has your participation in the network favoured the involvement of your organization/agency/company, etc. in the social life of your locality/region? (i.e.: charity initiatives, with prisons, etc.)
- Do you support/promote any local association/organization/initiative/festival/fair/sport club/etc.?
- Are you involved in any local association/club/organisation for the promotion of the local society?
- (i.e. local festival, local fairs, etc.)
- Has your participation in the network contributed to improve the well-being of your workforce's conditions in this region? (i.e.: labour standards, diversity promotion, health and safety, etc.)

- Has your participation in the network contributed to improve the environmental sustainability of your economic activity? (i.e.: introducing cleaner technologies, environmental sound processes, materials, etc.)
- Do you think that your business has contributed to change/improve your region's image/reputation? In what ways? (i.e.: local specializations, brand rent effect, testimonials, etc.)

Concluding session

- In your opinion, how important is your contribution to the production network you participate in?
- How do you think you are contributing to the development of local society?
- What are the main values that inspire your activity/organization?
- How do you imagine this industry in ten years' time?
- (focus on e.g. cultural hybridization, technological innovation, new markets, etc.)
- How do you imagine you/your activity in this industry in ten years' time?